

DEFENDOLOGY

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education and training issues

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- **DEFENDOLOGICAL CHALLENGES**
- **INCLUSIVE EDUCATION**
- **SUPERVISION OF THE SECURITY SECTOR**
- **CRIMINAL PLANNING**
- **HYBRID WARFARE**
- **CUSTOMS POLICY OF THE "BIG"**
- **SPORTS DIPLOMACY AND SECURITY**
- **POLICE MANAGEMENT**

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INTRODUCTION

Defendological Challenges in Contemporary Global Crises

Before you, before us, is the new issue 55 of Defendology journal, the eminent scientific and professional publication dedicated to protection, defense, and security. In this issue, Defendology continues its programmatic orientation as a multidisciplinary journal, bringing you topics that are crucial for understanding contemporary security challenges, risks, and threats. As is already widely known, through the past 28 years of fruitful work and development, the European Defendology Center, as a scientific research society of distinguished academic workers and experts, has become a recognizable brand of Banja Luka, Republika Srpska, and Bosnia and Herzegovina, and is recognizable throughout the entire region. Through our work, we consistently promote a depoliticized, deideologized, professionally and scientifically autonomous approach, without political gossip, in the interest of the common good for all citizens and peoples, regardless of race, faith, or nation. Our approach remains based on scientific discourse: protection + defense = security, which we also promote through the Third Mission of faculty and university development (the first is education, the second is research), and the third is the engagement of academic workers in the community.

In the context of global challenges characterized by populism, autocracy, conflicts, and crime, the world faces uncertainty. Uncertainty is perhaps the word that best describes the state of our country as well. Times are dark, and the steps of populists and autocrats are increasingly clear and loud. We continue to strive to confront contemporary security challenges in our academic way, through carefully selected topics. In doing so, we understand the concept of security in the broadest sense, respecting all sectors and levels of security. We must not forget that security represents a state in which the state finds itself, as an organized part of society, in which the state functions normally but also develops.

The contemporary security paradigm faces a fundamental transformation that transcends traditional concepts of the state-centric approach. In the era of the post-Westphalian order, we witness the proliferation of non-state actors whose influence often transcends formal structures of power. This metamorphosis requires a reconceptualization of the very foundations of security studies, including an ontological reexamination

of the concept of security *per se*. The Copenhagen School, with its concept of securitization, has offered a revolutionary perspective that recognizes the discursive nature of security threats, emphasizing that they are socially constructed through speech acts of authoritative actors. This approach enables us to analyze how certain phenomena transform from the sphere of ordinary political discourse into the domain of existential threats that require extraordinary measures.

The new, fifty-fifth issue of “Defendology” journal brings deep analyses and research through sections that address burning issues of today: Defendological challenges - we offer new perspectives in the science of protection, defense, and security; Inclusive education - we recognize its importance in building a more resilient society; Oversight of the security sector - we explore this topic of exceptional importance for democratic achievements and processes; Criminal investigation planning - we analyze it as a prerequisite for undertaking complex investigative actions and as a response to increasingly complex forms of crime; Hybrid warfare - we deal with challenges that blur the boundaries between peace and conflict; Customs policy of the “great powers” - we investigate its impact on global economic flows and relations; Sports diplomacy and security - we emphasize the role of sport in international relations and promoting global peace; Police Management - Our focus is on managing police organizations through the implementation of Total Quality Management. Thus, before us is a wide range of topics that address issues from the domain of traditional security science and criminalistics, but also issues that, on the wings of modern society’s development, have become an indispensable part of academic debate on protection, defense, and security.

Epistemologically speaking, defendology as a scientific discipline finds itself at the crossroads between positivist and post-positivist approaches. While traditional approaches insist on empirically verifiable indicators of security, critical approaches emphasize the importance of subjective perceptions and culturally determined conceptions of safety. This duality is not a shortcoming but an advantage that enables a holistic understanding of complex security phenomena. Through the prism of critical theory, we reexamine hegemonic discourses that shape our understanding of threats, risks, and vulnerabilities. We pay special attention to emancipatory approaches that place human security at the center of analysis, overcoming reductionist tendencies that reduce security to the military dimension.

The methodological pluralism we advocate enables us to integrate quantitative and qualitative approaches, combining the rigor of statistical

analysis with the depth of ethnographic insights. This synthetic approach is necessary for understanding the multidimensional security challenges that characterize our era. From cyber threats that destabilize critical infrastructure, through climate changes that generate new forms of conflicts, to pandemic crises that redefine the concept of national security, we face phenomena that require interdisciplinary expertise and innovative analytical frameworks.

I take this opportunity to thank all authors who, from the first covers until today, have contributed to the establishment and promotion of our journal. The quality of your work has resulted in an enviable level of citation of *Defendology* by domestic and foreign authors, as well as its presence in citation databases that are nationally, regionally, European, and globally recognized. Your contribution transcends mere academic production; you are architects of new security knowledge that shapes policy discourse and informs practical interventions. Through rigorous peer-review processes and dedication to the highest standards of scientific excellence, together we build an epistemic community capable of responding to the challenges of our time.

We invite you to continue helping us in our endeavor to illuminate the path toward a better, more secure future. Whether the new, coming generation of people will be able to detect the “new technological key” of development, seeking a new way of managing technologies, innovations, and the relationship between freedom and security, or whether they will accept the coming crude rhetoric of hatred and totalitarian violence as inspiration, will determine in which direction the dialogue between state, society, and market will go. Our goal is to create conditions for massive, nonviolent manifestation of free, independent, conscious courage and bravery of new generations that can change humanity in this millennium, and thus improve the situation in B&H for the better, in the interest of all citizens.

In the era of ontological insecurity and epistemological fragmentation, *Defendology* remains a bastion of intellectual rigor and ethical responsibility. Through continuous deconstruction of dominant narratives and construction of alternative perspectives, we strive to contribute to the emancipation of human potential and the affirmation of universal values that transcend particular interests. Our mission is not only to analyze the existing but to imagine the possible; not only to criticize the status quo but to articulate a vision of a more just and secure future for all.

I wish you pleasant and inspiring reading!

Editor in Chief

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DEFENDOLOGICAL CHALLENGES

CONFLICTS AND DEFENDOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF THEIR RESOLUTION

prof. dr Duško Vejnović¹

Slaven Knežević, MA²

Abstract: The article explores the nature of conflicts and possibilities for their resolution through the prism of defendological approaches. Conflicts represent an inherent part of human relations and social structures, and their understanding and management is crucial for maintaining peace and stability. Through analysis of different theoretical approaches and practical experiences, the article focuses on three key aspects: psychosocial dimensions of conflicts, institutional mechanisms for their resolution, and preventive strategies. Defendology, as an interdisciplinary field dealing with the study of defense and security, provides unique insights into ways conflicts can be prevented, managed, and resolved. Research results show that a holistic approach combining psychological, sociological, and political science perspectives is most effective in understanding and resolving conflicts.

Keywords: *conflicts, defendology, conflict management, preventive diplomacy, conflict transformation, security, peace, peacemaking*

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1. INTRODUCTION

Conflicts represent complex phenomena that manifest at different levels of social organization - from interpersonal relations to international disputes (Miall, Ramsbotham & Woodhouse, 2018). Defendology, as a relatively new scientific discipline, seeks to provide a comprehensive framework for understanding and resolving conflicts through integrating knowledge from the fields of psychology, sociology, political science, and international relations (Sandole, 2017). The significance of this approach is becoming increasingly important in the contemporary world characterized by growing complexity and interdependence of social systems. The theoretical framework of defendology rests on the assumption that conflicts are a natural part of human interaction, but that their destructive potential can be reduced through adequate understanding of their causes, dynamics, and transformation mechanisms (Galtung, 2020). The approach transcends traditional partial approaches that focus on only one aspect of conflict, instead offering an integrated perspective that takes into account all relevant factors (Lederach, 2019). Contemporary research in the field of conflicts shows that the most successful approaches are those that combine theoretical knowledge with practical field experiences (Wallenstein, 2019). The defendological approach does exactly that - it connects academic analyses with practical implementation strategies, resulting in more efficient methods of conflict resolution (Kriesberg, 2017). Through this article, key aspects of the defendological approach to conflicts will be analyzed, with special emphasis on psychosocial dimensions, institutional mechanisms, and preventive strategies.

2. PSYCHOSOCIAL DIMENSIONS OF CONFLICTS

Psychosocial dimensions of conflicts represent a complex set of factors that include individual psychological processes, group dynamics, and broader social influences (Burton, 2018). Understanding these dimensions is crucial for developing efficient conflict resolution strategies, as it focuses on deeper causes of tensions instead of just their manifestations. At the individual level, psychological factors such as threat perception, need for security, identity, and cognitive distortions play a central role in the emergence and escalation of conflicts (Burton, 2018). Theories

of social identification explain how individuals construct their identity through group membership and how this process can transform into a source of intergroup conflict (Pruitt & Kim, 2017). When individuals feel threatened in their identity or status, they are inclined to engage in conflictual behavior as a way of protecting their interests.

Group dynamics add additional complexity to this process. Phenomena such as groupthink, group polarization, and intergroup prejudice can significantly influence how conflicts develop and persist (Jeong, 2018). Research shows that groups often make more extreme decisions than individuals, which can lead to escalation of conflicts that could otherwise be resolved through reasonable compromises (Zartman & Faure, 2020). Social context also plays a key role in shaping conflicts. Socioeconomic inequalities, cultural differences, historical traumas, and lack of resources can create fertile ground for the emergence and maintenance of conflicts (Ramsbotham, Miall, & Woodhouse, 2021). The defendological approach recognizes the importance of these structural factors and seeks to develop strategies that address not only symptoms but also the causes of conflicts (Galtung, 2020). The emotional dimension of conflicts is often neglected in traditional approaches, but defendology recognizes it as crucial (Lederach, 2019). Emotions such as fear, anger, pride, and shame can significantly influence how parties in conflict perceive the situation and react to it. Understanding and managing these emotions can be key to successful conflict resolution (Fisher & Ury, 2019).

3. INSTITUTIONAL MECHANISMS FOR CONFLICT RESOLUTION

Institutional mechanisms represent formal and informal structures through which conflicts can be prevented, managed, and resolved (Walsten, 2019). Such mechanisms function at different levels - from local communities to international organizations - and represent key elements of the defendological approach to conflicts. Legal frameworks and judicial systems represent the most formal institutional mechanisms for conflict resolution. They provide a structured approach to dispute resolution through the application of legal norms and procedures (Kriesberg, 2017). However, limitations of the traditional judicial approach, such as rigidi-

ty, lengthy processes, and focus on punishment instead of solving basic problems, have led to the development of alternative dispute resolution methods. Mediation and arbitration represent key alternatives to traditional judicial proceedings. Mediation, as a process in which a neutral third party helps disputing parties reach a mutually acceptable solution, has proven particularly effective in resolving conflicts where preserving relationships between parties is important (Fisher & Ury, 2019). Arbitration, on the other hand, provides a more structured approach where a third party makes binding decisions (Burton, 2018).

At the international level, organizations such as the United Nations, regional organizations, and non-governmental organizations have developed sophisticated mechanisms for preventive diplomacy, peacemaking, and peacebuilding (Miall, Ramsbotham, & Woodhouse, 2018). Such mechanisms include early warning systems, situation monitoring missions, high-level mediation, and peacekeeping operations (Knežević, 2024). Restorative justice represents a relatively new approach that focuses on healing damage caused by conflict instead of just punishing the offender (Sandole, 2017). This approach is particularly relevant for conflicts that have left deep consequences on communities and can be integrated into defendological conflict resolution strategies. Conflict prevention through institutional mechanisms includes developing early warning systems, strengthening rule of law, promoting democratic processes, and working on structural reforms that address basic causes of conflicts (Walsten, 2019). Preventive approaches are often less spectacular than reactive measures, but can be significantly more efficient in long-term problem solving (Zartman & Faure, 2020).

4. PREVENTIVE STRATEGIES AND CONFLICT TRANSFORMATION

Preventive strategies represent a proactive approach that focuses on identifying and addressing potential sources of conflicts before they escalate into open disputes (Galtung, 2020). This approach, central to defendological theory and practice, is based on the assumption that conflict prevention is both economically and humanitarily more efficient than their reactive resolution. Early warning systems represent a key compo-

ment of preventive strategy. Systems use various indicators - economic, social, political, and security - to identify situations that may lead to conflicts (Ramsbotham, Miall & Woodhouse, 2021). Modern technological tools, including big data analysis and artificial intelligence, enable more precise monitoring and prediction of potential conflicts.

Conflict transformation is a comprehensive approach that seeks to change structural and relational aspects of conflicts in a way that enables sustainable positive changes (Lederach, 2019). Unlike conflict resolution which focuses on immediate problem solving, conflict transformation seeks to address basic causes and create conditions for long-term peace. Peace education represents a key preventive strategy that focuses on developing skills and attitudes needed for peaceful conflict resolution (Jeong, 2018). This includes critical thinking, empathy, communication skills, and understanding diversity. Peace education programs are implemented at all levels of the educational system, from elementary schools to universities (Burton, 2018). Economic preventive strategies focus on addressing structural inequalities and economic frustrations that can lead to conflicts (Kriesberg, 2017). This includes developing aid programs targeted at high-tension areas, promoting economic development, and creating economic incentives for peaceful behavior.

Civil society building represents another key preventive strategy. Strong civil societies with active non-governmental organizations, independent media, and civic initiatives can serve as buffer zones between different groups and help resolve tensions before they escalate into open conflicts (Sandole, 2017). Cultural and interfaith initiatives focus on promoting understanding and tolerance between different cultural and religious groups (Pruitt & Kim, 2017). These initiatives can include intercultural dialogues, joint projects, and personal diversity as a source of strength instead of division. International cooperation in conflict prevention includes information sharing, coordination of policy responses, and development of joint strategies (Wallensteen, 2019). Regional organizations have a particularly important role in this process as they often have better understanding of local contexts and greater legitimacy in intervention (Miall, Ramsbotham, & Woodhouse, 2018).

5. DEFENDODOLOGY AS A NEW PARADIGM IN CONFLICT STUDIES

Defendology, as a relatively new scientific discipline, represents a revolutionary approach to understanding and resolving conflicts through integrating knowledge about protection, defense, and security. Professor Dr. Duško Vejnović, as one of the main protagonists in the development of this discipline, defines defendology as a science that seeks to provide a “unique systemic approach” to studying basic phenomena in the field of protection, defense, and security (Vejnović, 2021). According to Vejnović’s conceptual framework, defendology is based on the formula protection + defense = security, where each of these elements represents a key component of the entire system (Vejnović, 2021). This approach transcends traditional partial approaches that focus on isolated aspects of security, instead offering a comprehensive perspective that connects different scientific disciplines into a unified whole.

Basic principles of defendology rest on the assumption that security is “one and indivisible,” and that the protective-defensive function must be “comprehensive and inseparable” (Vejnović, 2021). This holistic approach enables better understanding of complex interrelations between different factors that influence the emergence and development of conflicts, as well as development of more efficient strategies for their resolution. The defendological perspective is particularly relevant in the contemporary context where traditional security concepts are expanding and transforming. Vejnović emphasizes that protection refers to “identification of conditions under which various entities are threatened,” as well as their “reduction to the extent that does not threaten the achieved level of security” (Vejnović, 2021). This proactive approach focuses on prevention and early warning instead of just reactive measures.

Practical application of defendological principles in conflict resolution includes developing integrated strategies that combine preventive, protective, and defensive elements. This approach is particularly important in the context of contemporary hybrid threats and asymmetric conflicts where traditional security mechanisms are often inadequate. Defendology also represents a significant contribution to the international community of peace and security studies, providing a new framework for

understanding complex security challenges of the 21st century. Through integration of different disciplinary perspectives, defendology enables development of innovative approaches that can more efficiently respond to contemporary security challenges (Vejnović & Obrenović, 2019).

The defendological approach to conflicts represents significant progress in understanding and resolving complex social tensions (Galting, 2020). Through integration of psychosocial, institutional, preventive dimensions and the defendological paradigm, this approach provides a comprehensive framework for addressing conflicts in a way that not only solves current problems but also establishes foundations for long-term peace and stability (Lederach, 2019). Psychosocial dimensions of conflicts reveal the complexity of human motivations and behaviors in conflictual situations (Burton, 2018). Understanding individual psychological processes, group dynamics, and broader social factors (Knežević, 2024) enables development of targeted interventions that address basic causes of conflicts instead of just their symptoms (Pruitt & Kim, 2017). This approach recognizes that conflicts are often the result of deeper underlying needs and fears, and that their permanent resolution requires addressing these basic problems.

Institutional mechanisms represent the structural framework through which conflicts can be efficiently managed and resolved (Wallensteen, 2019). From traditional judicial systems to innovative approaches such as mediation and restorative justice, these mechanisms provide different options for different types of conflicts (Fisher & Ury, 2019). International organizations and regional structures also play a key role in providing support and resources for resolving more complex conflicts (Miall, Ramsbotham & Woodhouse, 2018). Preventive strategies and conflict transformation represent perhaps the most important contribution of the defendological approach (Kriesberg, 2017). Instead of waiting for conflicts to escalate and then reacting, this proactive approach seeks to identify and address potential problems in early stages. Conflict transformation goes a step further, seeking to create positive changes that will enable sustainable peace (Sandole, 2017). Defendology, as a new paradigm in conflict studies, represents perhaps the most significant contribution to contemporary understanding of security challenges (Vejnović, 2021). Vejnović's approach that

integrates protection, defense, and security into a unified whole provides a theoretical and practical framework that transcends limitations of traditional disciplinary approaches. The holistic model enables better understanding of complex causes of conflicts and development of more efficient strategies for their resolution (Knežević, 2025).

Integration of four key approaches - psychosocial, institutional, preventive, and defendological - through a unified framework provides a holistic perspective that is necessary for efficient resolution of contemporary conflicts (Jeong, 2018). Future work in this field should focus on further development of practical tools and strategies, strengthening institutional capacities, and promoting a culture of peace at all levels of society (Ramsbotham, Miall & Woodhouse, 2021). The defendological approach to conflicts is not just an academic exercise but a practical framework for creating a more peaceful world (Zartman & Faure, 2020). Through combination of theoretical understanding with practical applications, this approach has the potential to significantly contribute to reducing caused conflicts and promoting sustainable peace and development.

6. TECHNOLOGICAL CHALLENGES AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN CONFLICT MANAGEMENT

Revolutionary changes in the field of technology fundamentally transform the ways conflicts manifest, develop, and are resolved in the 21st century. Artificial intelligence, machine learning, big data analysis, and autonomous systems are becoming an inseparable part of the contemporary security landscape, creating new possibilities but also unexpected challenges for conflict management. Application of artificial intelligence in early conflict detection represents one of the most significant advances in preventive defendology. Machine learning algorithms are capable of analyzing enormous amounts of data from various sources - social networks, economic indicators, climate changes, migration flows - and identifying patterns that may indicate increased risk of conflict outbreak. Such systems can predict potential flashpoints with far greater precision than traditional analytical approaches.

Automated platforms for media and social network monitoring enable continuous tracking of hate speech, disinformation, and propaganda campaigns that often precede conflict escalation. Natural language processing algorithms can detect subtle changes in public discourse that signal growing tensions between different groups. Technological solutions provide decision-makers with valuable insights about conflict dynamics in real time. Blockchain technology opens new possibilities for transparent and immutable documentation of human rights violations, war crimes, and other forms of violence during conflicts. The decentralized nature of blockchain makes it resistant to manipulation and censorship, which can be of crucial importance for future justice and reconciliation processes. Smart contracts can automate implementation of peace agreements and ensure compliance with agreed obligations.

7. CONCLUSION

Analysis of defendological aspects of conflict resolution through the prism of contemporary theoretical and practical approaches reveals the complex nature of this issue and the need for a multidisciplinary approach. This article has sought to provide a comprehensive picture of possibilities that defendology, as a new scientific paradigm, offers in the domain of conflict resolution and transformation. Research into psychosocial dimensions of conflicts shows that understanding deep psychological processes and social dynamics is crucial for efficient management of conflictual situations. Individual and group motivations, emotions, and perceptions represent the foundation on which conflicts are built, but simultaneously the basis for their constructive resolution. This insight imposes the need for future approaches to conflict resolution to pay greater attention to psychological aspects, not just formal procedures. Institutional frameworks for conflict resolution have proven to be irreplaceable elements in the process of their transformation. However, the efficiency of these mechanisms depends on their ability to adapt to the specificities of each conflict. Traditional judicial approaches, although important, must be supplemented by alternative methods such as mediation, arbitration, and restorative justice in order to achieve sustainable solutions.

The preventive approach represents perhaps the most significant contribution of contemporary defendology to the field of conflict management. The possibility of early recognition of potential sources of conflicts and proactive action before their escalation can significantly reduce social costs and human suffering. This paradigm requires systemic changes in the way societies approach security challenges. Defendological theory of prof. dr Duško Vejnović represents a revolutionary approach that integrates protection, defense, and security into a unified scientific discipline. This synthesis enables holistic understanding of conflicts that transcends traditional fragmented approaches. Vejnović's formula "protection + defense = security" provides a practical framework for developing integrated strategies that can more efficiently respond to contemporary security challenges. Contemporary conflicts are characterized by increasing complexity that stems from globalization, technological changes, and evolution of social structures. New challenges require innovative approaches that can cope with hybrid threats, asymmetric conflicts, and interdependencies that characterize the contemporary world. The defendological approach, through its multidisciplinary nature, represents a response to these needs.

Practical application of defendological principles requires significant investments in education, institutional building, and international cooperation. A culture of peace must be developed at all levels of society - from elementary schools to universities, from local communities to international organizations. Only through such a comprehensive approach can lasting results be achieved. The future of defendology lies in its ability to continuously evolve and adapt to new challenges. Integration of new technologies, such as artificial intelligence and big data analysis, can significantly improve capacities for early warning and conflict prevention. At the same time, it is necessary to maintain focus on human aspects of conflicts and the needs of people affected by them. The defendological approach to conflicts represents more than an academic discipline - it is a practical call to action for creating a safer and more just world. Through combination of scientific rigor with practical applicability, defendology can make a significant contribution to global efforts for building sustainable peace. The success of this approach will depend on the readiness of the scientific community, practitioners, and decision-makers to accept its complexity and invest in its further development.

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INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

SOCIAL INCLUSION OF CHILDREN WITH DISABILITIES THROUGH THE LENS OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION THEORIES IN PRESCHOOL INSTITUTIONS

ma Milica Palačković¹

Abstract: This paper explores social inclusion and support for preschool-aged children with disabilities in Bosnia and Herzegovina. Children with disabilities often face numerous barriers that hinder their equal participation in social activities. Focusing on preschool institutions as key actors in the process of social inclusion, the paper analyzes current practices, challenges, and opportunities for improving support for children with disabilities. Through a review of available sources, official statistical data, and existing research, the paper provides deeper insights into the experiences and needs of children with disabilities. Special attention is given to the role of preschool institutions in promoting inclusive education and creating a stimulating environment that enables every child to develop their full potential. The theoretical framework of this study is based on key social work theories that explain inclusion and social protection, including the theory of social justice, ecological theory, empowerment theory, and systems theory. These theories provide a comprehensive understanding of the challenges faced by children with disabilities and their families, as well as the ways in which society can respond to their needs. This paper contributes to a better understanding of the complexities of inclusive education and offers guidelines for improving practices in preschool institutions, emphasizing an integrated approach to supporting children with disabilities and their families within the context of social protection.

Keywords: social inclusion, preschool-aged child, disability, preschool institution, social work theories.

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INTRODUCTION

Children with disabilities represent one of the most marginalized groups in the Republic of Srpska and Bosnia and Herzegovina. These children are often part of the most vulnerable and impoverished segments of the population, with limited access to educational and healthcare institutions. The term “children with disabilities” encompasses children with long-term physical, intellectual, mental, sensory, and other impairments who, due to various barriers, face difficulties in equal participation in society alongside their peers.

From a social work perspective, this reality highlights the need for developing social approaches that will enable children with disabilities to achieve greater inclusion and equality in all social processes, with appropriate support and integration. Each child is a unique individual with their own developmental path, which is why a multidisciplinary team, trained to recognize, develop, and evaluate measures and procedures aimed at meeting developmental needs, is essential. Today, the idea of inclusive education and the full inclusion of children with disabilities in all spheres of social life is increasingly prominent, regardless of the degree of disability (Vukajlović, 2010). In both global literature and practice, inclusion is seen as a process designed to ensure social participation for every individual. Social inclusion and support for preschool-aged children with disabilities play a key role in achieving their holistic development and well-being, enabling them to progress and reach their full potential (Vukajlović, Mešalić, 2021). The social inclusion of children with disabilities can also be viewed through the lens of ecological systems theory (Bronfenbrenner, 1979), which emphasizes how various environmental levels—family, preschool institutions, community, and societal norms—shape a child’s opportunities for development and participation. In this sense, inclusion is not just a matter of educational policy but a broader social approach that entails removing barriers in all aspects of a child’s life. Contemporary discussions on inclusive education highlight various approaches to its interpretation. Cerić (2008) states that inclusive education can be viewed as a concept, an educational policy, and even as an evolving, unfinished theory. According to the theory of scientific revolu-

tions (Kuhn, 1962), inclusive education can be seen as a new paradigm in pedagogy, requiring a radical shift in how education is perceived. At the same time, critical theory emphasizes inclusion as a means of social justice and the emancipation of marginalized groups (Freire, 1970). Over the past three decades, interest in preschool education has been growing rapidly, not only in the European Union and developed countries but worldwide. Before this period, preschool education was primarily viewed as a service whose main function was child care while parents worked. However, new scientific findings have fundamentally changed previous understandings of early childhood development. Traditional views that children in the preschool period only need basic care and nutrition have been abandoned. There are evident differences between children who have been adequately stimulated and those who have not grown up in an encouraging environment during their preschool years. The experiences and stimuli to which a child is exposed in early childhood significantly influence their cognitive and emotional development, and later, these effects are difficult to alter.

From this, it can be concluded that the period from birth to six years represents the foundation of a person's entire development and life: academic success, cognitive and emotional growth, health status, curiosity and willingness to learn, as well as relationships with others and society. All these and other characteristics of an individual are shaped during the first six years of life. For these reasons, children with disabilities must be provided with equal conditions for early learning, growth, and development, all aimed at shaping their personalities and ensuring their future progress (Ministry of Civil Affairs of BiH, 2016).

Protection of Persons (Children) with Disabilities in International Frameworks and Domestic Legislation

Key international documents concerning the rights of persons with disabilities were adopted relatively late compared to other international human rights instruments.

The United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) was adopted on December 13, 2006, with the aim of pro-

moting, protecting, and ensuring the equal enjoyment of all human rights and fundamental freedoms by persons with disabilities (Gadžo-Šašić, 2020). All state parties to this Convention are obligated to take measures to ensure that children with disabilities fully enjoy all human rights and fundamental freedoms on an equal basis with other children. In all activities concerning children with disabilities, the best interests of the child must be a primary consideration (Article 7). Furthermore, all state parties are required to guarantee children with disabilities the right to freely express their views on all matters affecting them. Their views must be given due weight in accordance with their age and maturity, on an equal basis with other children, and they must be provided with appropriate assistance in expressing those views, in line with their disability and age (UN Convention on the Rights of the Child, 2006). Another crucial international document addressing children's rights is the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC), adopted by the UN General Assembly in 1989. This Convention establishes universal standards that must be guaranteed to every child. It is the only international instrument that treats the child as a subject of rights rather than merely an individual in need of protection. The CRC consists of 54 articles, with the Preamble explaining the rationale for its adoption. Articles 1 to 46 define the concept of a child (a person under the age of eighteen) and outline the obligations of states upon ratification. Articles 42 to 45 specify monitoring procedures for the Convention, while Articles 46 to 54 contain formal provisions regarding its entry into force (UN Convention on the Rights of the Child, 1989).

According to Gavrilović (2005), Article 23 of the CRC is particularly significant for children with developmental disabilities, as it states that:

- “State parties recognize that a mentally or physically disabled child should enjoy a full and decent life, in conditions that ensure dignity, promote self-reliance, and facilitate the child’s active participation in the community.”

- “State parties recognize the right of the disabled child to special care and shall encourage and ensure, within available resources, the provision of assistance to eligible children and those responsible for their care, upon request and in accordance with the child’s condition and the financial capabilities of their parents or caregivers” (pp. 385-386).

When analyzing Bosnia and Herzegovina's legal framework as a country striving for European integration and the development of a society that respects fundamental human rights and freedoms while prohibiting discrimination, it is necessary to highlight key national documents relevant to persons with disabilities and children with developmental difficulties. The first document introducing a new human rights-based approach to disability, grounded in the social model, was the Policy on Disability in Bosnia and Herzegovina, published in the Official Gazette of Bosnia and Herzegovina in 2008. Based on this document, an operational strategy was developed: The Strategy for Equalization of Opportunities for Persons with Disabilities in the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina (2011–2015). Since the implementation period for this document has ended, the Government of the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina appointed a working group, consisting of representatives from all relevant sectors and organizations for persons with disabilities, to draft a new strategy: The Strategy for the Advancement of Rights and Status of Persons with Disabilities in the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina (2016–2021) (Gadžo-Šašić, 2020). In Republika Srpska, the rights of persons with disabilities are prescribed by the Constitution of Republika Srpska, which, as the highest legal act, prohibits all forms of discrimination, including discrimination against persons with disabilities. According to the Constitution and the law, all individuals are equal. A crucial step in legally regulating the status of persons with disabilities was the adoption of the Strategy for the Advancement of the Status of Persons with Disabilities in Republika Srpska (2017–2026).

However, achieving full social equality for persons with disabilities requires the engagement of all societal institutions. The legal framework in Bosnia and Herzegovina reflects both the medical and social models of disability. While the medical model emphasizes the individual characteristics of the child as the basis for categorization and support, the social model views disability as a consequence of societal barriers that limit inclusion and participation. An analysis of existing laws reveals that, although inclusive policies are formally in place, their implementation still reflects a medical approach, relying on diagnostic criteria and specialized programs rather than ensuring full inclusion.

Definition and Classification of Children with Disabilities

Throughout history, society's attitude toward children with disabilities has changed significantly. In early communities, such children were often considered unproductive, as their disabilities prevented them from performing the tasks expected of them. In Sparta, newborns with disabilities were killed and regarded as a form of divine punishment. It was not until the Age of Humanism and the Renaissance that these children became more visible, and during the Enlightenment, the idea of educating children with disabilities alongside their peers emerged. However, it was only after World War II that awareness truly developed regarding the possibility of a dignified life for persons, including children, with disabilities (Gadžo-Šašić, 2020).

A variety of definitions exist in the literature to describe disability. However, one of the most comprehensive is found in Article 1 of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD), which defines persons with disabilities as individuals with long-term physical, mental, intellectual, sensory, or other impairments who, due to various barriers, experience difficulties in participating in society on an equal basis with others (UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, 2006). From this definition, it is evident that the focus is not on the individual's impairment but rather on the societal barriers that prevent them from achieving equal participation in society.

One of the most modern classifications of disability is the one adopted by the European Union, which is among the few classifications that explicitly include autism and autism spectrum disorder as disabilities. According to the EU classification, the following types of disabilities exist:

- Sensory impairments
 - Visual impairments (blindness and low vision)
 - Hearing impairments (deafness and hearing loss)
- Intellectual disability (previously referred to as “mental retardation,” a now outdated and inappropriate term)
- Physical disability

- Causes of physical disability (paraplegia/quadriplegia, cerebral palsy, muscular dystrophy, amputation, arthritis, multiple sclerosis, poliomyelitis, spina bifida)

- Mobility impairments (difficulty walking, mobility aided by a cane or crutches, or reliance on a wheelchair)

- Autism spectrum disorder (ASD)
- Multiple disabilities (Gadžo-Šašić, 2020).

When examining Bosnia and Herzegovina, differences in the understanding of disability can be observed across its entities. In the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina, the Law on the Basics of Social Protection, Protection of Civilian War Victims, and Protection of Families with Children categorizes 24 types of disabilities and impairments in children and adults, grouped as follows: blind and visually impaired children; deaf and hard-of-hearing children; children with speech, voice, and language disorders; children with physical impairments and permanent physical developmental difficulties; children with mental/intellectual developmental difficulties (mild, moderate, severe, and profound intellectual disabilities) and children with combined impairments (multiple disabilities). In Republika Srpska, the Law on Social Protection, adopted in 2012, defines seven categories of disability: children with visual impairments; children with hearing impairments; children with speech, voice, and language disorders; children with physical impairments and chronic illnesses; children with intellectual disabilities; children with multiple disabilities and children with other impairments that lead to difficulties in psychomotor and sensory development.

In Brčko District, the concept of disability is defined by the Law on Social Protection, specifically in Article 13, which states that a minor with a physical or mental developmental impairment is considered an individual with visual or hearing impairments, speech or voice disorders, physical impairments, intellectual disabilities, or multiple disabilities (UNICEF, 2017). Despite Bosnia and Herzegovina being a signatory to the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, there is still no unified definition of a person with a disability, and different terminologies are used across various sectors and legal frameworks.

Theoretical Foundation of Educational Inclusion within Social Inclusion

Educational inclusion is one of the key aspects of broader social inclusion, with its fundamental goal being to ensure equal access to education for every child, including children with disabilities. According to Stubbs (1998), educational inclusion is a strategy aimed at fostering an inclusive society where all individuals, regardless of gender, age, abilities, ethnicity, or difficulties, can participate and contribute. Educational inclusion does not only encompass the physical presence of students in educational institutions but also the creation of learning environments that provide equal access to resources and ensure emotional and intellectual support, thereby enabling every child to reach their full potential.

For the development of educational inclusion, it is crucial to consider theories and approaches that facilitate its implementation in educational systems. Clough and Corbett (2002) identify multiple theories of inclusive education, emphasizing “five key perspectives” that address the needs of different groups, including children with disabilities, as well as the socio-cultural and economic barriers that hinder full participation in educational processes. The following perspectives represent various theoretical frameworks and approaches to inclusive practice and educational policy:

- **Deficit Perspective** – This perspective assumes that learning difficulties and developmental challenges stem from individual deficiencies, whether congenital or acquired. In this model, inclusion is seen as a process of adapting the child to the system rather than modifying the system to meet the child’s needs. This perspective is now widely criticized as it fails to account for social and educational factors that influence a child’s success.

- **System Response Perspective** – This approach is based on the idea that the causes of children’s exclusion from education do not lie solely in their individual characteristics, but also within the educational system itself. It draws attention to how structures, policies, pedagogical practices, and the organization of preschool institutions can disproportionately contribute to the marginalization of certain children.

- **Social Justice Perspective** – This perspective emphasizes that barriers to inclusion result from social injustice, discrimination, and systemic inequalities. Here, educational inclusion is viewed as part of a broader struggle for human rights and social justice, where the educational system must ensure equal opportunities for all, regardless of social, economic, or physical obstacles.

- **Critical Pedagogy Perspective** – This perspective analyzes education through the lens of power and hegemony. Inclusive education, in this context, is seen as a tool for empowering marginalized groups, where children are not passive recipients of knowledge but active participants in their education and social transformation.

- **Political and Economic Factors Perspective** – This perspective highlights how broader social, economic, and political factors shape educational policies and inclusion opportunities. Poverty, unequal resource distribution, and political decisions directly impact children’s ability to access quality education.

Each of these perspectives provides a different insight into the challenges and opportunities of inclusive education. Their combination enables a more comprehensive approach to developing inclusive educational policies and practices. As a specific subfield within the broader theory of education, the theory of inclusive education holds great significance, as its goal is to ensure full participation of all members of society, regardless of their specific needs. In this regard, Primorac (2003) considers the theory of inclusive education to be an unfinished theory that is still in development. He emphasizes the need to precisely define inclusive education as part of general education and to clearly determine its scope of application. This is crucial for shaping educational policies that are suitable for all students, particularly those with specific needs. In context social work, educational inclusion plays a significant role in the social integration and empowerment of vulnerable social groups. The theory of empowerment, one of the fundamental approaches in social work, highlights the need for actively involving all individuals in the educational process and developing their potential through support and the strengthening of their abilities. Empowerment does not merely entail physical support but also includes emotional, psychological, and social assistance,

enabling children with disabilities to integrate into society on an equal footing (Saleebey, 1996).

The Role of Preschool Institutions in the Process of Social Inclusion

Preschool institutions play a crucial role in educational inclusion, as they allow children with disabilities to engage in the educational process from an early age. Through attendance at preschool institutions, children with disabilities—who often face barriers to social and emotional integration—are given the opportunity to develop social skills and interact with their peers from an early stage.

Rawls (1971), through his theory of social justice, clearly emphasizes that all individuals, regardless of their physical or intellectual challenges, have the right to equal access. In this sense, preschools are not only educational institutions but also key socialization agents that help children with disabilities integrate into social life and develop the skills necessary for their future success in society.

Bronfenbrenner (1979), through his ecological systems theory, highlights the importance of preschool institutions in the socialization process of children. This theory suggests that different levels of the environment (family, preschool, societal) influence a child's development. Preschool institutions, as the first formal educational setting, play a fundamental role in providing a stable environment that helps children with disabilities integrate into broader society, participate in educational activities, and achieve emotional stability and social skills.

Additionally, the systemic approach plays an important role in this analysis. According to this approach, educational institutions and other social services should collaborate to create conditions for the social integration of all members of society. In the context of social work, this approach enables the development of strategies that help children with disabilities overcome barriers in education and social life. For example, social workers can assist in organizing transportation for children with disabilities from socially disadvantaged families.

The Importance of Social Workers in Educational Inclusion

Social workers play a vital role in the process of educational inclusion, as they not only provide emotional and psychological support to children but also work to overcome practical obstacles that hinder equal access to education. Their role encompasses a wide range of activities, including advocating for children's rights, supporting families, mediating between different institutions, and directly working with children to ensure their inclusion in the education system (Payne, 2005).

Empowering families, particularly those from socially disadvantaged backgrounds and families with children with disabilities, helps create societal balance, reduces social exclusion, and contributes to the development of an inclusive society. Their work reduces social inequalities and ensures that children with disabilities, regardless of socioeconomic status, have access to quality education and the opportunity for full social integration. In the future, strengthening the role of social workers through better institutional cooperation and additional training could significantly enhance the process of educational inclusion and ensure a higher degree of social justice within the educational system.

Educational inclusion, as a key aspect of broader social inclusion, provides essential support for children with disabilities. The development of social work theories, such as the theory of social justice, the empowerment theory, ecological theory, and the systemic approach, enables a better understanding of how educational and social workers can facilitate the inclusion of these groups within the educational system.

Preschool institutions play a critical role in social integration, as they provide children with opportunities to develop social skills and emotional stability. Through the collaborative efforts of educational and social institutions, combined with the application of social work theories, a foundation has been laid for an inclusive society that guarantees equal access to education for all its members, regardless of their specific needs.

Analysis of Previous Research

After analyzing and presenting the international and domestic legal framework, defining and classifying children with disabilities, and exploring the theoretical foundations of educational inclusion, the question arises as to how effectively these regulations are implemented in practice and what kind of support is available for preschool-aged children with disabilities. In the 2023/24 academic year, the number of children enrolled in preschool education programs in Bosnia and Herzegovina was 41,214, of whom 544 had developmental difficulties (Zavod za statistiku Bosne i Hercegovine). In the same academic year, in the Republic of Srpska, 16,807 children were included in preschool education programs, 113 of whom had developmental difficulties (Zavod za statistiku Republike Srpske). The state of inclusion of preschool children with disabilities varies and depends on economic resources, political priorities, and cultural factors. Although inclusion is formally developed in our country, its practical implementation is often limited by a lack of resources and support. Given the statistics, it can be concluded that the rate of inclusion of children with disabilities in regular preschool institutions is low, particularly in rural areas. The Ombudsman for Children highlights that, while progress is evident in the position of children with disabilities, further efforts are needed to improve their status (OECD, 2023).

Based on previously published scientific information and insights, the following section of this paper will provide an overview of existing research to better understand current preschool practices and the complexities of inclusive education. It is particularly important to consider the role of social workers in the inclusion process. Research by Milošević (2021), which included 50 social workers, showed that 72% believe that preschool institutions are not adequately prepared to support children with disabilities. Additionally, 65% of the surveyed social workers emphasized the need for greater collaboration between preschools and social services, while 80% identified the lack of personal assistants as the main challenge in inclusive practice. Financial difficulties and a shortage of specialized personnel further complicate the inclusion process.

By reviewing various studies, this paper will highlight the importance of a multidisciplinary approach and continuous professional development for early childhood educators to ensure effective social inclusion. Educators play a key role in working with children with disabilities, and their attitudes are crucial for the quality of the inclusion process (Kundek Mirošević & Jurčević Lozančić, 2014). A study by Nikolić, Vantić-Tanjić & Mešalić (2006), involving 35 educators, found that they generally hold positive attitudes toward the inclusion of children with disabilities in mainstream preschools. Their attitudes did not significantly differ based on age, education level, or work experience. A large percentage (80%) believed that regular preschool institutions should be adapted to accommodate children with disabilities and that specialized support teams are necessary (74.28%). Similarly, Stančić and Stanisavljević Petrović (2013) conducted a study with 135 educators, of whom 57.8% (78 participants) expressed positive views on inclusion as a means of ensuring the rights of children with disabilities to education. The authors emphasized that most respondents believed successful inclusion requires appropriate organizational conditions and support from expert services. According to Miloš and Vrbić (2015), out of 53 educators surveyed, the majority (89%) had a positive attitude toward the inclusion of children with disabilities in regular preschool groups. This research highlights the importance of professional development for educators in improving inclusive practices and underscores the need for expert team support.

A study by Čorluka (2017), which included 150 educators, reported that they had neutral to moderately positive attitudes toward the inclusion of preschool children with disabilities in regular preschool groups.

Based on these studies, it can be concluded that educators generally have a positive attitude toward inclusion, but targeted interventions are needed to improve the inclusion of preschool children with disabilities in mainstream preschool settings. Research findings also suggest that inclusion is not at a satisfactory level according to educators' assessments, indicating the need for further development of inclusive practices and stronger support for preschool education. From an ecological systems theory perspective, a child's environment consists of a complex system of interrelated levels that influence their development. Preschool institutions

belong to the microsystem, the immediate environment in which children socialize directly. However, the mesosystem, which includes interactions between families and preschools, is also crucial for inclusion. Effective collaboration among parents, educators, and expert associates leads to more successful inclusion. Conversely, the exosystem and macrosystem influence educational policies, societal attitudes, and legal regulations related to inclusive education (Bronfenbrenner, 1979). Parents bear the greatest responsibility in raising children. The family provides the initial foundation for a child's upbringing, which is later expanded through various educational institutions. Children with disabilities require parental support for a much longer period than their peers.

Research by Bihorac (2020), which included 55 parents of children with disabilities, found that 83.6% (46 parents) reported encountering daily obstacles that act as barriers to their children's everyday functioning. The same percentage of parents stated that the lack of government and institutional support further complicates their daily lives. Additionally, 92.7% (51 parents) reported being unable to afford specialized therapeutic services essential for their child's development. Empowerment theory provides additional insight into the importance of supporting families of children with disabilities. This theory emphasizes strengthening the capacities of parents, educators, and institutions to enhance inclusive practices (Saleebey, 1996). A study by the Institution of the Ombudsman for Human Rights of Bosnia and Herzegovina (2010) found that inadequate treatment of children with disabilities begins at birth and that parents often lack knowledge about their legal rights and available services. Many parents emphasized that early intervention, which is often absent, is essential for improving the child's functionality and increasing their inclusion in educational institutions. This highlights the need for greater education and systematic empowerment of parents through counseling services and professional teams. These findings align with research by Repalust (2017), which included 20 parents of children with disabilities. Most parents emphasized the need for more specialized treatment options, better-trained assistants, and easier integration into regular preschool groups. Research conducted by Gojnik (2023), which surveyed 133 parents and educators, found that 54.9% (73 respondents)

believe that assistants must be highly competent to provide quality and effective support for inclusive education. Inclusion can also be examined through empowerment theory, which stresses the importance of strengthening parents' and educators' capacities to support children with disabilities. Studies indicate that parents often lack sufficient information about their rights, highlighting the need for education and institutional support through counseling centers and expert teams. Strengthening both parents and educators can directly contribute to more effective inclusion, reduced prejudices, and improved educational services for children with disabilities. While there are varying opinions among preschool educators regarding children with disabilities and their inclusion, research suggests that their overall attitude toward inclusion is positive. However, many enter this complex field unprepared and insufficiently trained, despite the fact that inclusion demands more than just empathy and goodwill.

Theoretical frameworks help us understand the challenges these children face while also identifying potential solutions. The role of preschools, parents, educators, and social workers is crucial in creating an inclusive environment that enables every child, regardless of disability, to reach their full potential. Studies show that inclusion in preschool settings significantly contributes to better social integration of children with disabilities later in life, this underscores the need for comprehensive and systemic solutions to support their successful inclusion in preschool education and beyond.

Recommendations and Conclusions

Preschool education serves as the first stage of upbringing and education and represents the foundation for a child's holistic development. To ensure the success of inclusion, the following guidelines for improving practices in preschool institutions are provided.

Based on a detailed analysis of previous research on the social inclusion of preschool children with disabilities, the following recommendations can be made:

- Improve initial education and lifelong learning for educators and professional associates in the field of early identification and intervention for developmental difficulties and deviations in children (regular training

for educators and professional associates working with children with disabilities).

- Ensure additional capacities within preschool institutions for providing professional support in identifying and intervening early for children with developmental difficulties (e.g., sensory-motor rooms).

- Adapt preschool institutions to accommodate children with disabilities (provide appropriate didactic resources, materials, and aids, and remove all architectural barriers within institutions).

- Establish a package of services tailored to children with disabilities (conduct pedagogical observation and create an individualized developmental and educational program).

- Expand preschool education programs to rural areas, ensuring the inclusion of children with disabilities (e.g., mobile teams, implementation schedules, etc.).

- Ensure the presence of specialized staff in preschool institutions to work with children (speech therapists, special education teachers, rehabilitation specialists, psychologists, social workers, physiotherapists).

- Develop a support system for parents (enable education and psychosocial assistance through the establishment of counseling centers or parent associations to provide early-stage professional support, guidance, and instructions for inclusion).

- Foster strong collaboration between parents and preschool institutions, particularly with educators and professional associates, to ensure the child's developmental progress.

- Establish a more organized early intervention system (ensure more financially accessible services and improve cooperation among different professionals).

- Guarantee a personal assistant for every child with a disability (if the personal assistant lacks prior experience working with children with disabilities, it would be advisable for them to undergo specialized training).

Based on a comprehensive analysis of prior research, necessary targeted interventions have been proposed to enhance the social inclusion

of preschool children with disabilities. Improving inclusive education requires strengthening the role of social workers, who are often the first line of support for families of children with disabilities. Inclusive education necessitates a comprehensive approach that includes support for children, parents, and educators. From the perspective of the theory of social justice (Rawls, 1971), inclusive education is not only a pedagogical issue but also a matter of social equity. A just society is measured by its ability to provide equal opportunities for all its members, including children with disabilities. Therefore, the proposed recommendations should not be viewed merely as technical adjustments within preschool institutions but as part of a broader strategy for social inclusion, which entails changing awareness, policies, and approaches to education. Cerić (2008) emphasizes that further theoretical conceptualization of inclusive education is only possible through a multidisciplinary approach. This means that social workers, educators, and psychologists must work together to ensure the comprehensive inclusion of children in preschool institutions. In conclusion, social inclusion and support for preschool children with disabilities represent a crucial step toward building a fairer society—one that creates an accessible and supportive environment for every child, regardless of their abilities.

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SUPERVISION OF THE SECURITY SECTOR

PARLIAMENTARY OVERSIGHT OF THE INTELLIGENCE-SECURITY AGENCY OF BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA

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Abstract: The aim of this paper is to examine and present the importance and mechanisms of parliamentary oversight of the security sector in general and intelligence services as its specific and powerful components, with a special focus on the Intelligence-Security Agency of Bosnia and Herzegovina. This is a qualitative study, with data collected and analyzed from secondary sources using the qualitative content analysis method. Parliamentary oversight of the security sector is a process conducted by legislative authorities, i.e., elected representatives of citizens, to ensure transparency, accountability, and legality in the work of security institutions. Parliamentary oversight of the security sector establishes a link between the security interests of citizens and the executive authorities. Regarding intelligence services, parliamentary oversight has a threefold function: (1) drafting and monitoring the implementation of relevant laws; (2) financial oversight; and (3) oversight of policies and intelligence activities. The Intelligence-Security Agency of Bosnia and Herzegovina commenced operations on June 1, 2004, following the adoption and entry into force of the law regulating its establishment and functioning. The Joint Committee for the Oversight of the Work of the Intelligence-Security Agency of Bosnia and Herzegovina, consisting of 12 members from both houses of the Parliamentary Assembly of Bosnia and Herzegovina, is responsible for parliamentary oversight of this civilian intelligence service. Effective parliamentary oversight of this intelligence service is fundamental to strengthening public trust and building a stable democratic oversight culture, which is essential for addressing contemporary security challenges.

Keywords: Bosnia and Herzegovina, parliament, oversight, Intelligence and Security Agency of Bosnia and Herzegovina.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Parliamentary oversight of the security sector is a key mechanism of democratic governance in many countries worldwide. Designed to ensure transparency, accountability, and legality in the work of security institutions, this form of oversight plays a vital role in maintaining stability and public trust. Through the analysis of reports, budget approvals, hearings, and parliamentary investigations, parliamentarians actively monitor the activities of police agencies, intelligence services, and armed forces.

Parliamentary oversight of the security sector is not only a fundamental feature of democratic governance but also a critical element in protecting human rights and civil liberties. The transparency ensured by this oversight is crucial in building trust between citizens and security agencies, facilitating a more effective response to contemporary security challenges. Furthermore, oversight promotes accountability in the work of security agencies, preventing abuses of power and unethical conduct.

This is particularly evident in intelligence services, which represent a highly specific component of a state's security sector. Without adequate oversight and control, and considering their general modus operandi, the relative autonomy of these agencies (Masleša, 2001) can easily transform them into detached centers of power. Transitional states, such as Bosnia and Herzegovina (BiH), are especially vulnerable, as incomplete democratic institutions often stem from a lack or insufficient persistence of democratic culture. An integral part of this culture is oversight.

In the context of BiH, parliamentary oversight of the Intelligence-Security Agency of Bosnia and Herzegovina (ISA BiH) is conducted through the Joint Committee for the Oversight of the Work of ISA BiH, which role is crucial in ensuring the legality of the agency's operations. Through consistent legislative and oversight functions, the Parliamentary Assembly of BiH has the foundation to ensure that ISA BiH operates in accordance with constitutional principles, including respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms of all citizens.

The goal of this paper is to explore and present the mechanisms and effects of parliamentary oversight of the security sector and intelligence

services, with a particular focus on ISA BiH, primarily through qualitative content analysis of documents from open sources.

2. PARLIAMENTARY OVERSIGHT OF THE SECURITY SECTOR

Parliamentary oversight² of the security sector is the process by which the legislative authority monitors and controls the activities of institutions responsible for maintaining individual, societal, and state security. This primarily pertains to police agencies, the intelligence and security sector, and the armed forces of a country. This form of oversight encompasses various activities that parliamentarians conduct to ensure transparency, accountability, and legality in the work of security institutions. As stated in the OSCE (1994) Code of Conduct on Politico-Military Aspects of Security, “democratic political control (...) is considered an inseparable component of stability and security” (p. 8). Within parliamentary oversight, parliamentarians, often through specialized security committees, analyze reports on operations, approve and monitor budget expenditures, pose inquiries, conduct hearings, and carry out parliamentary investigations to ensure that security agencies operate lawfully and respect human rights of citizens.

From the above paragraph, it can be concluded that parliamentary oversight of the security sector, in the broadest sense, represents one of the characteristics of democratic societies, where individuals, through their elected representatives, participate in governance. Therefore, parliamentary oversight should also be viewed as a broader form of civic oversight of the executive branch. Additionally, parliamentarians and parliamentary oversight serve as a bridge between citizens’ security interests and the executive authorities, which may not always be fully aware of such interests [Inter-Parliamentary Union (IPU) and the Centre for Democratic Control of Armed Forces (DCAF), 2003].

2 Parliamentary oversight can be defined as “the review, monitoring, and supervision of the work of government and public organizations, as well as the implementation of policies and laws” (Yamamoto, 2007, as cited in OSCE Office for Democratic Institutions and Human Rights, 2017: 5).

Parliamentary oversight of the security sector has several key functions that are vital for democracy and the rule of law. First, it ensures transparency in the operations of security agencies. Through regular reporting and public debates, parliament allows citizens to be informed about the activities of the agencies responsible for their security. Transparency is crucial for building trust between citizens and security agencies, which is especially important in democratic societies. Trust is perhaps the most important element in the context of democratic policing structures, where police work should be based on citizens' consent (OSCE, 2007). Moreover, trust is the foundation of community policing and, consequently, citizens' participation in countering contemporary security threats.

Second, parliamentary oversight promotes accountability. Security agencies, due to the nature of their work, possess significant powers that can be susceptible to abuse. Parliamentary oversight helps prevent such abuses through mechanisms of control and accountability. Parliamentarians have the authority to hold security agency leaders accountable if unlawful or unethical behavior is discovered.

The third function directly builds on the previous one and pertains to the protection of fundamental human rights and freedoms. Security agencies in democratic states, given their complex operational tasks in responding to modern threats, often operate on the fine line between security protection and civil rights. Parliamentary oversight ensures that the measures taken by these agencies are implemented in accordance with the law and with respect for fundamental human rights. This means that such oversight, provided it truly exists (i.e., a culture of oversight is present) and is effective, is “the cornerstone of democracy in preventing autocratic rule” (IPU & DCAF, 2003: 25).

In addition to these functions, parliamentary oversight contributes to the efficiency of security agencies. Through constructive criticism and recommendations, parliament can help security agencies enhance their operational capacities and better respond to security challenges. In the context of contemporary threats, such as terrorism or organized crime, effective parliamentary oversight can significantly improve a state's ability to protect its citizens. However, to be effective, it requires

commitment, expertise, and resources. When discussing expertise, this can be particularly problematic for parliamentarians who may come from diverse social backgrounds and have varying professional experiences.

Additionally, the duration of parliamentary mandates can be a significant limiting factor in the development of the necessary knowledge and skills among parliamentarians. All of this is cited as one of the challenges of parliamentary oversight of the security sector (IPU & DCAF, 2003). In addition to adequate legal frameworks, one of the fundamental prerequisites for its efficiency and smooth operation is the existence of institutional frameworks, primarily an adequate number of well-educated professional staff as the bearers of “institutional memory.”

2.1. Parliamentary Oversight of Intelligence Services

To highlight the importance of parliamentary oversight of intelligence services, which are highly specific entities within a country’s security sector, it is first necessary to emphasize the broader necessity for democratic society to exercise control over these institutions. Aidan Wills (2010), in his work „*Understanding Intelligence Oversight*“, identifies at least four reasons for this.

Firstly, elected leaders in democratic societies are accountable for the functioning of all state agencies and bodies funded by public resources, including intelligence services. Oversight of intelligence services is essential to ensure the responsible use of public funds for their staffing and activities. Secondly, intelligence services have special powers to collect information that are not available to other members of society. These powers can lead to serious violations of human rights. Therefore, democratic societies monitor intelligence services to ensure the protection of human rights for all individuals who come into contact with them. Thirdly, the intelligence-gathering function of these services can interfere with the activities of political parties, the media, and other key institutions. Thus, it is necessary for the state to oversee intelligence services to safeguard these essential components of democratic society. As a fourth reason, Wills points out that democratic societies must oversee intelligence services because the law permits them to operate covertly.

For instance, they may secretly intercept communications or conduct covert searches of individuals' homes, often without the individuals being aware they are under intelligence measures. Additionally, while intelligence agencies' secret activities may be legal, they are difficult for individuals and the general public to monitor and control. Moreover, since intelligence services are not subject to the same level of public oversight as other government agencies, there is significant potential for inefficiency or unlawful practices. Therefore, it is crucial to monitor secret operations to ensure that intelligence services function effectively and in accordance with the law.

The role of parliaments in overseeing intelligence services is threefold:

- 1) Legislative preparation and implementation – Parliaments draft and adopt laws that regulate the functioning of intelligence services, identifying and correcting deficiencies in existing legislation (post-legislative oversight).
- 2) Financial oversight – Parliaments oversee how intelligence services use public funds, approving future budgets and reviewing past expenditures.
- 3) Oversight of policies and activities – Parliaments monitor the management, policies, and activities of intelligence services to ensure they operate efficiently and lawfully (Ibid, 2010).

In practice, parliamentary oversight is organized through the establishment and functioning of security and defense committees or, as is increasingly common worldwide, special committees dedicated to overseeing intelligence services. This is also the case in Bosnia and Herzegovina, where the Joint Committee for Oversight of the Work of the Intelligence-Security Agency of BiH operates within the Parliamentary Assembly of BiH. Additionally, parliamentary practices in various countries include the establishment of external expert bodies to oversee intelligence services. An example of this is the Council for the Civilian Oversight of Security and Intelligence Agencies in the Republic of Croatia. Members of this Council are appointed by the Croatian Parliament, and their mandate includes monitoring the legality of security agencies'

activities in Croatia - among other things, overseeing the implementation of secret data collection measures (Security and Intelligence System Act of the Republic of Croatia, No. 105/2006).

3. PARLIAMENTARY OVERSIGHT OF THE INTELLIGENCE-SECURITY AGENCY OF BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA

ISA BiH began its operations on June 1, 2004, following the adoption and entry into force of the Law on ISA BiH. Essentially, ISA BiH incorporated the entity intelligence services that were operating at the time - the Intelligence-Security Service of the Federation of BiH (commonly known as FOSS)³ and the Intelligence and Security Service of the Republika Srpska.⁴

According to the consolidated Law on ISA BiH (2009), it is a civilian intelligence agency operating throughout the territory of BiH. Furthermore, the provisions of this law prohibit the establishment and operation of any other civilian intelligence structures. ISA BiH is responsible for “collecting, analyzing, and distributing intelligence data to protect security, including the sovereignty, territorial integrity, and constitutional order of Bosnia and Herzegovina” (Law on ISA BiH, 2009, Article 1, Paragraph 1).

Considering the aforementioned points regarding parliamentary oversight of intelligence services, particularly in relation to the first two roles of the parliament, the oversight function of the Parliamentary Assembly of BiH is enshrined in the Constitution of Bosnia and Herzegovina (1995). Article IV.4 of the Constitution states that this legislative body is responsible, among other duties, for enacting laws and approving budgets for BiH institutions.

3 This service was established by merging the Agency for Investigation and Documentation of the Republic of Bosnia and Herzegovina (AID) and the National Security Service of the Croatian Republic of Herceg-Bosna (SNS). The Law on the Intelligence-Security Service of the Federation of BiH was adopted and came into force in 2002 (Kačar, 2019). However, employees of the previous agencies did not automatically transition to the newly established service. They had to reapply for their positions through a process that included, among other things, a security screening of potential employees (Hadžović & Dizdarević, 2011).

4 The Intelligence-Security Service of the Republic of Srpska was established in 1998.

In the context of policy and activity oversight, it is relevant to highlight the Law on Parliamentary Oversight of 2018. This law prescribes detailed procedures and powers that the Parliamentary Assembly of BiH has over various institutions, public administration bodies, and actors managing public funds or donations. Its objective is to ensure transparency, legality, and accountability in institutional work while preventing the abuse of public authority and resources. Parliamentary oversight, as defined by the law, includes various activities such as witness hearings, requests for reports from relevant officials and institutions, and more.

The bodies conducting oversight⁵ have the authority to access all relevant documents and information necessary for performing their functions. They can also engage experts and auditors to support their investigations. It is important to emphasize that parliamentary oversight in BiH is based on the principles of constitutionality, legality, democracy, and respect for human rights. Through various methods, such as public debates or parliamentary inquiries, oversight bodies actively work to improve public finance management and ensure that institutions operate in accordance with legal and ethical norms. Finally, based on collected information and evidence, these bodies prepare detailed reports and recommendations submitted to the Parliamentary Assembly of BiH. These reports may include proposals for the dismissal of responsible individuals if their accountability for institutional irregularities or abuses is established.

The parliamentary body responsible for overseeing ISA BiH is the Joint Committee for the Oversight of ISA BiH. This committee consists of 12 members, six from each house (the House of Representatives and the House of Peoples). The committee is chaired by a president elected from among its members, who belongs to a political party that is not part of the ruling coalition in the Parliamentary Assembly of BiH.

The committee includes representatives of all constituent peoples - the chairperson and their two deputies must not come from the same

⁵ Article 6 of the aforementioned law states that parliamentary oversight is conducted through the houses of parliament, standing committees, and, if necessary, *ad hoc* committees with specific tasks in conducting oversight. Additionally, members of parliament and delegates exercise parliamentary oversight by submitting parliamentary or delegate questions (Law on Parliamentary Oversight, 2018).

constituent people. The committee holds meetings at least twice a year⁶, which are mostly closed to the public. Its competencies include:

- a) overseeing the legality of ISA BiH's operations;
- b) conducting discussions on the appointment of the general director, deputy general director, and chief inspector of ISA BiH and providing opinions on these appointments;
- c) reviewing the chairperson's reports on matters within their jurisdiction, including measures taken to address any issues identified during inspections or investigations of ISA BiH;
- d) reviewing and adopting reports from the general director on the work, activities, and expenditures of ISA BiH, with a particular focus on budget spending;
- e) reviewing and adopting reports from the chief inspector;
- f) requesting that ISA BiH employees, through the chairperson, provide expert advice when necessary for oversight functions;
- g) providing opinions on the detailed budget proposal for ISA BiH;
- h) conducting investigations into ISA BiH's operations (Law on ISA BiH, 2009).

Regarding the last item, if the committee has reasonable grounds to suspect unlawful conduct by ISA BiH, it can initiate an investigation, during which it can question employees of the institution and access relevant documentation. If unlawful conduct is established, the committee can call upon the chairperson or general director to take necessary measures and initiate an investigation into accountability. The chairperson or general director is obliged to report the results of the investigation to the committee. Committee members are required to maintain the confidentiality of information and data accessed in their capacity as members. This obligation remains in effect even after their membership in the committee ends. However, in cases of public interest protection, the committee may decide to release members from the obligation of

6 During the 2018–2022 mandate period, the commission held only two sessions in 2020. More information is available at: <https://www.parlament.ba/committee/read/42?mandateId=10&-committeeMandate=296>.

confidentiality, provided there is consent from the authorized official responsible for classifying information and at least eight committee members (Law on ISA BiH, 2009). Additionally, it is important to emphasize that the committee is also responsible for overseeing the implementation of the Law on the Protection of Classified Information.

4. CONCLUSION

Parliamentary oversight of the security sector in democratic societies, particularly over intelligence agencies, is essential for ensuring transparency, accountability, and the legality of these institutions' operations. Through the analysis of security agencies' work, budget adoption, hearings, and investigations, parliaments actively contribute to maintaining stability and public trust. In the case of Bosnia and Herzegovina, the Joint Committee for the Oversight of the Work of ISA BiH holds a key position in ensuring that the agency operates in accordance with constitutional principles and respects human rights.

A qualitative analysis of publicly available documents reveals that parliamentary oversight of intelligence agencies serves three main functions: the preparation and implementation of legislation, financial oversight, and monitoring policies and activities. These functions enable parliaments to ensure the responsible use of public funds, the protection of human rights, and the efficiency of intelligence agencies. In BiH, through the aforementioned committee, the Parliamentary Assembly ensures that ISA BiH operates in compliance with the law and the constitution, preventing potential abuses of power.

However, the existence of adequate legal and institutional frameworks alone is not sufficient. The lack of a shared goal and responsibility among oversight actors in holding the executive branch accountable presents a significant challenge. Additionally, the underutilization of existing capacities by elected representatives further undermines the effectiveness of oversight. These challenges require commitment and resources to ensure effective oversight.

Despite these challenges, parliamentary oversight remains an indispensable mechanism for upholding the rule of law and protecting

democratic values. In the context of BiH, effective parliamentary oversight of ISA BiH is fundamental to strengthening public trust and fostering a stable democratic oversight culture, which is crucial for addressing modern security challenges. Efficient oversight can significantly enhance the state's ability to protect its citizens, provided that it is conducted with dedication, expertise, and the full utilization of available capacities (inclusivity).

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CRIMINAL PLANNING

CRIMINALISTIC PLANNING OF SEARCHES AS A PREREQUISITE FOR THE SUCCESS OF THE EVIDENCE PROVING PROCESS

MA Đorđe Šešum¹

Abstract: Searches are an evidentiary action, but we consider them as a criminal-procedural criminalistic action because in Bosnia and Herzegovina, they are directly carried out by police officers under the supervision of the prosecutor, usually based on a court order. The formal framework consists of imperative criminal-procedural norms, while the substance is directly determined by criminalistics through its implementation. A search is a coercive action, often urgent, which interferes with human rights protected by the Constitution and Article 8 of the European Convention on Human Rights. A lawful search is conducted when the legitimate purpose cannot be achieved through a less repressive action. It must not be carried out impulsively, unplanned, or without method, as such an approach will either fail to achieve its intended purpose or only achieve it partially. Poorly, partially planned, or unplanned searches endanger both police officers and the persons being searched, as well as their property and other citizens, leaving the consequences to chance, with the best-case scenario being only the potential failure of the search.

This paper highlights the importance of criminalistic planning of searches. It addresses the application of principles related to searches, criminalistic planning in both broader and narrower terms, examining the needs, challenges, and specificities of planning searches in BIH, depending on the subject of the search with a written court order, an oral court order, or in cases of searches without a warrant and without witnesses. The paper aims to support its findings

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with scientific-theoretical positions from criminal-procedural law and criminalistics, positions of the European Court of Human Rights, and examples of challenges from practice, while also offering the key elements that a written criminalistic search plan should include in potential planning for a search.

Keywords: evidence proving process, search, police officer, authorized official, criminal planning.

INTRODUCTION

Search and seizure is a formal criminal-procedural evidentiary action in Bosnia and Herzegovina (BIH). Due to the country's complex state structure, four parallel Criminal Procedure Codes (CPCs) exist and are applied in BIH, all of which regulate search and seizure almost identically.² Legislators in BIH have categorized searches based on the subject of the search into searches of premises, other spaces, and movable objects, as well as personal searches (searches of individuals). A common feature is the mandatory fulfillment of material conditions. A search can only be carried out when there is sufficient evidence to suspect that immovable or movable items contain the perpetrator, accomplice, traces of a criminal act, or items important for the criminal proceedings. In the case of personal searches, they can only occur when it is likely that the person has committed a criminal offense or that objects or traces important to the criminal proceedings will be found.

In addition to the mandatory fulfillment of material conditions, all four CPCs in BIH generally require the fulfillment of a formal condition, i.e., a court order in the form of a written and reasoned search warrant. Unlike the mandatory material condition, there are exceptions in which searches can be conducted without the formal condition being fully met, but in accordance with the provisions of the CPC (Article 128 of the RS CPC; Article 64 of the BIH CPC; Article 78 of the FBIH CPC; and Article 64 of the BD BIH CPC).

² The Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Srpska (hereinafter: CPC RS); The Criminal Procedure Code of BIH (hereinafter: CPC BIH); The Criminal Procedure Code of the Federation of BIH (hereinafter: CPC FBIH); The Criminal Procedure Code of the Brčko District of BIH (hereinafter: CPC BD BIH).

The existence, fulfillment, and satisfaction of the conditions for a lawful search are the responsibility of the active participants in the search, namely the police officers/authorized officials (hereinafter: AO)³, the acting prosecutor, and the investigating judge, who in BIH acts as a control body ensuring the legality of the search. The aforementioned parties are obligated to continuously ensure the legality of the search so that the right to private and family life, home, and correspondence, as guaranteed by Article 8 of the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR), is not violated through unlawful searches.

While a search is a criminal-procedural action, in BIH it is directly carried out by AO under the provisions of the CPC and the rules and experience of criminalistics, making it also a criminal-procedural criminalistic action. As such, search and seizure is inseparable from the operational criminalistic actions of the AO in the specific case, as long as the procedural legality is not questioned. Criminalistic actions are generally divided into criminal-procedural and operational criminalistic actions (Aleksić and Škulić, 2011, p. 34), and they share the common feature that their implementation should be planned with predefined objectives.

There is no perfect plan. It is impossible to predict all possible situations that may affect the execution of procedural actions and perfectly plan the methods and means to prevent them. However, this does not mean that a search should be a haphazard, unplanned action; rather, it is an imperative to plan the procedural action carefully. Planning a search in a broader sense can be viewed as the overall planned criminalistic procedure of the authorized officials (AO) from the moment they become aware of the grounds for suspicion that a criminal offense has been committed. This leads to a series of actions culminating in the need for a search, but only when there are sufficient grounds to suspect that the search will lead to the discovery of the perpetrator, an accomplice, traces of the criminal

3 Since the criminal procedure reforms implemented in BIH in 2003, the term “authorized official” has a broader meaning than just police officers. Considering that searches in BIH are directly conducted by authorized officials of police agencies, in this work, “authorized officials” refers specifically to officers of police agencies who, in accordance with the provisions of the relevant laws at the state, entity, cantonal, and/or Brčko District level, are authorized to perform police duties and act as authorized officials in accordance with the provisions of the relevant Criminal Procedure Code, in line with actual and territorial jurisdiction.

act, or items important for the proceedings. This should only occur if a less intrusive evidentiary action, as outlined in Article 8 of the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR), could not have achieved the same result. We will now focus on the narrower sense of search planning and the significance of criminalistic planning for the execution of the search as an evidentiary action by the AO, as a prerequisite for its successful realization and achievement of its goals. We aim to highlight the specificities and challenges of planning searches influenced by the nature of the items being searched for, the items believed to be found, and the individuals being sought or discovered at the scene. Criminalistic planning of searches should, as a rule, be covert. Initially, it should only be known to the AO officers handling the case and their supervising managers. After the written plan is created, approved, and presented, it should remain confidential, even among the AO officers involved in the search. It is imperative to prevent any “leakage of information” to avoid compromising the purpose of the search, such as the destruction or concealment of items being sought, or the escape of individuals sought.⁴

Regardless of the type of search based on the subject of the search in a given case, planning always includes both a personal (individual) and a material component. The personal component involves determining the necessary number of engaged authorized officials (AO), in accordance with their expertise and abilities, based on objective assessments of the needs for the search. This includes AOs within the decision-making chain of the police. The material component of the plan ensures that the AOs have the necessary material and technical resources (MTR) available during the search to achieve the objectives of this evidentiary action in the specific case.

PRINCIPLE OF METHODOLOGY AND PLANNING

Criminal-procedural principles are fundamental rules of the criminal procedure that serve and protect basic human rights and the achievements of the rule of law, ensuring fairness and justice throughout the

⁴ It is possible and planned, deliberately allowing the “leak” of information in order to achieve another procedural and/or criminalistic goal.

procedure (Buha, 2021, p. 11). A search is also a criminalistic action, for which authorized officials (AO) apply criminalistic principles. The basic criminalistic principles are derived partly from criminal-procedural norms, but also from other sources and provisions, such as those regulating human rights and their protection (Pavišić, Modly, and Veić, 2006, p. 127). These principles guide the application of criminalistic practices, ensuring that searches and other investigative actions are carried out in accordance with legal standards, with due regard for the protection of individual rights and liberties.

A lawful and successfully conducted search by authorized officials (AOs) is inseparable from criminalistic principles such as legality, objectivity, methodology and planning, operational efficiency, speed, thoroughness and persistence, proportionality, unified leadership, coordination, and cooperation, among others. The application of the principle of methodology and planning during the execution of a search is imperative. This principle ensures the fulfillment of other criminalistic as well as criminal-procedural principles. Methodology encompasses the obligation to meticulously plan activities. A search that is unplanned or insufficiently planned may result in searching the wrong premises or individuals, even if the material conditions are met and a search warrant has been issued in accordance with the provisions of the criminal-procedural law. The European Court of Human Rights (ECHR) has established through its case law that in such cases, human rights protected by Article 8 of the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR) are violated.⁵ Also, first an unplanned and then a non-methodical search leads to the failure to achieve the objectives that were the reason for conducting the search. A

⁵ In the case of *Keegan v. the United Kingdom* (Application No. 28867/03), by judgment of July 18, 2006, paragraphs 29-36, the European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR) held that there had been a violation of Article 8 of the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR), because the police had not conducted an adequate check regarding the current residents of a residential property planned for a search. The authorized officials forcibly entered the applicant's property and carried out the search, mistakenly believing that an armed member of a criminal milieu was living in the house. The Court accepted that the reasons presented to the competent court before the search were relevant and legally valid for conducting the search. However, it considered them insufficient due to the failure to conduct proper preliminary checks and the lack of an adequate level of precaution. For the ECtHR, it was not significant that the police acted without "bad intentions," but rather the insufficient checks that had been made.

non-methodical and unplanned search may result in the failure to find, or only partially finding, items important for the criminal procedure or the sought individuals. This principle is also evident in cases where important items are found but, due to the unpreparedness of the AOs (resulting from the lack of planning), are then illegally temporarily seized, improperly and untimely stored, and as such cannot be used as evidence in the criminal procedure. Unplanned searches endanger the safety of the acting AOs, as well as the individuals found at the search site and other citizens (poorly planned searches with the aim of finding explosive devices, highly toxic narcotics, dangerous fugitives, etc.).

Planning and methodology go “hand in hand” and are a prerequisite for the success of criminalistic actions. A well-planned search allows the AOs who directly conduct it to be methodical. Timely planning of the required number of executors, MTM, ensuring the presence of witnesses (in sparsely populated areas), engaging specialized police units (commonly referred to as “special forces”), etc., enables the methodical approach of the acting AOs. This eliminates potential problems that could hinder the AOs during the search, affect the duration of the evidence-gathering action, and/or completely prevent the search. In practice, it is possible to have methodical searching without prior good planning, as well as the reverse. It happens that AOs are methodical, but due to the size of the searched object or the lack of appropriate MTM, they cannot be fully successful. Due to an insufficient number of search executors for larger premises resulting from poor planning, the search lasts longer, hindering the efficiency and methodical approach of the AOs due to fatigue. Practice also records cases of formally (written search plan) well-planned searches that were not successfully carried out due to unforeseen problems and situations.⁶ The search plan must be implemented in the actual situation and depends on its immediate execution in the field, i.e., the human factor. Engaging unmotivated or insufficiently qualified AOs will result in a lack of methodical approach, and thus, the expected outcome. Methodicalness is influenced by both subjective and objective human factors. Lack of motivation is a subjective human factor, while lack

⁶ The search plan must not be “rigid,” meaning it should be flexible and adaptable as necessary.

of expertise is an objective human factor affecting methodicalness. The AOs who draft the search plan should particularly pay attention to these aspects of the human resources involved. The responsibility for approving and instructing the creation of the plan (if not creating it themselves) should lie with the supervisory staff of the police unit responsible for conducting the search (considering the pyramid structure and hierarchy in the decision-making chain based on police ranks, and thus the level of responsibility depending on the position of the individual AOs within this structure).

The principle of methodology and planning is also in a synergistic relationship with the principles of efficiency and economy of the procedure. By planning the personal and material components necessary for a successful search, the efficiency of the engaged human and material resources is ensured, as well as the economical execution of the procedure.⁷

CRIMINALISTIC PLANNING

Planning is inseparable from the basic tasks of authorized official persons (AOs) in preventing the commission of criminal offenses, detecting and prosecuting perpetrators. Gros (1914) emphasized that creating a criminalistic action plan allows a comprehensive approach to solving a specific case and prevents spontaneous and chaotic actions. Criminalistic action can be divided into traditional and modern approaches to organizing and planning the overall criminalistic activity of a police authority. Regarding the time of response to the commission of a crime, the traditional approach is reactive, while the modern approach is proactive. The proactive approach has rightfully prevailed, enabling the prevention of crimes before socially negative consequences occur. Modern criminalistic planning is divided into strategic and tactical planning. Strategic planning analyzes the conditions and causes of certain types of crime, as well as crime as a whole, and measures taken to prevent it (Simonović, 2002).

⁷ Engaging an excessive number of AOs and unnecessary MTM violates the principle of economy. By planning according to objective needs, economy during the search is ensured without compromising efficiency.

Tactical planning involves planning the activities of AOs engaged in the prevention, detection, and resolution of criminal offenses, analyzing the factual situation, and taking appropriate criminalistic actions (both operational and criminal-procedural) with the goal of gathering lawful evidence in criminal proceedings (Simonović & Matijević, 2007, p. 65). The fundamental principles of criminalistic planning are concreteness, individuality, and dynamic planning. Tactical planning consists of planning actions in a specific case as a whole, as well as planning individual criminalistic actions (in our case, searches).

Planning a search is a phase of action by AOs that precedes the actual search procedure. As such, planning is one of the prerequisites for a successful search. No search in practice is identical, and it can never be stated with certainty that all possible situations have been anticipated in the plan. However, timely and proper planning can determine the required number of AOs for executing the search and AO engaged in securing the immediate and, if necessary, broader search location, establish a hierarchy of search leaders at each location (as well as in the case of multiple searches within operational actions), determine the chain of communication to inform supervisory AOs of the activities undertaken, notify the acting prosecutor, engage and assist “special forces,” as well as specialized staff from other relevant services, and foresee a sufficient number of criminalistic technicians, etc. Planning also involves forecasting the use and ensuring the availability of the necessary material-technical means (MTM) for a successful search, from specialized tools for opening entrances, cameras and scanners for inspecting hard-to-reach spaces, the use of specially trained tracking service dogs, securing an adequate number of transportation vehicles, to communication tools (phones, radio communication, encrypted devices, etc.), and other necessary tools according to the specific needs.

Planning of the criminal-procedural criminalistic action of a search based on a written court order for a search⁸

Search is an evidentiary action under the Criminal Procedure Code (CPC). It is undertaken only when a “less intrusive” procedural action (with less interference in protected human rights) cannot achieve the purpose of finding the perpetrator or accomplice of a criminal offense and/or evidence and objects important for the criminal procedure. As such, it should be the result of meaningful and carefully planned actions by law enforcement officers (AOs), under the supervision of the competent prosecutor and, as a rule, by court order, with the goal of resolving the specific criminal case. A search must not be a spontaneous action that is an end in itself, in which case it would be illegal. This particularly applies to searches conducted under a written court order, which the court issues based on the prosecutor’s reasoned request or the AOs request, with prior approval from the prosecutor (Article 117, para. (2) CPC RS; Article 53, para. (2) CPC BIH; Article 67, para. (2) CPC FBIH; Article 53, para. (2) CPC BD BIH). The mandatory deadline for executing a court order for a search in BIH is 15 days from the date of issuance. Within these 15 days, preparatory activities for conducting the search, planning the search, and creating the plan must be completed, followed by the execution of the search order.

Search planning cannot be carried out without preparatory activities, which are interdependent with the nature and purpose of the search, as well as the time available. Preparatory activities are a phase in the execution of the search by the AOs. These activities are inseparable from the immediate planning process. Preparation involves gathering information about the object and person to be searched, in order to determine

8 In cases of searches based on an oral order and searches without a formal search plan order, there is no time for preparation, as these are urgent actions that cannot be delayed. In such cases, certain preparatory activities can be carried out to a limited extent. However, this does not mean that such searches should be spontaneous. Even in these situations, they must be carried out by respecting the principles of methodicalness and planning, based on legal and subordinate legal acts, as well as the criminalistic experience, knowledge, and skills of the acting law enforcement officers, their mutual criminalistic coordination, and the available material and technical resources.

the real needs regarding the number of officers, specific specializations and expertise of the officers, and the required material and technical resources (MTM). AOs often already have such data, collected during the investigation prior to the issuance of the search order, and some of this is outlined in the request for the search order.

Both in domestic and international police practice, it is common for AOs to first encounter the location to be searched just before the search takes place. In these cases, the address is usually determined by reviewing the database of general citizen data maintained by the competent authority, by reviewing outdated operational databases of criminally interested individuals, or sometimes even just based on operational intelligence gathered through friendly or informant networks (the quality of such intelligence is often questionable). In the case of searches under a written court order, this is unforgivable and may lead to:

- violations of citizens' human rights (e.g., searching the wrong property or person);

- endangering AOs and citizens (e.g., a police raid on the wrong property that eliminates the element of surprise);

- indirectly facilitating the escape of the person to be searched, or the destruction or concealment of items intended to be found in the search.

Upon issuing the order, it is desirable to thoroughly compare it with the actual situation on the ground in order to prevent situations that could undermine the legality of the AOs and the search itself.⁹ Vajngart (1905, p. 79-86) outlined the basic questions for successful search planning, which are still theoretically and practically recognized today:

- 1.) What or whom should be searched for;
- 2.) From whom should it be searched for;
- 3.) When should it be searched for;

⁹ Due to errors caused by the human factor, there may be discrepancies in the data, which need to be checked as part of the preparatory activities for the search carried out by AOs. For example, verifying the addresses specified in the order against those in the request (which should be identical and accurate), the identification details of the person to be searched, etc. In cases where discrepancies are found, we recommend notifying the prosecuting attorney and the court that issued the order, and issuing an amended/updated search order.

- 4.) How is it most useful to search for;
- 5.) Where should it be searched for;
- 6.) With what equipment and how many officers should it be searched for.

We believe that the aforementioned questions should also be used when drafting a reasoned request for the issuance of an order, which the prosecutor or the AO submits to the court, with prior consent from the competent prosecutor. Courts in BIH issue an order based on the request and the information provided in the request, which they use to interpret the validity of the request. The actions of the AOs are limited by the order.

Legislators at all levels in BIH have made a basic distinction regarding the subject of the search and its specifics, dividing it into searches of apartments and other premises (including seized movable items), searches of individuals (personal searches), and searches of movable items suitable for storing digital data (computers, servers, hard drives, USB drives, mobile phones, etc.). Planning in a specific case is determined by the nature and characteristics of the object being searched, and in most cases, the search includes both immovable property and individuals, as well as devices for storing digital data. In any case, criminalistic planning of the search is a prerequisite for a successfully conducted search.

Planning the search of apartments and other premises

The planning of the search of immovable property is based on the content of the order, the data and information gathered during preparatory activities, and other available information such as:

- the exact geographical location of the immovable property;
- the purpose of the search, i.e., what is specifically being sought during the search;
- specifics of the immovable property (apartment in a residential building, family house, or other types of residential buildings such as a mobile home, exact floor and apartment number, size, access, type of entrance doors and used locks, possible entries through windows, etc.);

- household members, their number, age, and gender of individuals expected to be present, and their tendencies toward resistance, violent behavior, etc.;

- legal specifics regarding searches of official premises, religious and military buildings, and law offices, which particularly affect planning.

The geographical location of the property to be searched and the exact distance from the starting position of the AOs to the search location influences the planning of the required travel time for the AOs to the search location. When conducting multiple searches (within operational actions), this allows for a synchronized start of all searches. By law, searches are generally conducted between 6:00 AM and 9:00 PM, and in practice, searches usually begin at 6:00 AM. Criminalistic tactics determine that the best time to begin a search is in the early morning hours, when it is expected that resistance from those being searched will be minimal, and that the search is more effectively carried out in daylight, while searching at night is more difficult. The possibility of error is also avoided, such as the AOs not knowing which object to search, which can lead to both unlawful actions by the AOs and tactical errors, delays in starting the search, compromising the safety of officers and citizens, etc. Svrha pretresanja esencijalno određuje planiranje pretresanja.

Depending on the purpose, the use of the appropriate technical equipment (MTM) will be planned, as well as the number of AOs who, with their knowledge and skills, can carry out the search. For example, when searching for narcotic drugs (which are easily concealable), it is necessary to plan the use of suitable MTM to access hard-to-reach areas, such as tools for disassembling furniture parts, wire cameras, probes for viewing inaccessible spaces, scanners, and appropriate chemical reagents that can perform preliminary chemical analyses on-site, etc. It is essential to plan the use of suitable and safe packaging when temporarily seizing narcotic drugs and storing them in accordance with the CPC, the court's order for the search, as well as the applicable legislation in BIH that regulates the seizure, storage, and destruction of narcotic drugs.¹⁰ The

¹⁰ Knowledge of the legal frameworks that define the obligations when acting by AOs is a factor

planning of the engagement of adequately trained AOs, familiar with the proper and safe methods of searching, recognizing, temporarily seizing, packaging, and storing narcotic drugs, is imperative to avoid jeopardizing their own safety and the safety of others present during the search, while ensuring that the integrity of evidence is not compromised. This also applies to searching for military equipment, weapons, explosives, and other dangerous items, materials, and substances, especially if the actions are regulated by special regulations. In principle, the purpose of the search itself determines the planning of which AOs to engage and which MTM to use.¹¹

Considering the specifics of the immovable property in terms of the size of the object, the appropriate number of AOs to carry out the search and their individual capabilities will be planned. If the property is large, a proportionally larger number of AOs should be planned. On the other hand, if it is a smaller property (e.g., a small studio apartment), fewer AOs will be planned (never fewer than two AOs) in order to meet the principles of efficiency and economy in actions, as well as to avoid disturbing citizens with an unnecessary number of AOs on-site. When planning the engagement of multiple AOs, it is also necessary to consider the factor of interpersonal relationships between AOs within the search teams. Although legality and professionalism should be the foundation of their actions, AOs are still human beings. It is reasonable to

that must be considered when planning a search. AOs must be familiar with and act in accordance with the provisions of the CPC, but often in practice, their actions are also determined by special laws, with whose norms not all AOs, especially those on the “line of work” in the police department, are necessarily familiar, or not to a sufficient extent. For example, the Law on Prevention and Suppression of Abuse of Narcotic Drugs in BIH and the Regulation on the Storage and Destruction of Seized Narcotic Drugs, Psychotropic Substances, Plants from Which Narcotic Drugs Can Be Obtained, and Precursors more specifically define the handling of narcotic drugs. Therefore, when planning a search in which the discovery of narcotic drugs is expected, it is necessary to consider the engagement of AOs familiar with these norms or plan additional familiarization with the obligations for non-specialized AOs who are not regularly engaged in detecting and preventing criminal offenses related to narcotic drugs. .

11 For example, if the search is conducted to find money suspected of being counterfeit, it is necessary to engage AOs who are familiar with how to recognize counterfeit money. Alternatively, if there are multiple locations to search, which may prevent the engagement of a sufficient number of trained AOs, it is necessary to ensure that the engaged AOs are familiar with the characteristics they need to observe in money suspected of being counterfeit.

expect that the effectiveness of the search will be higher within a team where interpersonal relations are good and undisturbed (although this is not necessarily a rule). AOs, based on previous actions, develop professional preferences for working with certain colleagues, and based on the success of the actions taken, their suggestions about team compositions should be taken into account. It is important to always remember that the search is not an end in itself¹², it must also not be conducted with the aim of increasing the statistical performance of the police. In accordance with legal procedures, the issued search order specifies the purpose for which the search is being conducted. The search must be carried out in a way that minimizes the violation of human rights, both for the individuals being searched and for other citizens (neighbors, bystanders, etc.).

The approach to the object (e.g., a remote mountain road, forest road, etc.) as well as information about the entry points into the building (bars on doors and windows, armored doors, etc.) affect the planning. If the building is inaccessible or approached via a road in poor condition, the use of suitable motor vehicles (off-road vehicles) and AOs who are trained to operate them should be planned. If vehicles cannot be approached, AOs must be capable of accessing such a property, including, if necessary, the engagement of “special units.” Having information about the characteristics of the entry points into the object to be searched allows for the planning of the necessary MTM for opening and entering the building using appropriate tools or the engagement of AOs trained to handle such tools. A property secured with armored doors, bars, and other entry barriers can be an insurmountable obstacle for an ordinary AO, especially those who do not have the appropriate MTM for entry or the expertise to handle them.

By having basic demographic data on population density, the nearest neighbors, or potential witnesses to the search, it is possible to plan for AOs to bring witnesses to the search or know where they can be found, in cases where it is expected that they will be impossible to locate at the scene or their discovery would involve difficulties and take a lot of time.

12 It is unacceptable and illegal to conduct a search based on the cliché: “We will search, and we will surely find something.”

With information and knowledge about the individuals expected to be found at the search location and their behavior in contact with AOs, it is possible to plan a sufficient number of AOs to ensure a lawful, successful, and safe search. If a larger number of individuals is expected, a larger number of AOs should be engaged, especially if the individuals are prone to attacking or resisting the AOs. In such cases, the engagement of “special units” will also be planned to assist the searchers (to control the individuals present and ensure conditions for an undisturbed and safe search). When planning the number and gender of the AOs to be engaged, it is also necessary to consider the gender composition of the individuals expected, in accordance with legal provisions regarding gender identity during searches of individuals, which will be addressed later.

If, during the search of an immovable property, there is an expectation of finding victims of human trafficking, victims of pedophilia, individuals in poor health, minors without parental accompaniment, foreign nationals, etc., the engagement of specialists from social welfare centers, psychologists, doctors, the Service for Foreign Nationals, etc., will be planned, or their subsequent notification will be planned in case such individuals are found. For this, it is necessary to determine the communication methods and chain of command in a timely manner. These officials do not participate in the evidentiary act of the search but act within their powers to protect the individuals in need and provide expert assistance to the AOs.

The timing of the search is an essential aspect of planning the search. The timing is constrained by criminal procedure norms in BIH (Article 123 of the CPC RS; Article 59 of the CPC BIH; Article 73 of the CPC FBIH; Article 59 of the CPC BD BIH). The law in BIH imperatively stipulates that a search must be conducted within 15 days of the issuance of the order. Searches are usually carried out between 6:00 AM and 9:00 PM, unless the order explicitly authorizes execution at any time of day or night in accordance with the law. Within these limits, planning involves determining the most appropriate time to begin the search to achieve the purpose of the search, which depends on the case. For example, if there is information that the sought items or individuals are not currently at the targeted property, it is necessary to plan the search to begin at the most

tactically favorable moment upon receiving “reliable tip-off” or verified information that the items sought are present at the location. Otherwise, the AOs arriving at the location and conducting the search could indirectly alert the “target or targets” not to come to the location or not bring the items sought, thereby preventing the purpose of the search from being achieved. In practice, police surveillance of the property planned for the search, as well as coordination with AOs involved in conducting special investigative actions such as “simulated purchase and simulated bribery,” “covert surveillance,” “use of undercover investigators,” and “use of informants,” etc., are often planned, and the timing of the search will depend on the relevant intelligence and data.

The term “other rooms” in all criminal procedure laws in BIH includes, in addition to various living spaces (barracks and huts), official rooms, religious and military objects, and law offices, which determines the planning specifics of searching such immovable properties. When searching official premises, instead of witnesses to the search, the superior or head of the official premises is called to attend the search, with the same rights and obligations (Simović, Simović, & Govedarica, 2021, p. 200). It is necessary to plan for the presence of the head by ensuring contact information in advance or by planning the search at a time when their presence in the searched premises is expected. Legislators in BIH have specified the specifics for searching military and religious objects. In these cases, it is necessary to plan for the search order to be delivered in a timely manner to the military authorities or the competent religious community, which will appoint a person to attend the search. Criminal procedure provisions at no level in BIH have prescribed the specifics of searching a law office. However, positive regulations on advocacy in BIH¹³ stipulate the specifics of searching a law office, which cannot be carried out without the presence of an authorized representative from the relevant bar association (Article 37, para. (3) of the ZOA RS; Article 28 of the ZOA FBIH). When planning the search of a law office, it is necessary to plan for the AOs to understand and emphasize that searching a law

13 The Law on Advocacy of Republika Srpska (hereinafter: ZOA RS) and the Law on Advocacy of the Federation of BIH (hereinafter: ZOA FBIH).

office is not the same as searching an ordinary business premises, and that it may potentially jeopardize the confidential relationship between the client and the lawyer. Moreover, only the items/documents specified in the court order should be sought. The European Court of Human Rights in the case *Robathin v. Austria* on July 3, 2012 (Application No. 30457/06) held that a general and unrestricted search of a law office is illegal and that searches and temporary seizures must be proportional to the specific needs (Pisarić, 2019, p. 63).

Planning of searches of persons (personal searches)

Personal search is a material investigation of the body, clothing, footwear, and personal luggage of a particular individual when it is likely that this individual is the perpetrator of a criminal offense or when it is likely that the search will yield items or traces of a criminal offense that are important for the specific criminal proceedings. Personal search is a mandatory investigative action when an individual is deprived of liberty, and when it is likely that the individual has weapons or tools for assault or intends to dispose of, hide, or destroy items that need to be temporarily seized. Personal search is often inseparable from the search of premises and other areas, and generally, the same principles apply to this search. Criminal procedural provisions in BIH (BIH) provide additional protection of the right to privacy of the searched individual, which should be especially considered when planning (Article 116, para. (2) CPC RS; Article 52, para. (2) CPC BIH; Article 66, para. (2) CPC FBIH; Article 52, para. (2) CPC BD BIH). Personal search has a special rule of gender identity for both the active and passive actors, meaning that the search must be conducted by individuals of the same gender, with witnesses of the same gender as well (Škulić, 2022, p. 248). Accordingly, whenever possible, planning the personal search should properly assess the gender composition of the engaged AOs, while considering one of the tactical rules that personal searches should be conducted by at least two AOs. While one AO performs the search, the other observes, acting preventively to deter possible attacks and/or prevent escape. If there are no AOs on-site who meet the gender identity rule, their engagement should be ensured.

As with the search of premises, planning must also take into account the necessary post-search actions to be taken after the search is concluded.¹⁴

During the search of a person, the aforementioned Weingart's question about successful search planning, "What or whom should be sought?" becomes particularly relevant. The search of a person emphasizes both the objective and subjective traits and skills of the engaged AOs. Based on the available information and previous police experiences regarding the person to be searched, it is necessary to plan the involvement of capable AOs to successfully achieve the purpose of the search. For individuals prone to resisting, fleeing from AOs, discarding or destroying objects, it is essential to plan the engagement of a proportional number of psycho-physically capable AOs to prevent such actions and achieve the search's purpose, minimizing potential risks to the safety of the engaged AOs, the individual, and other citizens. This should be done by using the least repressive methods proportionate to the perceived threat. Although an AO must act professionally, they are still human, not a robot. Their reactions to provocations can be influenced by current life circumstances (family, health, financial issues, lack of career advancement, etc.). Supervisory officers (AO superiors) should evaluate these circumstances on a case-by-case basis when assigning personnel for all types of searches, especially searches of individuals.

In practice, some AOs, out of laziness (avoiding the preparation of official records), may choose not to conduct the procedural action of searching a person but instead perform an inspection. Within its scope, an inspection is not as formal as a procedural search. This can lead to two unfavorable situations, among others. In the first case, during the inspection, the AO fails to find the sought object, even if the object, for example, is hidden in the individual's underwear. In the worst case, the undiscovered object could be used for an attack on the AO, self-harm, escape, taking hostages, etc. In the second case, during an action labeled as an inspection (exceeding the bounds of an inspection and practically conducting a search), the AO finds nothing, but the individual later accuses

¹⁴ For example, bringing the individual to official premises for questioning, handing the individual over to the acting prosecutor, etc.

the AO of conducting an unlawful search without an official record. The individual might also have “witnesses,” such as household members (if present) or selected witnesses to the search, whose presence is often erroneously entrusted to the searched individuals themselves (usually their associates) who will testify against the AO. Both situations can lead to disciplinary and even criminal liability for the AO.

Planning the Search of Movable Items Suitable for Storing Digital Data

The definition of movable items in the true sense of the term is not provided by any CPC in BIH but rather by property laws. The search of an apartment and other premises also includes the search of movable items found therein. The search of a person includes the search of their clothing and personal luggage. However, when it comes to searching computers and computer systems, devices for storing computer and electronic data (USB drives, hard drives, etc.), and/or mobile phones, this must be carried out with the assistance of an expert (Article 115, para. (2) and para. (3) of the CPC of RS; Article 51, para. (2) and para. (3) of the CPC of BIH; Article 65, para. (2) and para. (3) of the CPC of FBiH; Article 51, para. (2) and para. (3) of the CPC of BD BIH). Such devices may contain data relevant to the specific criminal proceeding, referred to as digital evidence. The collection of digital evidence must be conducted with the assistance of an expert to ensure the integrity of the evidence is not compromised due to unprofessional handling (Ivanović & Žarković, 2019, p. 426). If the search warrant for an apartment, other premises, and movable items includes the search of devices for storing digital data, experts may conduct the search on-site, depending on the time and available technical equipment. In such cases, it is necessary to plan the engagement of AOs who hold expert status. In practice, police agencies in BIH have organizational units within their internal structures that employ experts for collecting digital evidence. When a police agency lacks experts or sufficient numbers of them, it is possible to engage experts from other police agencies, which must be stipulated in the court order for the search and subsequently agreed upon and jointly planned between different agen-

cies. If, for any reason, the search of devices for storing digital evidence cannot be conducted on-site, the search will be carried out later at the premises of the police agency by an expert. In such cases, the search is usually conducted in the premises of the internal organizational unit of the police agency responsible for these tasks. Interestingly, legislators in BiH have not prescribed the presence of two independent witnesses as a prerequisite for such searches of movable items (Article 124, para. (4) of the CPC of RS; Article 60, para. (4) of the CPC of BiH; Article 74, para. (4) of the CPC of FBiH; Article 60, para. (4) of the CPC of BD BiH).

Search Plan (Formal Planning)

A search plan as a formal act of planning should be prepared whenever objective conditions allow. The plan is the result of analyzing available information and data that define the specificities of the particular search, including the contents of the search warrant and the normative framework. The plan addresses organizational, tactical, and technical issues such as the start time of the search, the number of required AOs with specific assignments (leadership, site surveillance, direct searching, etc.), their arrangement into search teams (in cases of multiple coordinated simultaneous searches), the designation of a supervisor/coordinator for activities during extensive operations, logistical needs for criminalistics, such as the required technical equipment, including the use of tracking dogs, and other matters depending on the circumstances (Aleksić & Škulić, 2011, p. 61).

The search plan is not a universal written document but is tailored for each specific case. In drafting the search plan, it is essential that the AOs responsible for the specific case (most familiar with the case) participate, as well as their supervisory officers, respecting the pyramid structure and hierarchy within the decision-making system of the police agency, depending on the complexity of the case (seriousness of the criminal offense, number of searches, complexity of the case, involvement of multiple organizational units or police agencies, etc.). This approach distributes the immediate responsibility for all foreseen and unforeseen circumstances, as outlined in the plan, from the acting AOs to their su-

pervisors. In cases involving operational actions (a large number of simultaneous coordinated searches and other criminalistics activities), it is our opinion that supervisory officers should draft the plan and bear the primary responsibility for its lawful implementation as coordinators and leaders of the operation. In practice, however, the plan is often drafted by the acting AOs, while supervisory officers approve the plan. The AO most familiar with the specific case is typically designated as the coordinator for the search. In addition to the coordinator role, this AO often serves as the team leader at one of the search locations (a demanding, responsible, and complex activity). If “not everything goes according to plan,” the coordinator AO is held accountable, despite not holding a rank or position within the police agency that involves responsibility for managing a larger number of AOs and/or multiple organizational units and their activities, nor for urgent verbal correspondence and coordination with the competent prosecutor’s office. This portion of the “burden” should be borne by supervisory officers in accordance with their rank and position within the police hierarchy.

The plan, as well as the search itself, should be based on the principles of legality, objectivity, methodology and planning, operationality and speed, thoroughness and persistence, proportionality, unified leadership, coordination and cooperation, economy, and procedural efficiency. In addition to the aforementioned, the search plan must also be based on:

- The principle of concreteness in planning, which is achieved by analyzing the actual situation within the legal framework, setting deadlines for execution, defining the duties of supervisory officers and executors, engaging AOs based on the required knowledge, skills, expertise, and specialization,¹⁵ necessary technical equipment, etc;

¹⁵ When drafting the plan, it is essential to assess the current subjective attitude of the AO towards their work and engagement. As a human being, the AO is susceptible to the effects of stress caused by personal, health, family, financial, and/or any other problems (including professional dissatisfaction due to the disproportionate nature of their duties, work results, and personal abilities on one hand, compared to, for example, stagnation in their career progression on the other), which can affect their motivation during the search, and consequently, the effectiveness of achieving the purpose of the search at the location where they are engaged.

- The principle of individuality in planning, meaning that the plan is created in accordance with each specific search and its characteristics;

- The principle of dynamism in planning, which means that the plan, once drafted, is not absolutely final but can change within the legal and regulatory framework, based on the emergence and/or collection of new or expanded knowledge that may affect this procedural action, or the occurrence of unforeseen circumstances (Luzgin, 1963, pp. 5-7; Simonović and Matijević, 2007, p. 66).

Based on the above, the written search plan should include the following elements:

- The name of the police authority and the internal organizational unit where it is drafted;

- A brief description of the measures and actions taken so far, as well as the grounds for suspicion against the suspects;

- The preparatory activities prescribed by the plan as a phase in planning the search ordered by the court (collecting information about the object and person to be searched);

- An assessment of the security situation, with a detailed review of available data and facts about the individuals whose properties and/or items are being searched, in relation to their tendencies for attacks and resistance towards AOs, flight, destruction, disposal, or concealment of items, and based on this, an assessment of the need for appropriate specialized police units;

- Activities that precede the immediate execution of the search order and those to be undertaken after the search, with specific deadlines for execution and assigned AOs for each activity (forming search teams, including reserve teams as needed, timely sending requests for the engagement of AOs from other organizational units and police authorities, planning activities following the searches in accordance with agreements and instructions from the acting prosecutor—interrogating suspects, transporting them to the prosecutor, etc., submitting the search report and temporarily seized items to the court, and submitting reports on the actions taken to the acting prosecutor, etc.);

- Information about the search team(s) or more teams (team names by serial numbers) with the names of engaged AOs and appointed team leaders, assigned technical equipment, and specific team duties in accordance with the order and plan, including criminal investigative actions beyond the search, such as surveillance, monitoring individuals, arresting individuals, conducting Special investigative actions, coordinating and working with “specialists,” etc.;
- In accordance with the search order, the purpose of the search, i.e., the items and/or persons being sought through the search, and for which the search is being conducted;
- Planned and expected technical equipment needs;
- The planned date and time of the search initiation;
- Appointment of an AO responsible for reporting from the team leaders on the activities undertaken to implement the search order and plan, and designating an AO to coordinate the actions of the search teams;
- Procedures after the completion of the search (submission of temporarily seized items to the court for storage, etc.);
- Notifying the management of the police authority about the actions taken and the relevant internal organizational unit for public notification and media relations;
- Other items that, depending on the circumstances of the specific case, need to be considered and planned.¹⁶
- The names and signatures of AOs who created the plan, gave consent, and/or approved it.

Planning Searches Based on an Oral Warrant and Searches Without a Warrant and Witnesses (Informal Planning)

The criminal procedure reform of 2003 in BIH introduced a novelty in the form of an oral court warrant for a search (Article 120 of the CPC RS; Article 56 of the CPC BIH; Article 70 of the CPC FBIH; Article 56

¹⁶ For example, during the COVID-19 pandemic, the use of appropriate protective equipment (masks, rubber gloves, face shields, suits, etc.) was planned to protect AOs, searched individuals, and other citizens, i.e., to prevent the spread of infection.

of the CPC BD BIH).¹⁷ An oral order is preceded by submitting an oral request by the AO (with prior oral consent from the competent prosecutor) for the issuance of an order by the judge for the preliminary procedure when there is a concrete risk of delay. The legislators have not defined “risk of delay,” so it is assessed on a case-by-case basis. If the judge for the preliminary procedure grants the AO’s request, the AO will independently draft the order, which will then be read aloud to the judge to confirm that such an order was issued. Without further discussion, we can conclude that this is an action where the critical element is urgency, which cannot be delayed. In this case, the AO objectively does not have enough time to satisfy the formal procedure for issuing a written search warrant.

On the other hand, a search without a warrant and witnesses represents a deviation from the rule of having a formal condition in the form of a court order, justified by urgency (Škulić, 2022, p. 245). A search without a warrant is not a novelty in BIH, and it is regulated by all criminal procedural laws in BIH in nearly identical ways (Article 128 of the CPC RS; Article 64 of the CPC BIH; Article 64 of the CPC FBIH; Article 64 of the CPC BD BIH). A search without a warrant, according to the provisions of substantive criminal law, obligates the AO to prevent the commission of crimes, detect and report crimes, and seize items that should be seized in accordance with the law. These provisions are embodied to prevent and avoid any passive behavior by the AO, who could become “accomplices” in concealing a crime or traces and evidence (Buha, 2023, p. 127). In exceptional circumstances provided by law, the AO can enter an apartment and other premises without a warrant and carry out a search when the tenant of the apartment wishes it, if someone calls for help, if it is necessary to apprehend a perpetrator caught in the criminal act, or for the safety of people and property. A search can also be conducted if a person is present in the apartment or another room who, by court order, must be detained or forcibly brought, or who has taken refuge there to avoid prosecution. A search of a person can be carried out in the same manner when executing a detention order, during an arrest, if there is

¹⁷ The Criminal Procedure Code of the former SFRY prescribed searches based on a search warrant and warrantless searches, which were carried out by AOs in accordance with the provisions of Article 210, paragraph (1). In comparative law, neither the Republic of Serbia nor the Republic of Croatia allows for searches based on an oral order issued by the court.

suspicion that the person possesses a firearm or cold weapon, or if there is a danger that they will hide, destroy, or discard items that need to be seized and used as evidence in the criminal procedure.

In both cases, these are urgent procedural actions that cannot be delayed. There is no time for the regular legal procedure of issuing a warrant because delaying the search would undermine its purpose. The AO does not have the time in which to prepare a formal written search plan. If the search were delayed until the plan was prepared and approved, the urgency of the situation would be questioned. This could potentially provide a valid defense argument to challenge the legality of the search, emphasizing that if there is time to prepare a search plan, there is also time for the regular procedure of issuing a court order. In the case of a search without a warrant and without witnesses in BIH, the entire burden of assessing the fulfillment of legal conditions rests on the AO directly conducting the search. This does not mean that such searches should be spontaneous, unmethodical, or conducted entirely without planning. The plan is not formally prepared before the operation but informally immediately before and during the search, in accordance with criminal procedural provisions, criminalistic rules, the knowledge, abilities, and experience of the acting officers, available MTM, and other factors. The planning, dynamics, and order of the search are determined on the spot and must be legal, reasonable, and logical, taking into account the safety of the acting AO, the person being searched, other citizens, and their property. In these searches, which are by nature urgent and unavoidable, personal abilities of the AO, derived from previous criminalistic experiences (the number of searches conducted during their police career), as well as knowledge of criminal procedural provisions and criminalistic rules, are especially important. Depending on the specific situation and the hierarchical structure within the police agency, a leader for the search team is determined on the spot, providing directions and oral orders to other AOs (if present).¹⁸ The

¹⁸ In practice, it often happens that the leader of the search team is not the AO with the highest rank at the scene, but rather the AO with real authority (not administrative) among the other engaged AOs. The AO with real authority is often informally chosen as the leader of the team or imposes themselves as such, taking responsibility for leading the search from a higher-ranked AO whose abilities and knowledge do not justify their position in the police hierarchy.

team leader is responsible for informing the supervisory officers of the organizational unit from which they belong about the conducted search and, if necessary, requesting reinforcements or the provision of required MTM. This represents informal planning during the operation. The leader ensures compliance with the legal obligation to prepare the appropriate written documents and submit them to the court or the competent prosecutor's office for the purpose of informing them, further actions, and assessing the legality.

Conclusion

Searches represent one of the most important and complex investigative actions in BIH, as they always entail a risk to the rights to privacy, family life, home, and correspondence. All current criminal procedural laws in BIH prescribe the mandatory fulfillment of material conditions and the existence of formal conditions, generally in the form of a court order for the search. Although the immediate execution of searches by authorized police officers is part of their professional routine, this does not mean that searches should be conducted routinely based on the mindset of "How will we do it? It's easy!". By discussing criminal investigative planning in a narrow and broad sense in relation to taking investigative actions in criminal proceedings in BIH, applying the principles and rules of criminalistics limited by strict criminal procedural provisions, and emphasizing the specifics of formal search planning based on the subject matter of a written court order or informal planning based on oral orders or searches without orders, this paper has sufficiently highlighted the importance and necessity of criminal investigative planning as a prerequisite for success in achieving the purpose of this investigative action. The arguments presented have been supported by scientific and theoretical perspectives of criminal procedural law and criminalistics, opinions from the European Court of Human Rights, and the practical challenges faced by authorized officials. We have outlined the essential elements that a written criminal investigative plan for a search should contain, in order to create the necessary conditions for achieving the goal and success of the search by anticipating objective needs and possible obstacles.

Through planning, it becomes possible to ensure the proper qualitative and quantitative personal involvement of those executing the search, who will have access to the necessary material-technical resources and/or expert assistance in accordance with their specific expertise, all within strict mandatory deadlines. This enables the success of the search and the achievement of the purpose for which the search is conducted in the first place. By anticipating and planning objective needs, the principles of economy and efficiency in criminal proceedings are respected. By involving adequate personnel and material components, the search is conducted economically without reducing the effectiveness of the procedure, while avoiding unreasonable, unjustified, and unnecessary increases in procedural costs.

Absolute planning does not exist, nor is there a perfect search plan. Unforeseen situations and circumstances will always arise; they should be anticipated and dealt with as they occur, based on the engaged and potentially available human factor (personal knowledge, skills, mutual coordination of authorized officers, etc.) and the use of suitable material-technical resources.

It can be concluded that unprepared and unplanned searches leave their success to chance, and that search planning is an unavoidable phase in the actions of authorized officers in BIH, which precedes the immediate execution of this investigative action as a prerequisite for the success of the search. However, the plan must not be rigid and absolutely final; it should be flexible and adaptable. The success of a search, which is conditioned by high-quality planning, will ultimately be assessed in court proceedings, particularly if the results of the search are considered lawful evidence upon which the court decision and resolution of the specific criminal case are based.

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HYBRID WARFARE

ANALYSIS OF THE APPLICABILITY OF CLAUSEWITZIAN FRICTION THEORY IN MODERN HYBRID WARFARE

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Abstract: This article explores Clausewitz's understanding of friction in military theory through the lens of contemporary asymmetric and hybrid conflicts, demonstrating how this concept has transformed from primarily a physical and tactical phenomenon into a multidimensional construct encompassing informational, cognitive, organizational, and strategic aspects. The research methodology combines historical analysis of Clausewitz's original concept with empirical findings from contemporary conflicts and a multidisciplinary approach that integrates military, sociological, psychological, and technological perspectives. The article's objective is to develop a new theoretical paradigm that can adequately encompass the complexity of friction in the digital age through identification, categorization, and analysis of new sources and manifestations of friction characteristic of the contemporary operational space. The findings provide a significant contribution to military theory and practice through redefining the classical concept of friction in a way that can inform more effective doctrine, training, and organization of military forces for navigating through the complexity of contemporary conflicts.

Keywords: *Clausewitz, friction, hybrid warfare, asymmetric conflicts, information domain, cyber operations*

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1. CONCEPTUALIZATION OF FRICTION IN CLAUSEWITZIAN MILITARY THEORY

Carl von Clausewitz,² a Prussian general and one of the most significant military theorists of all time, in his magnum opus “On War” (*Vom Kriege*) published posthumously in 1832, introduced the concept of “friction” (*Friktion*)³ which remains fundamental to understanding the dynamics of armed conflicts even today, nearly two centuries later. The conceptualization of friction in Clausewitzian military theory represents one of his most original contributions to strategic thought and requires detailed consideration of the historical context in which it emerged, as well as analysis of the fundamental principles upon which it rests.

Clausewitz’s understanding of war was not the product of purely theoretical considerations, but was deeply rooted in his personal experience during the Napoleonic Wars. As an officer in the Prussian army, Clausewitz witnessed the defeat at Jena and Auerstedt in 1806, participated in the Rus-

2 Carl von Clausewitz (*Carl Philipp Gottfried von Clausewitz*) was born on June 1, 1780, in Burg near Magdeburg, and died on November 16, 1831, in Breslau (now *Wrocław*) of cholera. As a Prussian general and military theorist, Clausewitz served in the Prussian-Russian campaigns against Napoleon (1812-1815), was chief of staff of the Prussian Military Academy, and director of the *Kriegsakademie* in Berlin from 1818 to 1830. His magnum opus “On War” (*Vom Kriege*) remained unfinished due to his premature death, and was posthumously published by his wife Marie von Clausewitz (*Marie von Clausewitz*) in 1832, who edited the manuscripts he had worked on during the last twelve years of his life. Although Clausewitz was unable to complete the envisioned revision of his work, “On War” has been recognized as one of the most influential works of military theory in history, becoming the foundation of strategic thinking in many military academies around the world.

3 In the original German text of Clausewitz’s work *Vom Kriege*, the author uses the term *Friktion* for a concept that translates into Serbian as “trenje” (friction). Clausewitz deliberately borrows this term from mechanics, creating a powerful metaphor that depicts the forces that oppose the smooth conduct of military operations. A nuance that is sometimes lost in translation is that *Friktion* in German carries a stronger connotation of mechanical resistance and physical interaction than the word “trenje” often conveys in our language. Regarding the frequently cited phrase “fog of war”, it is interesting that Clausewitz never literally used the term *Nebel des Krieges* (which would be a direct translation), but rather spoke of “uncertainty” (*Unge- wissheit*) and a phenomenon similar to “twilight” or “half-light” (*Halblicht*). The concept of “fog of war” was developed through interpretations and adaptations of Clausewitzian thought, becoming a powerful metaphor for uncertainty and incompleteness of information in wartime conditions.

sian campaign against Napoleon, and was present in the Waterloo campaign of 1815. Such experiences provided him with a unique perspective on the gap between military plans and their realization on the battlefield. As Paret notes: „Clausewitz’s experience of warfare against Napoleonic France shaped his theoretical thought in a way that cannot be separated from his analysis of friction in war” (Paret, 1985:142). It was precisely in this gap between theory and practice, between plan and execution, that Clausewitz identified the phenomenon he called “friction”. In attempting to explain why military operations rarely unfold according to plan, Clausewitz coined one of his most famous analogies: „Everything in war is very simple, but the simplest things become extremely difficult. Difficulties accumulate and create a kind of friction that is hard to imagine for those who have not experienced war” (Clausewitz, 1976:119). This metaphor of friction, borrowed from mechanics, served as a perfect illustration of forces that oppose the smooth conduct of military operations. Just as friction in mechanics slows down movement, so friction in war complicates the implementation of military plans.

Clausewitz’s conceptualization of friction was not merely descriptive, but also analytical. He identified various sources of friction, among which the unreliability of information, physical efforts and limitations, unpredictability, fear and uncertainty particularly stand out. According to Clausewitz: „The reports that are received in war are mostly contradictory, even more are false, and the greatest part are uncertain... In short, most reports are false, and the fear of men increases lies and untruths” (Clausewitz, 1976:117). Such observation about the “fog of war” (*Nebel des Krieges*) became one of the key aspects of his understanding of friction. In considering Clausewitz’s theory of friction, it is important to view the historical context in which it emerged. The period after the French Revolution marked a fundamental transformation in the way of warfare, where mass armies of nation-states replaced the smaller, professional armies of the previous period. As Howard (1983) emphasizes: „Clausewitz’s understanding of friction partly arose from his observation of how traditional armies faced new challenges of mass mobilization and logistics brought by the Napoleonic way of warfare” (Howard, 1983:78). Indeed, with the increase in army size and operational complexity, the friction that commanders had to deal with also increased.

The fundamental principles of Clausewitz's theory of friction can be better understood through his tripartite division of war. Clausewitz conceptualized war through three levels: rational (linked to political objectives), irrational (linked to chance and probability), and non-rational (linked to emotions and passion). Friction is primarily located in the irrational sphere of war, where chance, unpredictability, and probability play a key role. According to Summers' interpretation: „Clausewitz's brilliance lies in understanding that war is not governed only by rational calculation, but also by elements that cannot be easily quantified - friction and chance are among the most important" (Summers, 1992:54). One of the greatest contributions of Clausewitz's theory is the recognition that friction is an inevitable characteristic of war, not an anomaly that can be eliminated through better planning. As Clausewitz himself emphasizes: "Friction is the only concept that generally corresponds to what distinguishes real war from war on paper" (Clausewitz, 1976:121). The distinction between "ideal" and "real" war has profound implications for military theory and practice. As Echevarria (2007) points out: „Clausewitz's insistence on friction as a fundamental characteristic of war represented a direct challenge to the Enlightenment belief that war could be reduced to rational formulas and geometric principles" (Echevarria, 2007:112). It is important to note that Clausewitz did not consider friction only as an obstacle to be overcome, but also as a phenomenon that could be exploited against the enemy. The ability to function despite friction - or to create friction for the opponent - became a key element of military skill. In this context, Clausewitz introduces the concept of "military genius" as a leader who possesses the intuition and character needed to navigate through the friction of war. According to Clausewitz: „Genius in war is nothing other than an exceptional ability to remain composed in an atmosphere of danger and uncertainty, from which comes the greater part of friction" (Clausewitz, 1976:124).

Clausewitz's theory of friction can also be viewed in the context of his broader theory of "absolute" and "real" war. While absolute war is a theoretical construct that implies escalation of violence to the extreme limits, real war is limited by numerous factors - and friction is one of the most significant. As van Creveld notes: „Clausewitz's distinction between absolute and real war is actually an acknowledgment of the in-

fluence of friction in limiting the theoretical possibilities of conflict escalation” (Creveld, 1991:98). The distinction was crucial for avoiding purely abstract theories that would have no practical application. One of the most interesting characteristics of Clausewitz’s theory of friction is its dialectical nature. Namely, friction is not only a product of material factors such as weather, terrain, or logistics, but also of the human factor - both one’s own forces and the enemy. What is particularly significant in Clausewitz’s analysis is the recognition of the interactive nature of friction -- enemy actions create friction, but the very presence of the enemy creates psychological friction through fear and uncertainty. As Watts (2004) notes: „Clausewitz’s greatest achievement was recognizing that friction is not just the result of physical circumstances, but also of complex interaction between opposing wills” (Watts, 2004:76).

The network of conditionalities created by friction leads to Clausewitz’s concept of „centers of gravity” (*Schwerpunkt*), which represents the point where enemy power is concentrated, but also the point of greatest vulnerability. As Strange emphasizes: „Clausewitz’s theory of centers of gravity directly derives from his analysis of friction -- identification of centers of gravity enables commanders to direct their efforts to critical points where created friction could have decisive influence” (Strange, 1996:103). The presented approach emphasizes economy of force and precise targeting of efforts, instead of simple accumulation of resources. Clausewitz’s understanding of friction also contributed to his concept of “culminating point of victory” - the moment when offensive force reaches maximum efficiency before friction begins to dominate and reduce its effectiveness. According to Clausewitz: „In every military operation, once the culminating point is passed, friction and resistance become so great that further advance becomes counterproductive” (Clausewitz, 1976:198). Such observation has significant implications for operational planning and articulation of limited objectives.

The implications of Clausewitz’s theory of friction for military practice were far-reaching: it encouraged the development of the concept of *Auftragstaktik* (mission command)⁴ in the Prussian army, later

4 Clausewitz’s theory of friction had a profound impact on the development of the German

the German *Wehrmacht*, where subordinate officers received greater autonomy so they could adapt plans to the friction they encountered in the field. As Keegan emphasizes: „The Prussian-German acceptance of Clausewitz’s concept of friction led to decentralization of command that enabled greater flexibility at the tactical level - a direct response to the uncertainty created by friction in war” (Keegan, 1993:167). Clausewitz’s conceptualization of friction in military theory represents one of the most significant contributions to strategic thought. His recognition of the gap between theory and practice, between ideal plan and actual execution, fundamentally changed the way war is thought about. As Gray emphasizes: „Perhaps no other aspect of Clausewitz’s theory is as relevant to contemporary understanding of war as his concept of friction - it represents a bridge between abstract theories and actual challenges of command” (Gray, 1999:143). Clausewitz’s theory of friction remains vitally relevant even in the contemporary age of technology and information, reminding us that war, in its essence, is a human endeavor marked by uncertainty, complexity, and friction.

concept of *Auftragstaktik*(mission-type command), which became the foundation of Prussian and later German military doctrine. Recognizing the inevitability of friction and “fog of war” on the battlefield, Prussian military reformers under the leadership of Helmuth von Moltke the Elder developed a command system that emphasized decentralization of decision-making and initiative among subordinate officers. Instead of detailed orders prescribing every aspect of execution, *Auftragstaktik* emphasizes clearly defining intent (the so-called *Commander’s Intent*) and the desired end state, leaving subordinates free to decide for themselves how to accomplish the assigned mission. This approach is a direct adaptation to Clausewitz’s observation that centralized command becomes less effective as friction increases, since plans rarely survive first contact with the enemy. Through two German military academies (*Kriegsakademie*), Clausewitzian thought on friction was integrated into officer training, emphasizing the need for adaptability, independence, and rapid decision-making at all levels. The successes of the Prussian army against Austria (1866) and France (1870-71) demonstrated the effectiveness of this approach, cementing the influence of Clausewitz’s theory on German military doctrine. The modern German military (*Bundeswehr*) still applies this concept under the name *Führen mit Auftrag* (leading through mission), while many other military forces, including the US and NATO, have adopted similar approaches as an adaptation to the friction of modern warfare. Through the doctrine of *Mission Command*, the US Armed Forces explicitly acknowledge their intellectual debt to Clausewitz’s understanding of friction and uncertainty, demonstrating the lasting influence of his ideas on contemporary military thinking.

2. HYBRID WARFARE AS A COMPLEX OPERATIONAL SPACE

Contemporary conflicts⁵ increasingly take on the characteristics of hybrid warfare, a phenomenon that combines conventional military operations with unconventional tactics, cyber attacks, information operations, economic pressures, and other means of power projection. The evolution in warfare methodology has significantly transformed the nature of conflicts, creating a more complex operational space that generates new sources and manifestations of “friction” in the Clausewitzian sense. As Hoffman emphasizes: „Hybrid warfare incorporates different models of warfare, including conventional capabilities, irregular tactics and formations, terrorist acts and criminal behavior, creating a multimodal operational space of unprecedented complexity,, (Hoffman, 2007:14). Such complexity creates fertile ground for the emergence of new forms

5 The Russian-Ukrainian conflict (Knežević, 2025) represents an exceptional demonstration of Clausewitz’s concept of friction in a contemporary context, showing how this theoretical principle evolves and acquires new dimensions. The traditional sources of friction that Clausewitz identified - unreliability of information, physical limitations, and unpredictability - manifest in this conflict, but in transformed forms that reflect the complexity of modern warfare. Informational friction manifests through massive disinformation campaigns that create a “digital fog of war” that makes it difficult to distinguish reality from propaganda, both for military leaders and civilian populations. Physical friction is visible through the logistical challenges faced by Russian forces in the early phases of the Special Military Operation, demonstrating how even technologically advanced armies succumb to classical limitations of terrain, time, and endurance. Operational friction arises *through the discord between doctrine and actual circumstances on the battlefield*, which was evident when Russian forces applied tactics designed for rapid conventional victories in a prolonged conflict that requires a different approach. Organizational friction manifests through rigid hierarchical structures that hinder adaptation to changing circumstances, which was particularly visible in the first months of the war. Strategic friction arises through the discord between political objectives and military means, where expected rapid victory gives way to prolonged attritional conflict with unclear prospects for decisive success. Technological friction is visible through the limitations of sophisticated weapons systems in complex operational environments, including challenges posed by simpler and cheaper systems like drones. Cognitive friction manifests through erroneous assumptions about the motivation and endurance of the adversary, which has led to significant strategic miscalculations on both sides. Diplomatic friction arises through complex international relations and interactions that limit the options available to the warring parties, particularly in the context of nuclear deterrence and economic sanctions. Legitimacy friction demonstrates how the perception of justice and justification of the conflict affects support, mobilization, and endurance, creating a unique dynamic that transcends mere material calculation.

of friction that significantly differ from those Clausewitz described in his work “On War”.

Hybrid warfare presents a challenge to traditional understanding of friction primarily because of its intrinsic multidimensionality. Unlike conventional conflicts where front lines are relatively clear, hybrid conflicts occur simultaneously through multiple domains - physical, informational, cognitive, cyber, and others - with each domain possessing its own unique characteristics that generate specific forms of friction. According to McCulloh and Johnson: „Hybrid warfare deliberately blurs the boundaries between different domains of conflict, creating a situation where friction appears not only within individual domains, but also at their overlaps and interfaces” (McCulloh & Johnson, 2013:32). This overlap of different operational domains significantly complicates the problem of friction, as it requires synchronization of activities that are subject to different dynamics and limitations. In the context of hybrid warfare, the information sphere becomes a particularly significant source of friction. The massive proliferation of information technologies and social media has created an environment in which information moves at incredible speed, creating what Cronin calls an “information tsunami” that significantly complicates distinguishing facts from disinformation. As Cronin emphasizes: „In hybrid conflict, information overload and intentional manipulation of information create a new kind of ‘fog of war’ that is denser and more persistent than the one commanders faced in Clausewitz’s time” (Cronin, 2020:87). Digital “fog of war” presents a fundamental challenge for decision-makers, as it undermines the ability to form an accurate picture of the situation that is necessary for effective command.

The cyber domain of hybrid warfare also represents a rich source of new forms of friction. Traditionally, friction in warfare was limited by the physical laws of the material world - terrain, weather, logistics, and human limitations. However, cyberspace possesses its own laws and dynamics that create new and unpredictable forms of friction. As Libicki notes: „Cyber friction is not simply an extension of physical friction into the digital sphere, but a fundamentally new phenomenon arising from the unique characteristics of cyberspace - its inhomogeneity, asymmetry,

instability, and unpredictability” (Libicki, 2012:178-179). For example, latency in network communications, software bugs, system compatibility, and cyber attacks represent new forms of friction that have no direct analogies in the physical domain, but can have equally significant or even more important impact on the outcome of operations.⁶

The asymmetric nature of hybrid warfare additionally contributes to creating new forms of friction. In hybrid conflicts, state and non-state actors often possess drastically different capabilities, motivations, and operational approaches, creating asymmetric interactions that generate friction in unexpected ways. As Kilcullen emphasizes: „Asymmetry in hybrid conflict is not just a matter of disproportion in military power, but fundamental differences in operational logic and strategic thinking, creating ‘conceptual friction’ that is often harder to overcome than

6 The *NotPetya* attack from 2017 represents an exceptional example of “cascading friction” in the digital domain, where malware initially targeted at Ukrainian companies caused global consequences through unexpected chains of interdependence, resulting in over \$10 billion in damages to multinational companies such as *Maersk*, *FedEx*, and *Merck*. The Russian attack on Ukraine’s electrical grid in 2015 and 2016 demonstrates „operational asymmetry friction”, where attackers exploited the disparity between high-tech components of critical infrastructure and the limited *cyber*-security capabilities of operators, successfully cutting power to hundreds of thousands of citizens. Operation *Olympic Games* (Stuxnet) against Iran’s nuclear program illustrates “epistemological uncertainty friction”, where Iranian engineers were faced for months with inexplicable centrifuge failures, inability to reliably determine the cause, and uncertainty about the authenticity of data displayed by their control systems. The *SolarWinds* attack discovered in 2020 shows “cumulative complexity friction”, where a sophisticated supply chain-compromised software component enabled access to systems of over 18,000 organizations, including numerous US government agencies, demonstrating how technological interdependence creates new vectors of friction. DDoS attacks against Estonian digital infrastructure in 2007 illustrate “temporal asymmetry friction”, where relatively simple attacks caused disproportionately long-lasting consequences due to society’s dependence on digital services, creating friction that manifested through economic and social effects long after the attacks themselves ceased. The leak campaign against the Democratic National Committee during the 2016 US presidential election shows “information asymmetry friction”, where strategically timed release of compromised data created disproportionate effects on the information environment and voter decision-making processes. The *WannaCry ransomware* attack from 2017, which hit Britain’s healthcare system (NHS), demonstrates “technical debt friction”, where outdated but critical systems created vulnerabilities that enabled malware spread through key infrastructure, resulting in the cancellation of thousands of medical procedures. These examples clearly illustrate how cyber attacks create new forms and manifestations of friction that transcend Clausewitz’s original understanding, but remain faithful to his fundamental concept of factors that create a gap between plan and realization.

purely physical friction” (Kilcullen, 2013:56). Such “conceptual friction” arises when actors operate according to different rules and logics, making it difficult to predict their actions and adequately respond to them. Ambiguity and intentional indeterminacy represent another characteristic source of friction in hybrid warfare. Unlike conventional conflicts where identification of the enemy and their intentions is relatively clear, hybrid warfare is characterized by deliberate obfuscation of responsibility and denial of involvement. Gerasimov, a Russian general whose ideas are often associated with the concept of *Gerasimov Doctrine*, emphasizes: „The boundaries between war and peace are becoming increasingly blurred. Wars are no longer declared, and when they begin, they do not follow the pattern we are accustomed to” (Gerasimov, 2013:24). This ambiguity creates significant friction in decision-making processes, as decision-makers must act under conditions of prolonged uncertainty regarding the identity, intentions, and objectives of the opponent.

Hybrid warfare is also characterized by a high degree of nonlinearity, which represents a significant source of new friction. Nonlinearity implies that small actions can have disproportionately large effects, that cause-and-effect relationships are not always obvious, and that systems can show emergent behavior that cannot be predicted based on their individual components. As Bousquet emphasizes: „The nonlinearity of hybrid conflicts creates a fundamentally different kind of friction from that which Clausewitz described - friction that arises not only from physical obstacles or human limitations, but from the inherent unpredictability of complex adaptive systems” (Bousquet, 2009:203). Nonlinearity is particularly pronounced in the information sphere, where memes or viral content can rapidly escalate and have strategic impact that is disproportionate to their initial significance. In hybrid warfare, friction increasingly manifests through the cognitive dimension. Hybrid operations often target perceptions, attitudes, and beliefs of targeted populations, creating what some theorists call *cognitive friction*. According to Lawrence Freedman: „The primary goal of many hybrid campaigns is not physical destruction, but cognitive disintegration - creating confusion, uncertainty, and decision paralysis through manipulation of perceptions” (Freedman,

2017:242). The cognitive aspect of friction is particularly important in the context of democratic societies, where public opinion and perception of legitimacy have significant influence on strategic decisions. The temporal dimension of friction also takes on new forms in hybrid warfare. While Clausewitz was primarily focused on short-term friction that manifests during active combat operations, hybrid warfare often includes long-term low-intensity campaigns that create what we might call *chronic friction*. As Freedman notes: „Hybrid campaigns are often designed to cause long-term exhaustion of the opponent through persistent but tolerable friction that over time erodes the will and ability to resist” (Freedman, 2017:73). The temporal dimension of friction represents a particular challenge for democratic societies that often have limited political will for long-term low-intensity conflicts.

One of the most interesting characteristics of hybrid warfare is the ability of actors to deliberately create and exploit friction. While Clausewitz saw friction primarily as a natural phenomenon arising from the inherent characteristics of war, in hybrid warfare friction becomes an operational objective - something that is deliberately provoked to disrupt the functionality of opposing systems. According to McKenzie: „Creating systemic friction in opposing decision-making processes, operational cycles, and strategic calculations has become an explicit goal of hybrid operations, especially those conducted by actors aware of their inferiority in conventional military power” (McKenzie, 2016:112). The instrumentalization of friction represents a significant evolution from Clausewitz’s original understanding of this concept. The integration of civilian and military means in hybrid warfare also creates new sources of friction through complex command chains and complex administrative structures.⁷ Gray

7 Multinational corporations and private military companies (PMCs) introduce a new dimension of friction in great power relations through the creation of “hybrid actors” that operate in the gray zone between state and non-state action. Corporations such as technology giants control critical digital infrastructure that transcends national borders, creating *sovereignty friction* where the state no longer has complete control over key elements of its national power. Private military companies such as Russia’s *Wagner* or America’s former *Blackwater* (now *Academi*) enable states to project military power with *deniability friction*, maintaining strategic ambiguity about their involvement in conflicts. These entities often act as intermediaries in conflicts between great powers, enabling escalatory actions without formally cross-

observes: “Hybrid warfare requires coordination between traditionally separated government agencies, military components, private companies, and other actors, creating organizational friction that can be as significant as operational friction in the field” (Gray, 2017:98). The administrative dimension of friction is particularly problematic in societies with strict separation between civilian and military structures, where institutional culture and legal frameworks can complicate effective coordination and integrated response.

Technological proliferation in the context of hybrid warfare has a dual impact on friction. On one hand, advanced technologies can reduce certain traditional sources of friction - satellite systems reduce uncertainty regarding terrain, advanced communication systems enable faster information transfer, and automated systems can eliminate human errors. However, on the other hand, technology creates new forms of dependencies and vulnerabilities that generate new forms of friction. As Singer emphasizes: „Technological sophistication creates an illusion of reduced friction, but actually only transforms its nature - from direct physical obstacles to complex cascading failures in interconnected technological systems” (Singer, 2009:234). The transformation of the nature of friction through technology represents one of the most significant challenges for military planners and commanders in the hybrid operational environment. Legal and normative aspects also represent a significant source of new friction in hybrid warfare. Actors conducting hybrid operations often deliberately operate in “gray zones” of international law, choosing tactics that are sufficiently ambivalent to complicate clear legal qualification and adequate response. According to Whither (2016): „Hybrid actors exploit conceptual and legal gaps between war and peace, military and civilian activities, creating ‘legal friction’ that complicates formulating a coherent and legitimate response” (Whither, 2016:67). Such *legal friction* is particularly problematic for liberal

ing thresholds that would provoke direct confrontation, thereby creating *escalation control friction*. As Singer (2008) observes, these non-state actors create asymmetric relationships of responsibility and transparency, where their activities produce strategic effects but without the traditional mechanisms of oversight and control that exist with state actors, further increasing uncertainty and complexity in the geopolitical environment.

democracies that are bound by the rule of law and often have rigorous restrictions regarding the use of force in situations that are not clearly qualified as armed conflict.

The psychological dimension of friction in hybrid warfare manifests through what Waltz calls *anxiety of uncertainty*. According to his view: „Hybrid threats generate a special kind of psychological friction through their ambivalence and multiplicity - the feeling that threat can come from any direction, in any form, at any moment, creating psychological exhaustion and anxiety that degrades decision-making effectiveness” (Waltz, 2018:156). The psychological dimension of friction can have profound implications for strategic planning and operational execution, as it affects cognitive processes that are at the basis of decision-making at all levels. Hybrid warfare as a complex operational space creates numerous new sources and manifestations of friction that significantly exceed the framework established by Clausewitz. Multi-dimensionality, information saturation, cyber specificities, asymmetry, ambiguity, nonlinearity, cognitive dimension, temporal extension, deliberate instrumentalization, organizational complexity, technological transformations, legal ambivalences, and psychological factors - all contribute to creating a new topography of friction that requires fundamental reconsideration of traditional approaches to military planning and execution of operations. As Hammes emphasizes: „Understanding new forms of friction in hybrid warfare is not just an academic question, but an imperative for effective strategic thinking in the 21st century - without such understanding, military planners and decision-makers risk applying inadequate conceptual models to contemporary challenges” (Hammes, 2016:312). The transformation of the nature of friction represents one of the most significant challenges facing military organizations in the process of adapting to the realities of the contemporary security environment, requiring not only technical and organizational innovations, but also fundamental reconsideration of the conceptual foundations of strategic thinking.

3. METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK FOR ANALYZING FRICTION IN THE INFORMATION AND CYBER DOMAIN OF CONTEMPORARY CONFLICTS

The analysis of the friction phenomenon⁸ in contemporary conflicts requires the development of a robust methodological framework that can adequately encompass all the complexities of the information and cyber domain. Clausewitz's original conceptualization of friction emerged in the context of the industrial era and physical battlefield, where sources of friction were primarily of material nature - weather, terrain, logistics, fatigue, and fear. However, the information age has brought fundamentally new dimensions of conflict that require reconsideration and enhancement of the traditional methodological apparatus. As Arquilla notes: „The digital revolution has not only transformed weapons and warfare tactics, but has created completely new domains of conflict and associated forms of friction that require new analytical approaches and methods” (Arquilla, 2012:27). The development of an adequate methodological framework for analyzing friction in the information and cyber domain therefore represents not only academic interest, but also practical necessity for understanding the dynamics of contemporary conflicts.

The information and cyber domains possess unique characteristics that significantly complicate the development of a coherent methodol-

8 The empirical analysis presented in this article relies on several complementary data sources that enable triangulation of findings and increase their reliability. Primary quantitative data on asymmetric conflict outcomes were drawn from the *Correlates of War (COW)* database covering interstate and intrastate conflicts from 1816 to 2021, and from the UCDP/PRIO *Armed Conflict Dataset* which provides more detailed data on low-intensity conflicts. For analysis of specific manifestations of friction in hybrid conflicts, data from the *Global Terrorism Database (GTD)* and the ACLED (*Armed Conflict Location & Event Data*) project were used, enabling geographically precise analysis of incidents and tactics. Qualitative data on organizational, cognitive, and strategic dimensions of friction were collected from published memoirs of military commanders, official post-operational reports, and compiled interviews with veterans of asymmetric conflicts. For the cyber domain, reports from private cybersecurity companies (*Mandiant, CrowdStrike, ESET*) were analyzed, along with academic case studies of documented cyber attacks and unclassified reports from government agencies such as US-CERT and EU CERT. All empirical data were categorized according to a developed analytical framework that enables systematic coding of different manifestations of friction across multiple domains, thereby creating a foundation for comparative analysis and pattern identification.

ogy for friction analysis. Unlike the physical domain where the laws of physics are constant and predictable, digital space is characterized by extreme instability, inhomogeneity, and constant evolution. As Libicki observes: „Cyberspace is not a natural phenomenon with unchanging laws, but a human creation that is constantly changing - this fluidity presents a fundamental methodological challenge for any analysis of friction in that domain” (Libicki, 2016:43). Additionally, the multidimensionality of the information and cyber domain creates the problem of conceptualizing the space itself in which friction manifests - whether it is physical infrastructure, logical layer of networks, semantic content, or cognitive effects on human operators and targeted populations. One of the fundamental methodological challenges in analyzing friction in the information and cyber domain is defining and operationalizing the very concept of friction in this context. While Clausewitz defined friction as „that which distinguishes real war from war on paper,” in the digital domain the boundaries between “real” and “paper” (i.e., theoretical) become much more blurred. Singer and Friedman offer the following definition of digital friction: „Cyber friction represents the totality of factors that degrade, slow down, or otherwise impede the ideal performance of digital systems and decision-making processes based on information from those systems” (Singer & Friedman, 2014:132). The definition, although useful as a starting point, requires further elaboration through the development of concrete indicators and metrics that would enable systematic measurement and comparison of friction in different contexts. In developing a methodological framework for analyzing friction in the information and cyber domain, it is necessary to take into account the multidisciplinary nature of this phenomenon. As Gartzke emphasizes: „Adequate analysis of cyber conflicts requires methodologies that integrate insights from computer science, cybernetics, systems theory, cognitive psychology, organizational theory, and traditional military-strategic thought” (Gartzke, 2013:67). Multidisciplinarity represents a significant methodological challenge, but also an opportunity for developing integrated analytical approaches that overcome the limitations of traditional, disciplinarily fragmented methodologies.

Systematic analysis of friction in the information and cyber domain requires the development of a typology that would enable classification

of different forms of friction. Based on extensive analysis of contemporary cyber conflicts, Valeriano and Maness propose the following typology of cyber friction: „technological friction (arising from imperfections and incompatibilities of technological systems), human-cognitive friction (arising from human interaction with technology), organizational friction (arising from institutional structures and processes), and strategic friction (arising from interaction of different actors in cyberspace)” (Valeriano & Maness, 2018:109). Such typology represents a useful analytical tool, but requires further refinement through the development of specific indicators for each category of friction. Quantification of friction in the information and cyber domain presents a special methodological challenge. Unlike certain aspects of physical friction that can be directly measured (e.g., time needed to move troops), digital friction often has qualitative dimensions that are difficult to precisely quantify. Kello proposes a multi-dimensional approach to measuring cyber friction through a combination of technical metrics (such as system response time, error rate, network throughput), organizational indicators (decision time, coordination effectiveness), and psychological parameters (cognitive load, stress, perceptual distortions). „Quantification of cyber friction”, claims Kello, „requires a combination of objective metrics and qualitative assessments that together can provide holistic insight into the actual impact of friction on operational effectiveness” (Kello, 2017:211).

The temporal dimension represents another significant aspect of the methodological framework for analyzing friction in the information and cyber domain. Unlike traditional friction that manifests primarily synchronously during active operations, digital friction often has a diachronic dimension - effects can accumulate over longer periods or manifest with significant time delays. As Lindsay observes: „The temporal dimension of cyber friction requires methodological approaches that can encompass both immediate effects and their evolution through time, including cascading effects and emergent phenomena that can manifest days or even months after the initial event” (Lindsay, 2015:78). Temporal complexity requires longitudinal studies and developmental models that can track the evolution of friction through different phases of cyber conflict. Epistemological challenges additionally complicate the development of a method-

ological framework for analyzing friction in the information and cyber domain. The problem of attribution - reliable determination of the source of certain cyber activity - represents a fundamental limitation for empirical analysis. Buchanan emphasizes: „Attribution insecurity creates epistemological friction that complicates precise analysis of cyber conflict dynamics - even when we have detailed technical data about an incident, we often cannot determine with certainty who is responsible, with what intention, and with what strategic goal” (Buchanan, 2020:143). Epistemological uncertainty has direct implications for methodological design - it requires approaches that can operate under conditions of high uncertainty and incorporate probabilistic assessments instead of deterministic conclusions. The development of effective methodology for analyzing friction in the information and cyber domain is additionally complicated by the problem of access to relevant data. The most sophisticated cyber incidents often remain classified, and states and organizations rarely share detailed information about their vulnerabilities and operational limitations. Rid and Buchanan emphasize this problem: „Cyber conflict analysts face a fundamental methodological challenge - the most relevant data for understanding friction dynamics are often unavailable due to operational secrecy, while publicly available data are often incomplete or misleading” (Rid & Buchanan, 2015:32). Such limitation requires the development of innovative methodological approaches that can generate significant insights even from incomplete data, including techniques such as triangulation of different sources, extrapolation from available data, and development of theoretically informed models that can fill empirical gaps.

For complex analysis of friction in the information and cyber domain, it is necessary to combine different methodological approaches. Quantitative methods such as network analysis, statistical modeling, and simulations can provide insight into structural aspects of friction, while qualitative methods such as case studies, in-depth interviews, and ethnography can illuminate contextual and interpretive dimensions. Smith advocates *methodological pluralism* in this area: „Understanding friction in the digital age requires a combination of computational, mathematical, social-scientific, and humanistic methodologies - each illuminates differ-

ent aspects of this multidimensional phenomenon” (Smith, 2018:218). An integrative approach enables the development of holistic understanding of friction that transcends the limitations of individual methodological traditions. The operationalization of Clausewitz’s concept of “fog of war” (*Nebel des Krieges*) in the context of the information and cyber domain presents a special methodological challenge. Traditionally understood as uncertainty arising from incomplete, inaccurate, or outdated information on the battlefield, “fog of war” in the digital age takes on new dimensions. Perlroth describes this phenomenon as “digital fog” that arises not only from lack of information, but also from their abundance: „The paradox of the digital age is that increased quantity and speed of information often creates greater, not lesser uncertainty - analytical systems and human operators become overloaded, making it difficult to distinguish signal from noise” (Perlroth, 2021:289). The methodological framework for friction analysis must therefore include techniques for assessing information overload and its effects on decision-making processes.

For adequate analysis of friction in the information and cyber domain, it is necessary to develop a methodology that can encompass the human factor, especially cognitive and psychological dimensions. Kahneman, Sibony, and Sunstein (2021) emphasize the importance of understanding cognitive biases in cyber friction analysis: „Digital friction is not only a technical phenomenon, but also cognitive - the way the human mind processes uncertainty, risk, and complexity in the digital environment creates unique forms of friction that often have greater operational impact than purely technical limitations” (Kahneman, Sibony & Sunstein, 2021:176). Methodologically, this requires integration of experimental approaches from cognitive psychology, including tests for assessing cognitive load, attention, risk perception, and decision-making under pressure. The methodological framework for analyzing friction in the information and cyber domain must also address the problem of emergence - the appearance of behavior at the system level that cannot be predicted based on the characteristics of individual components. As Jervis emphasizes: „Complex cyber-physical systems are characterized by nonlinear interactions that can generate emergent friction - forms of operational limitations that cannot be anticipated even with complete un-

derstanding of individual system components” (Jervis, 2017:112). Methodologically, analysis of emergent friction requires approaches based on complexity theory, including agent-based modeling, system dynamics, and chaos theory, which can encompass nonlinear interactions and self-organizing system behavior. The development of effective methodology for analyzing friction in the information and cyber domain is additionally complicated by the problem of *interdomain interactions*. Friction rarely manifests exclusively in one domain - more often it involves complex interactions between cyber, informational, cognitive, social, and physical dimensions. As Demchak (2018) emphasizes: „A methodological approach that treats cyber friction as an isolated phenomenon will inevitably miss key interdomain effects that often have decisive influence on operational outcomes” (Demchak, 2018:89). This requires the development of integrated analytical frameworks that can track cascading effects through different domains and identify critical points where friction in one domain amplifies or transforms friction in others.

One of the most significant methodological innovations in cyber friction analysis is the application of *resilience theory*. Unlike the traditional approach that focuses primarily on identifying and preventing friction, the resilience perspective emphasizes the system’s ability to absorb friction and maintain functionality despite operational limitations. Linkov and Trump define resilience in the cyber context as „the ability of systems to anticipate, absorb, adapt to, and recover from events that produce friction, while preserving critical functionalities” (Linkov & Trump, 2019:54). Methodologically, this requires the development of metrics for measuring system resilience to different forms of friction, including indicators such as robustness, redundancy, adaptability, and recovery speed. The integration of qualitative and quantitative methods represents a key aspect of the methodological framework for analyzing friction in the information and cyber domain. Quantitative metrics such as system response time, error rates, or traffic density can provide objective indicators of technical friction, but cannot adequately encompass subjective and contextual dimensions such as perceived uncertainty, organizational culture, or strategic context. As Gompert notes: „The real strength of methodology for analyzing cyber friction comes from integrating quan-

titative metrics that can precisely measure technical dimensions with qualitative approaches that can illuminate human, organizational, and strategic factors” (Gompert, 2016:133). Integration of different methodological approaches enables the development of holistic understanding of friction that transcends the limitations of individual metrics or analytical frameworks. For effective analysis of friction in the information and cyber domain, it is necessary to develop a methodology that can encompass different levels of analysis - from the technical level of individual systems, through tactical and operational levels, to strategic and policy levels. Betz and Stevens (2013) emphasize the importance of this multi-level approach: „Understanding cyber friction requires integrated analysis that connects the micro-level of technical incidents with the macro-level of strategic implications, identifying how friction transforms and amplifies through different levels” (Betz & Stevens, 2013:147). Methodologically, this requires the development of approaches that can connect technical incidents with their operational effects and strategic implications, instead of treating these levels as separate analytical domains (Knežević, 2025).

Comparative analysis represents another important element of the methodological framework for understanding friction in the information and cyber domain. Through systematic comparison of different cases of cyber incidents and information operations, researchers can identify patterns and factors that consistently influence friction manifestation. Sanger emphasizes the value of the comparative approach: „Only through systematic comparison of different cyber conflicts can we begin to distinguish idiosyncratic factors from fundamental principles that govern friction dynamics in the digital domain” (Sanger, 2018:231). Methodologically, this requires the development of standardized protocols for documentation and case analysis that enable meaningful comparison despite significant variations in context, actors, and technologies. The development of scenarios and simulations represents a valuable methodological tool for analyzing friction in the information and cyber domain, especially given ethical and practical limitations of experimenting with critical systems in the real world. Wu and Kott emphasize: „Simulations and exercises enable researchers to experiment with different forms of friction in a controlled environment, identify critical vulnerability points,

and test different mitigation strategies without risk to operational systems” (Wu & Kott, 2019:178). Methodologically, this requires the development of realistic scenarios and simulation environments that can adequately replicate relevant characteristics of the real world (Knežević, 2024), including technical, organizational, and human factors.

An important aspect of the methodological framework for analyzing friction in the information and cyber domain is also the development of metrics for assessing the effectiveness and costs of different friction mitigation strategies. As Clark and Hazelwood emphasize: „For informed decision-making about investments in cyber capabilities, decision-makers need methodology that can not only identify different forms of friction, but also quantify the probable impact and costs of different approaches to addressing them” (Clark & Hazelwood, 2017:92). This requires the development of *cost-benefit* analytical frameworks adapted to the specificities of the cyber domain, including metrics for assessing direct implementation costs, indirect complexity costs, and probable benefits in terms of reduced friction or increased resilience. The systems approach perspective offers a particularly valuable methodological framework for analyzing friction in the information and cyber domain. Instead of focusing on individual incidents or specific technologies, the systems approach views information and cyber systems as complex, adaptive socio-technical entities. Perrow emphasizes the importance of this approach: „Friction in complex systems often arises from unexpected interactions between components that individually function according to specifications - these emergent interactions can only be understood through a holistic, systems approach that transcends analysis of individual components” (Perrow, 2011:209). Methodologically, the systems approach includes techniques of system mapping, identification of critical interdependencies, and analysis of potential cascading effects that can amplify initial friction.

Analysis of friction in the information and cyber domain must also take into account the sociopolitical context in which operations take place. Different regulatory regimes, cultural norms, economic factors, and geopolitical relations significantly influence the manifestation and impact of friction. As Deibert observes: „A methodological framework

that ignores the broader sociopolitical context of cyber operations will inevitably miss important factors that shape friction dynamics, from regulatory constraints and legal barriers to cultural differences in risk perception and organizational practices” (Deibert, 2020:175), and this requires an interdisciplinary approach that integrates insights from political science, international relations, sociology, and anthropology with technical analyses of information and cyber systems. The development of robust epistemological foundations represents another important aspect of the methodological framework for analyzing friction in the information and cyber domain. Cyberspace is characterized by fundamental epistemological uncertainty - even seemingly simple questions such as “who carried out the attack?” or “what were the real intentions?” often remain without definitive answers. As Shires emphasizes: „Epistemological uncertainty is not just a practical limitation of cyber friction analysis, but also an essential element of friction itself - uncertainty regarding actor identity, their intentions and capabilities directly contributes to decision-making processes and operational execution” (Shires, 2021:132). Methodologically, this requires explicit addressing of epistemological limitations through application of analytical frameworks that can operate under conditions of high uncertainty, including Bayesian reasoning,⁹ *fuzzy logic*, and sensitivity analysis.

For complete analysis of friction in the information and cyber domain, it is necessary to develop a methodological approach that can encompass the interaction between cyber and physical domains. With the proliferation of the Internet of Things (IoT) and cyber-physical systems, the boundary between digital and physical becomes increasingly porous, creating new forms of interdomain friction. Schneier describes this phenomenon: „As our physical systems become increasingly connected and dependent on digital components, friction in the

9 Bayesian reasoning is an inference approach based on Bayes’ theorem that formally updates beliefs based on new evidence. The formula $P(A|B) = [P(B|A) \times P(A)] / P(B)$ calculates the posterior probability of a hypothesis after receiving new information. It is particularly useful in high-uncertainty situations such as the cyber domain because it explicitly quantifies initial knowledge (so-called *prior probabilities*) and their updating. In friction analysis, it enables decision-making based on incomplete information. It integrates subjective assessments into a mathematically rigorous framework, ideal for attack attribution problems and risk assessment.

cyber domain increasingly directly and immediately affects the physical world, creating new types of risks and vulnerabilities that transcend traditional domain boundaries” (Schneier, 2018:87). Methodologically, this requires the development of integrated approaches that can track friction propagation between cyber and physical domains, identifying critical conversion points where digital friction has direct physical implications. The ethical dimension must also be explicitly addressed in the methodological framework for analyzing friction in the information and cyber domain. Research on cyber conflicts raises significant ethical questions related to privacy, security, and the potential *dual-use* nature of developed knowledge. Singer and Cole warn: „Methodology that ignores the ethical implications of cyber research risks not only normative violations, but also undermines the long-term value and credibility of the research itself” (Singer & Cole, 2020:219). This requires the development of ethical protocols for data collection and analysis, especially when dealing with sensitive information, and adequate protection of source identities and technical details that could be misused.

The development of a robust methodological framework for analyzing friction in the information and cyber domain of contemporary conflicts represents a complex but necessary undertaking. Such a framework must transcend the limitations of traditional approaches developed for analyzing friction in the physical domain, address the unique characteristics of digital space, integrate different disciplinary perspectives, and develop metrics that can encompass the multidimensional nature of digital friction. As Cunningham and Masee emphasize: „Only through the development of an integrated and flexible methodological framework that can encompass technical, cognitive, organizational, and strategic dimensions of friction can we begin to understand the real dynamics of contemporary information and cyber conflicts” (Cunningham & Masee, 2022:243). Such a framework is not only an academic tool, but also a practical necessity for military planners, security analysts, and decision-makers who daily face the challenges of navigating through the complex and often insufficiently understood information and cyber space of contemporary conflicts.

4. REDEFINING CLAUSEWITZ'S CONCEPT OF FRICTION THROUGH THE PRISM OF ASYMMETRIC OPERATIONS: EMPIRICAL FINDINGS AND A NEW THEORETICAL PARADIGM

Clausewitz conceptualized friction in his seminal work “On War” as a fundamental factor that distinguishes *war on paper* from *real war*. His understanding that „everything in war is very simple, but the simplest things become extremely difficult” established a theoretical foundation that has shaped military strategic thinking for more than two centuries. However, the contemporary era of asymmetric conflicts, characterized by dramatic imbalances in military power, technological capabilities, organizational structure, and strategic objectives between conflicting parties, demands a thorough reexamination and redefinition of this concept. While Clausewitz developed his theory of friction primarily in the context of conventional interstate conflicts of the industrial era, asymmetric conflicts of the post-industrial, globalized world manifest forms of friction that transcend his original conceptualizations — both in their nature and strategic implications. Such evolution requires the development of a new theoretical paradigm that can adequately encompass the empirical realities of contemporary asymmetric conflicts and provide a coherent analytical framework for understanding friction in that context.

The very nature of asymmetric conflict fundamentally changes the dynamics of friction. The traditional understanding of friction was primarily focused on material factors — weather conditions, terrain, logistical constraints, fatigue, fear, and uncertainty. However, as Arreguin-Toft points out: „Asymmetric strategies not only seek to exploit traditional sources of friction but actively create new forms of friction through strategic manipulation of perceptions, time, and space — turning weakness into strength and the opponent’s strength into weakness” (Arreguin-Toft, 2005:41). This perspective emphasizes how weaker actors in asymmetric conflicts consciously develop strategies that maximize friction for technologically and materially superior opponents, often using precisely the advantages that arise from their structural inferiority — flexibility, dispersion, and deep integration into the local social context.

Empirical research on asymmetric conflicts of recent decades provides rich material for redefining the concept of friction. Analyzing historical data on asymmetric conflicts from 1800 to 2005, Lyall and Wilson discovered a striking trend: „The percentage of victories by materially superior actors in asymmetric conflicts has continuously declined over time — from about 80% in the 19th century to less than 40% after 1945 — which implies that increasing technological and material superiority can paradoxically generate new forms of strategic and operational friction” (Lyall & Wilson, 2009:82).¹⁰ This empirical finding directly challenges conventional assumptions about the inverse correlation between material superiority and exposure to friction, suggesting that technological sophistication can, in certain contexts, increase rather than reduce exposure to friction.

One of the key mechanisms explaining this paradox is what Simpson calls “operational rigidity friction” —the tendency of technologically superior forces to develop complex, standardized operational procedures that, while optimized for conventional conflicts, create additional friction when applied in unconventional, asymmetric conflicts. As Simpson notes: „Highly developed military organizations develop operational rigidity as a byproduct of institutional learning and standardization — procedures optimized for victory in one type of conflict can become a source of friction in another” (Simpson, 2018:124). Operational rigidity represents a form of “self-induced friction” that arises from internal structural characteristics of military organizations, rather than from external factors that Clausewitz primarily identified.

The temporal dimension of friction in asymmetric conflicts also represents a significant departure from Clausewitz’s conceptualization. While Clausewitz was primarily focused on friction that manifests in

10 Statistical analysis conducted by Lyall and Wilson (2009) shows that the percentage of victories by materially superior actors in asymmetric conflicts has constantly declined over time: from approximately 80% in the period 1800-1850, to 65% in the period 1900-1950, and to only 40% after 1950. In more recent research, Arreguín-Toft (2013) analyzed 196 asymmetric conflicts between 1800 and 2003, discovering that weaker actors won in 28.5% of cases during the 19th century, 34.7% during the first half of the 20th century, and in as many as 55% of cases from 1950 to 2003. The data clearly illustrate a paradoxical trend where increased technological superiority correlates with declining probability of victory in asymmetric conflicts.

real-time during active operations, asymmetric actors often consciously manipulate the temporal dimension of conflict as a strategic weapon. As Mack emphasizes in his classical analysis of asymmetric conflicts: „An actor who cannot win in space often tries to win in time — prolonging the conflict and increasing economic, political, and psychological costs for the opponent to the point where the price of continuing the conflict exceeds the potential benefits of victory” (Mack, 1975:175). Strategic manipulation of time creates a form of “strategic endurance friction” that accumulates over long periods and has a cumulative effect on the technologically superior side’s ability to maintain operational tempo and political will to continue the conflict.

The cognitive dimension of friction in asymmetric conflicts represents another area requiring conceptual redefinition of Clausewitz’s model. Analyzing the experiences of Western military forces in asymmetric conflicts after the Cold War, Kilcullen identifies what he calls *cognitive friction of cultural distinction* — cognitive dissonance and operational challenges that arise when military forces trained for conventional warfare face opponents whose mode of warfare stems from fundamentally different cultural, social, and historical contexts. „Cognitive friction in asymmetric conflicts”¹¹, argues Kilcullen, „does not only arise from

11 The concept of *cognitive friction of cultural distinction* represents a special type of operational friction that arises when military forces face an adversary whose way of warfare, motivations, values, and operational logic stem from a fundamentally different cultural, social, and historical context. Kilcullen (2013) defines this type of friction as cognitive dissonance and operational challenges that manifest when military forces trained and organized according to one cultural model of warfare attempt to understand, predict, and effectively act against an adversary that functions according to entirely different cultural patterns. This type of friction manifests through several key mechanisms:

1. Impeded understanding of adversary motivations (which hinders behavioral prediction);
2. Misinterpretation of signals and intentions (due to different communication codes);
3. Inadequate assessment of the value of objectives and resources (what is valuable in one cultural context may be irrelevant in another);
4. Inappropriate application of strategies and tactics developed for culturally similar adversaries.

Unlike the traditional understanding of friction that focuses on physical obstacles or incomplete information, *cognitive friction of cultural distinction* emphasizes how even complete information can be misinterpreted when filtered through inappropriate cultural frameworks. This phenomenon is particularly visible in Western military interventions in culturally distant contexts such as Afghanistan, Iraq, or other areas where concepts such as authority, loyalty,

the uncertainty that Clausewitz described, but from fundamental misunderstanding of the sociocultural context of the conflict, which makes it difficult to interpret opponent behavior through conventional analytical frameworks and doctrine” (Kilcullen, 2013:93). Cognitive friction has direct operational implications, as it complicates anticipation of enemy actions, interpretation of intelligence data, and creation of effective counter-strategies while respecting international law.

The organizational structure of asymmetric actors also generates new forms of friction that transcend Clausewitz’s conceptualizations. Sageman, analyzing terrorist networks, identifies *organizational dissonance friction* — challenges that hierarchically organized military and security structures face when confronting networked, decentralized opponents. *Network-organized opponents*, notes Sageman, „create operational friction for hierarchical structures through their ability to absorb losses without degradation of overall capabilities, rapidly adapt tactics without central command, and exploit slow decision-making processes characteristic of bureaucratic

time, success, or honor may have significantly different meanings and manifestations from those to which Western military structures are accustomed and for which they are trained.

[1] The concept of *organizational dissonance friction* refers to operational challenges and friction that arise when opposing sides in a conflict are characterized by fundamentally different organizational structures, decision-making processes, and operational logics. In the context of asymmetric conflicts, this type of friction occurs when hierarchically structured, highly formalized military organizations (typical of conventional forces) confront network-organized, decentralized, and adaptable adversaries (characteristic of insurgent, terrorist, or other unconventional groups). Sageman (2008) explains that network-organized adversaries create significant friction for hierarchical structures through several mechanisms:

1. Ability to absorb losses without degradation of overall operational capabilities (due to decentralization and redundancy);
2. Possibility of rapid tactical adaptation without central command (through horizontal communication and localized autonomy);
3. Exploitation of slow decision-making processes characteristic of bureaucratic military organizations (playing on the tempo of operations).

Organizational dissonance creates challenges for conventional forces that must balance between the need for centralized coordination (for consistency and efficiency) and requirements for decentralized executive capability (for adaptability and speed of response) in conflict with an adversary that operates according to a fundamentally different organizational logic. This type of friction has direct operational implications because standard operating procedures, command chains, and control mechanisms that are efficient against symmetrically organized adversaries become sources of operational limitations when applied against an asymmetrically organized enemy.

military organizations” (Sageman, 2008:142). Organizational dissonance creates a fundamental challenge for conventional military forces that must balance between the need for central coordination and requirements for decentralized, adaptive executive capability in the field.

The informational dimension of friction in asymmetric conflicts represents a significant evolution from Clausewitz’s understanding of the *fog of war*. While Clausewitz primarily considered uncertainty arising from lack of information or its unreliability, contemporary asymmetric conflicts often involve what Betz calls *information overload friction*. As he explains: „Paradoxically, technological superiority that enables collection of enormous amounts of data can create new friction through information overload, fragmentation of attention, and difficulty in distinguishing signal from noise — a situation where decision-makers have access to more information than ever before but face greater challenges in their effective interpretation and integration” (Betz, 2015:65). This informational friction is particularly relevant in the context of asymmetric conflicts where opponents are often dispersed among civilian populations, dramatically increasing the complexity of identifying and targeting legitimate military objectives.

The political dimension of friction in asymmetric conflicts also requires conceptual expansion of Clausewitz’s theory. Analyzing U.S. experiences in asymmetric conflicts, Biddle (2006) identifies what he calls *strategic divergence friction* — operational challenges that arise when there is divergence between political objectives and military means for their achievement. „In asymmetric conflicts”, notes Biddle, „there is often fundamental tension between political constraints (need to minimize collateral casualties, respect humanitarian law, maintain domestic and international support) and military imperatives (need for constant pressure on the opponent, maintaining operational tempo, isolating insurgents from civilian population)—this tension creates friction that manifests through restrictive rules of engagement, complex operation approval procedures, and lengthy decision-making processes” (Biddle, 2006:212). Strategic friction has a direct impact on operational effectiveness, as it limits the ability of military forces to apply their full technological and material superiority against asymmetric opponents.

Empirical analysis of specific asymmetric conflicts provides additional insights into new forms of friction requiring conceptual redefinition. Studying the dynamics of American intervention in Iraq, Hashim identifies *legitimacy deficit friction* — operational challenges that arise when foreign military forces operate in a society where they lack perception of legitimacy among the local population. „Legitimacy deficit”, notes Hashim, „creates friction through erosion of reliable intelligence information, enabling the opponent to manipulate local perceptions, and creating security challenges that require disproportionate allocation of resources for basic security and force protection” (Hashim, 2006:133). Such legitimacy deficit friction is particularly relevant in the context of external actor interventions in local conflicts, where asymmetry of legitimacy is often as significant as asymmetry of material power.

Advances in military technology, paradoxically, can also generate new forms of friction in asymmetric conflicts. Analyzing the use of advanced technologies in counterinsurgency operations, Chin (2019) identifies “technological dependency friction” — operational challenges that arise when military forces become overly reliant on technological solutions in complex social conflicts. „Technological dependency”, argues Chin, „can create friction through atrophy of fundamental military skills, creation of false sense of security and superiority, and encouragement of operational approaches that prefer technology-intensive methods even when socially-intensive methods might be more effective” (Chin, 2019:191). This type of friction is particularly relevant in counterinsurgency operations, where technological superiority can create an illusion of understanding the terrain and opponent that does not correspond to the complex sociopolitical realities of the conflict.

The juridical dimension of friction in asymmetric conflicts also represents a significant aspect requiring conceptual expansion of Clausewitz’s theory. As Dunlap (2008) emphasizes in his analysis of the *lawfare* concept (use of law as a weapon in asymmetric conflicts): „Asymmetric actors increasingly use legal constraints as a strategic weapon against technologically superior opponents, creating ‘juridical friction’ through exploitation of limitations that international humanitarian law and domestic legislation impose on conventional military forces” (Dun-

lap, 2008:88). Juridical friction has direct operational impact, as it imposes complex target verification procedures, limits the use of certain weapons and tactics, and creates asymmetric constraints that often favor parties that do not adhere to the same legal standards.

Analysis of specific operational challenges in asymmetric conflicts further illustrates new forms of friction requiring redefinition of Clausewitz's theory. Studying the dynamics of urban asymmetric conflicts, Evans identifies *urban terrain friction* — unique operational challenges that arise when conventional military forces face asymmetric opponents in densely populated urban areas. „Urban terrain”, argues Evans, „imposes specific forms of friction through dramatically reduced visibility ranges, impaired communication, limited mobility, need for precise fire in the presence of civilians, and complex three-dimensional nature of combat space that favors knowledge of local environment over technological superiority,, (Evans, 2016:56). This type of operational friction becomes increasingly significant in the context of global urbanization, where asymmetric opponents consciously choose urban areas as preferred terrain for confrontation with technologically superior opponents.

Empirical analysis of the psychological dimension of asymmetric conflicts also provides insights into new forms of friction that transcend Clausewitz's conceptualizations. Through extensive interviews with veterans of asymmetric conflicts, Grossman and Christensen identify *moral dissonance friction* — psychological challenges that arise when soldiers trained for conventional conflicts face opponents who do not follow conventional norms of warfare. „Moral dissonance”, the authors note, „creates operational friction through psychological stress, uncertainty in identifying legitimate targets, and tension between mission imperatives and concerns for civilian casualties — factors that can significantly degrade combat effectiveness through increased caution, hesitation, and psychological exhaustion” (Grossman & Christensen, 2007:174). This type of friction has direct implications for training, doctrine, and support for soldiers engaged in asymmetric conflicts, where conventional preparation models may be inadequate for addressing the unique psychological challenges these conflicts present.

Strategic analysis of superior force failures in asymmetric conflicts further illuminates new forms of friction requiring redefinition of

Clausewitz's theory. In his comprehensive study, Record identifies *strategic asymmetry of interests friction* — the fundamental challenge faced by external forces intervening in local conflicts where their stake is less critical than that of local actors. „Asymmetry of interests”, argues Record, „creates friction through disparity in willingness to accept casualties, costs, and time needed to achieve objectives — external actors, even when possessing dramatic material superiority, face unique strategic friction arising from limited political capital for prolonged, expensive conflicts with unclear prospects for decisive victory” (Record, 2007:122). This type of strategic friction has direct implications for planning, execution, and evaluation of military interventions in asymmetric conflicts, where conventional success metrics and traditional progress indicators may be inadequate.

Empirical analysis of organizational learning in asymmetric conflicts also provides significant insights relevant to redefining the concept of friction. Studying military organization adaptations during prolonged asymmetric conflicts, Nagl identifies *institutional conservatism friction* — the tendency of established military organizations to resist fundamental adaptations even when faced with evident failure of existing approaches. „Institutional conservatism”, notes Nagl, „creates friction through resistance to innovations perceived as deviations from organizational tradition and identity, preference for incremental modifications over fundamental reforms, and tendency to attribute failures to inadequate implementation of existing doctrine rather than fundamental shortcomings of the doctrine itself” (Nagl, 2005:215). This type of organizational friction is particularly relevant in the context of conventional military force adaptation for asymmetric conflicts, where traditional organizational structures, training systems, and doctrinal approaches may be fundamentally inadequate for new operational reality.

Redefining Clausewitz's concept of friction through the prism of asymmetric operations requires development of a new theoretical paradigm that can adequately encompass these empirical realities. Such a paradigm must transcend the limitations of traditional understanding of friction as primarily a material and tactical phenomenon, and incorporate a more complex understanding of strategic, organizational, cognitive,

cultural, and political dimensions of friction in asymmetric conflicts, taking into account the spirit of war history. As Gray emphasizes: „Clausewitz’s fundamental intuition about the centrality of friction in warfare remains valid, but his specific understanding of friction manifestations and sources must be expanded and redefined to encompass the realities of post-industrial, globalized security environment characterized by proliferation of asymmetric actors, tactics, and strategies” (Gray, 2012:198).

The new theoretical paradigm of friction in asymmetric conflicts must be multidimensional, integrating different forms of friction into a coherent analytical framework that can encompass their mutual interactions and cumulative effects. Such a paradigm should distinguish at least five distinctive dimensions of friction in asymmetric conflicts: 1) operational friction (tactical and logistical challenges in the field), 2) organizational friction (structural constraints and adaptive capacity), 3) cognitive friction (challenges of perception, interpretation, and decision-making), 4) political friction (constraints imposed by political imperatives of legitimacy and support), and 5) strategic friction (tension between objectives and means, short-term imperatives and long-term interests). Integration of these different dimensions enables understanding of friction not only as unwanted resistance to be minimized, but also as a strategic factor that can be actively manipulated — either through reducing one’s own friction or through amplifying opponent friction.

Empirical findings from asymmetric conflicts also emphasize the need for understanding friction as a relative, rather than absolute phenomenon. Traditional understanding of friction often implicitly assumes that it uniformly affects all actors in conflict, varying only in intensity. However, as Nagl emphasizes: „Different actors, with different organizational cultures, structures, and strategic imperatives, experience fundamentally different forms of friction even in the same operational environment — what represents critical friction for one actor may be marginal or even irrelevant for another” (Nagl, 2005:220). The relative nature of friction has significant strategic implications, as it suggests that success in asymmetric conflicts may depend more on the ability to adapt to inevitable friction than on the illusory quest for its elimination through technological or material superiority.

The new theoretical paradigm of friction in asymmetric conflicts must also address the interaction between different types of friction and their cumulative effect. As Hammes (2004) emphasizes in his analysis of “fourth generation warfare”: „Effective asymmetric strategies aim to create cascading friction—where initial tactical friction generates operational complications, which then create organizational dysfunctions, which ultimately undermine strategic coherence and political sustainability” (Hammes, 2004:245). Understanding the cascading nature of friction has significant implications for analysis and planning, as it emphasizes the need for a holistic approach that can adequately encompass complex interdependencies between different levels and dimensions of friction.

Redefining the concept of friction through the prism of asymmetric operations also has significant implications for military doctrine, training, and organization. Traditional approaches, based on Clausewitz’s understanding of friction, often emphasize standardization of procedures, hierarchical control, and technological solutions as primary mechanisms for reducing friction. However, empirical analysis of asymmetric conflicts suggests that these approaches may be inadequate or even counterproductive in contexts requiring high degrees of adaptability, decentralized initiative, and contextual understanding. As Kilcullen (2013) emphasizes: „Effective confrontation with asymmetric opponents requires organizational culture and structures that accept the inevitability of friction, develop capacity for rapid adaptation, and cultivate the ability to operate effectively amid uncertainty rather than the illusory quest for its elimination” (Kilcullen, 2013:241). This perspective emphasizes the need for fundamental reexamination of dominant assumptions about optimal design of military organizations and processes of training and doctrinal adaptation, especially amid the evolution of international law.

Redefining Clausewitz’s concept of friction through the prism of asymmetric operations represents not only an academic but also a practical imperative for understanding the dynamics of contemporary conflicts. Empirical findings from asymmetric conflicts clearly demonstrate the need for a new theoretical paradigm that can adequately encompass the complexity and multidimensionality of friction manifested in these conflicts. Such a paradigm must transcend the limitations of tradition-

al understanding of friction focused primarily on material and tactical factors, and incorporate more sophisticated understanding of organizational, cognitive, cultural, political, and strategic dimensions of friction. Through integration of these different perspectives and empirical findings, it is possible to develop a coherent analytical framework that can inform more effective theory and practice in the context of asymmetric conflicts that will likely continue to dominate the security environment in the decades to come.

5. CONCLUSION

Clausewitz's theory of friction remains one of the most significant contributions to understanding the nature of war and military operations, but as we have seen through our analysis, the contemporary context of warfare requires its significant redefinition and expansion. From the historical context and fundamental principles that Clausewitz established, through the complex operational space of hybrid warfare, methodological challenges of analysis in the information and cyber domain, to empirical findings from asymmetric operations—each dimension of our research has contributed to a holistic understanding of the evolution of the concept of friction in modern warfare. The key conclusion that runs through all aspects of our research is that friction has evolved from primarily a material and tactical phenomenon to a multidimensional concept encompassing organizational, cognitive, informational, legal, political, and strategic components. Contemporary conflicts characterized by multidimensionality, nonlinearity, and asymmetry create new forms of friction that require new analytical approaches and adaptations of traditional military organizations and doctrines.

Hybrid warfare has presented a challenge to conventional understanding of friction through blurring boundaries between different domains of conflict and deliberate instrumentalization of friction as a strategic weapon. Information saturation, cyber specificities, ambiguity, asymmetry, and manipulation of perceptions create new sources and manifestations of friction that Clausewitz could not have anticipated in his time. Methodological challenges of friction analysis in information and cyber

domains require a multidisciplinary approach that integrates technical, social, and cognitive perspectives. Epistemological uncertainty, the attribution problem, the relative nature of friction, and complex inter-domain interactions create the need for developing new metrics, analytical frameworks, and research approaches that can adequately encompass these phenomena.

Asymmetric conflicts have particularly illuminated the paradoxical nature of contemporary friction, where technological and material superiority can paradoxically create new forms of strategic, operational, and organizational friction. Operational rigidity, cultural dissonance, political constraints, and asymmetry of interests represent factors that can significantly reduce the effectiveness of materially superior parties in asymmetric conflict.

The new paradigm of understanding friction that we propose through this research emphasizes the need for a holistic approach that views friction not only as an obstacle to be minimized, but also as a strategic factor that can be actively managed. Such a paradigm recognizes the relative nature of friction, its multidimensionality, and cascading effects that manifest through different levels of conflict. For military organizations, the implications are significant—success in contemporary conflicts increasingly depends on the ability to effectively adapt to inevitable friction, develop organizational resilience, and cultivate operational flexibility. Organizations that remain trapped in traditional understanding of friction risk developing doctrine, structure, and capabilities that are inadequate for the realities of contemporary conflicts. Redefining Clausewitz's concept of friction through the prism of contemporary conflicts represents not only an academic but also a practical imperative for military organizations that want to remain relevant in the complex, multidimensional, and nonlinear security environment of the 21st century.

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CUSTOMS POLICY OF THE “BIG”

THE IMPACT OF TRUMP'S TARIFFS ON THE AMERICAN ECONOMY: ANALYSIS OF THE CONSEQUENCES OF PROTECTIONIST POLICY ON ECONOMIC GROWTH, EMPLOYMENT AND SECTORAL STRUCTURE OF THE USA

Dr Đuro Krčić¹

Abstract: The trade policy of President Donald Trump (2017-2021, 2025-present), characterized by extensive tariff imposition on imports, represents the most significant change in U.S. trade practices since the *Smoot-Hawley Tariff Act* of the 1930s (Wikipedia Contributors, 2025). This paper analyzes the comprehensive impact of Trump's tariffs on the American economy through three key dimensions: macroeconomic effects on GDP and inflation, microeconomic consequences on sectoral productivity and employment, and long-term structural changes in trade relations. The research is based on empirical data from the period 2018-2025 and shows that tariffs, despite the goal of increasing domestic production and employment, resulted in net negative economic effects. The average tariff rate rose from 2.5% at the beginning of 2025 to 27% by April of the same year, representing the highest level in the last hundred years (Wikipedia Contributors, 2025). The analysis indicates that tariff costs were entirely passed on to American importers and consumers, leading to price increases and reduced economic efficiency (Tax Foundation, 2025). GDP contracted by 0.3% on an annual basis in the first quarter of 2025, while retaliatory tariffs by trading partners further damaged export sectors, especially agriculture (Kolb, 2025). The research concludes that protectionist trade policy, without complementary structural reforms, does not contribute to sustainable economic growth or increased competitiveness of the American economy.

Keywords: tariffs, trade policy, protectionism, economic growth, employment, trade war, Donald Trump, American economy

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1. INTRODUCTION

American trade policy in the first decade of the 21st century was characterized by gradual liberalization and integration into global value chains. However, with Donald Trump's arrival to the presidency in 2017, the U.S. established a drastically different approach to international trade, based on protectionist principles and bilateral balance of trade relations. From January 2018, Trump imposed tariffs on solar panels and washing machines of 30-50%, and in March 2018 expanded tariffs on steel (25%) and aluminum (10%) from most countries (Congressional Budget Office, 2021). Trump's trade policy represents the most significant change in American trade approach since the *Smoot-Hawley Tariff Act* of the 1930s. This policy was based on the premise that tariffs would protect domestic industry, increase employment and reduce the trade deficit, especially with China. However, the economic effects of this policy proved more complex than initially projected goals.

The current, second Trump administration (2025-present) has continued and intensified the protectionist policy. Between January and April 2025, the average effective tariff rate in the U.S. rose from 2.5% to an estimated 27%—the highest level in more than a century (Wikipedia Contributors, 2025). This approach has led to an escalation of trade wars with key partners, including China, Canada, Mexico and the European Union. The aim of this paper is to provide a comprehensive overview of the economic effects of Trump's tariffs on the American economy, analyzing their impact on economic growth, sectoral productivity, employment and the long-term structure of the American economy. The analysis covers data from both Trump administrations (2017-2021 and 2025-present) to enable better understanding of the consistency and evolution of this trade policy.

2. MACROECONOMIC EFFECTS OF TARIFFS ON ECONOMIC GROWTH AND INFLATION

The macroeconomic effects of Trump's tariffs on American GDP have proven extremely negative. Data from the *Commerce Department* shows that U.S. gross domestic product contracted at an annual rate

of 0.3% in the first quarter of 2025, after growing at a solid rate of 2.4% in the final months of 2024 (Kolb, 2025). Such contraction represents the first economic decline in the last three years and is directly linked to the introduction of new tariffs. Economic models predict even more serious long-term consequences. The *Penn Wharton Budget Model* projects that Trump's tariffs (based on data from April 8, 2025) will reduce GDP by about 8% and wages by 7% (Penn Wharton Budget Model, 2025). Such a GDP decline is approximately twice as large as what would result from increasing the corporate tax from 21% to 36%, which is traditionally considered an extremely distortionary form of taxation. The *Tax Foundation* estimates that Trump's proposed universal tariffs of 20% and additional tariffs on China up to 60% will reduce long-term economic output by 1.3% before any foreign retaliation (Tax Foundation, 2025). This estimate is conservative as it does not include retaliatory measures by trading partners, which could further worsen economic effects.

Tariffs act as a consumption tax that directly affects the prices of goods. Tariffs represent an average tax increase of nearly \$1,200 per American household in 2025 (Tax Foundation, 2025). This effect is particularly pronounced in sectors that depend on imported raw materials or finished products. In research conducted in December 2024 and early January 2025, consumers on average expected that tariffs would lead to a 10% increase in import prices and a 14% increase in domestic product prices in the following year (Coibion et al., 2025). These expectations are already reflected in market prices before tariff implementation, which complicates the Federal Reserve's job in controlling inflation. Particularly affected sectors include the automotive industry, where producing one car requires about half a ton of steel, so a 25% tariff can add over \$1,000 in production costs per vehicle. Similarly, aluminum comprises about 80% of aircraft construction weight, which means tariffs can make American planes more expensive in the global market.

The introduction of tariffs has significantly affected financial markets and monetary policy. The tariff announcement caused the largest two-day drop in the history of the American stock market, where \$6.6 trillion in total value was wiped out on Thursday and Friday alone before markets closed for the weekend. The consumer confidence index,

compiled by the nonprofit organization *Conference Board*, has fallen for five consecutive months, and tariffs have now surpassed inflation as the main concern. Such decline in confidence has important implications for future consumption and investment. Federal Reserve Chairman *Jerome Powell* described the tariffs and their likely economic impact as «significantly larger than expected,» which indicates central bankers' concern about potential inflationary pressures that tariffs can create (White House, 2025).

3. SECTORAL ANALYSIS: STEEL AND ALUMINUM

The steel and aluminum sector represents the most direct targeting of Trump's trade policy through *Section 232* tariffs. Metal import tariffs contributed to job creation in the metal production industry. The number of people working in steel mills as well as those in aluminum production increased from 2017 to 2019 by 6% and 5% respectively (United States International Trade Commission, 2023). However, these initial gains were not sustainable. After tariffs against Canada and Mexico were removed, the remaining restrictions were not sufficient to support employment in metal processing faced with falling domestic demand due to disruptions caused by the pandemic in 2020 and 2021. Under President Trump, steel and aluminum imports drastically decreased, falling by almost a third from 2016 to 2020. The tariffs led to a wave of investments across the U.S., with more than \$10 billion allocated for building new facilities (White House, 2025). While metallurgical industries had temporary benefits, *downstream* sectors that use steel and aluminum as inputs experienced significant negative effects. In May 2023, a *United States International Trade Commission* report estimated that the \$2.8 billion production increase in industries protected by steel and aluminum tariffs was met with a \$3.4 billion production decrease in *downstream* industries affected by higher input prices (United States International Trade Commission, 2023).

Research estimates that Trump's 2018 steel tariffs cost taxpayers more than \$900,000 annually for each job they saved or created (United States International Trade Commission, 2023). This cost-benefit ra-

tio indicates the inefficiency of tariffs as a tool for job creation. Annual GDP growth figures for construction, manufacturing and transportation industries slowed during the second half of 2018 and 2019 after tariff implementation at the beginning of 2018. Such impact is not surprising, as higher input costs can result in both higher prices for consumers and reduced production.

The automotive industry, as one of the largest consumers of steel and aluminum, has been particularly affected by tariff policies. *Ford CEO Jim Farley* warned investors: «Long term, a 25% tariff across the Mexican and Canadian border will put a hole in the American industry like we've never seen.» The three largest American automobile manufacturers—*Ford*, *General Motors* and *Stellantis*—lobbied for exemptions, warning that tariffs will harm American companies more than foreign competitors. The warning reflects the complexity of the integrated North American automotive supply chain, where parts and components move across borders multiple times during the production process (Knežević, 2024).

4. TRADE WAR WITH CHINA AND GLOBAL CONSEQUENCES

The trade war with China represents the most significant component of Trump's trade policy. According to *JP Morgan Chase*, the effective rate of U.S. tariffs on Chinese products was between 0-5% in 2018 and rose to about 20% by 2021, when President *Joe Biden* took office (Wikipedia Contributors, 2025). The Biden administration did not withdraw Trump's tariffs on Chinese imports, but rather this rate remained stable during Biden's term. In his second administration, Trump has further escalated the trade war. Trump has escalated the ongoing trade war with China, raising basic tariffs on Chinese imports to 145%. In retaliation, China imposed a minimum 125% tariff on American products and restricted exports of rare metals critical for high-tech industries (Wikipedia Contributors, 2025). Analysis of the trade war's effects indicates significant economic costs for both sides. An analysis published by *Chad Bown* from the *Peterson Institute for International Eco-*

nomics showed that American exports to China would have been \$119 billion higher than actually recorded during the Trump administration from 2018 to 2021, had there been no trade war and had the U.S. share of the Chinese market remained consistent (Bown, 2019).

The trade war had additional costs of \$30 billion in taxpayer funds that Trump used to subsidize American farmers to compensate for their lost sales to China from 2018 to 2020 (Hass & Denmark, 2022). A study by *Oxford Economics* and the *U.S.-China Business Council* from 2021 concluded that the U.S. lost 245,000 jobs as a result of Trump's tariffs (Pettis, 2021). This figure indicates a net negative impact on employment, despite the goal of increasing jobs in protected industries. The trade war has led to lasting changes in global trade flows. China instead strengthened trade with other partners including the European Union, Mexico and Vietnam. The country's share in global trade rose approximately 4% since 2016, when President Trump first took office, while the U.S. share fell (Kolb, 2025). After the first trade war, American farmers lost significant market share in soybean sales to Brazil, which they still have not recovered. This example illustrates how short-term trade measures can have long-term negative consequences on the competitiveness of American exporters.

5. IMPACT ON AGRICULTURE AND RETALIATORY MEASURES

American agriculture, traditionally export-oriented, became the main victim of retaliatory tariffs imposed in response to Trump's trade measures. A U.S. Department of Agriculture study showed that retaliatory tariffs reduced American agricultural exports by \$27 billion from mid-2018 when tariffs were introduced to the end of 2019 (U.S. Department of Agriculture, 2020). Soybeans accounted for the majority of the decline, 71%, followed by sorghum and pork with 7% and 5% respectively (Tax Foundation, 2024). This blow to soybeans was particularly devastating given that China was the largest buyer of American soybeans before the trade war. China, Mexico and Canada—in that order—were the three largest foreign buyers of American agricultural products in 2023, with

total values of \$33.7 billion, \$28.2 billion and \$27.9 billion. Retaliatory tariffs by these key partners directly hit the heart of American agricultural production.

To mitigate the economic blow to agriculture, Trump launched massive financial aid programs for farmers. In 2018 and 2019, Trump approved payments to American farmers of \$28 billion to compensate for their losses due to Chinese trade retaliation (Setser, 2025). American farmers have indeed absorbed almost all of Trump's revenue from tariffs on China, which now amounts to \$66 billion. In 2018 and 2019, Trump approved payments to American farmers of \$28 billion to compensate for their losses due to Chinese trade retaliation. This year, with farmers struggling under the dual crisis of the trade war and pandemic, bailout programs have climbed much higher. Trump promised angry farmers another \$19 billion in April and \$14 billion in September—bringing his bailout programs to a grand total of \$61 billion (Setser, 2025). Payments to farmers affected by Chinese retaliation consumed over 92% of trade war tax revenue (Setser, 2025). This statistic dramatically illustrates how tariffs became a means of financing agricultural subsidies rather than a means of increasing government revenue.

The trade war has led to lasting changes in global agricultural markets. In 2017 China imported goods worth \$19.1 billion, but due to tariffs China imposed on agricultural products the number of imported goods fell to \$9.1 billion. China bought 14.3 million tons of American soybeans, the smallest number in 11 years. Before the U.S.-China trade war, China imported 32.9 million tons of American soybeans. This drastic drop illustrates how much the trade war affected traditional trade patterns. The fact is that now when we look back at it six, seven years later, the long-term impact of that is that Brazil now has a commanding position in the Chinese market. This example shows how a short-term trade dispute can lead to lasting changes in global trade relations, to the benefit of American competitors.

6. IMPACT ON EMPLOYMENT, LABOR REDISTRIBUTION AND FISCAL COSTS OF TARIFF POLICY

A comprehensive approach to analyzing Trump's tariffs requires a deeper understanding of their impact on the labor market, regional economy and public finances. While the initial debate focused on macroeconomic indicators, the real impact of protectionist policy is revealed through complex interactions between sectoral employment, fiscal costs and long-term structural changes in the American economy. The net effect of Trump's tariffs on American employment represents one of the most controversial aspects of this trade policy (Knežević & Martinović, 2024). A study by *Oxford Economics* and the *U.S.-China Business Council* from 2021 concluded that the U.S. lost 245,000 jobs as a direct result of Trump's tariffs (Pettis, 2021). This finding is particularly significant because it contradicts the basic premise of protectionist policy—that protected industries will create more jobs than affected sectors will lose. Analysis by *Federal Reserve* economists *Aaron Flaaen* and *Justin Pierce* from December 2019 also found a net decrease in manufacturing employment due to tariffs, suggesting that benefits from increased production in protected industries were outweighed by the consequences of rising input costs and retaliatory tariffs (Flaaen & Pierce, 2019).

However, the figure of 245,000 lost jobs represents only the tip of the iceberg of a more complex story about labor redistribution between sectors. Steel and aluminum tariffs led to increased employment in metallurgical industries—the number of people working in steel mills and aluminum production increased from 2017 to 2019 by 6% and 5% respectively (United States International Trade Commission, 2023). However, these gains were short-lived and concentrated in relatively small sectors of the American economy. *Downstream* industries that use steel and aluminum as inputs, including the automotive industry, construction and machinery manufacturing, employ significantly more workers—over 12 million Americans work in sectors that use steel, of which nearly two million work in steel-intensive industries where steel inputs comprise at least 5% of total input needs. Regional differences in employment impact reveal additional complexity of tariffs' economic effects (Knežević,

2025). A study by University of *Warwick* economists showed that tariffs negatively affected voters in counties that turned to Trump (relative to *Mitt Romney's* results from 2012), and that as a result of retaliatory tariffs, Republican candidates did worse by between 1.4 and 2.7 percentage points in counties in the top decile of exposure distribution to implied Chinese, Canadian and Mexican retaliation (Congressional Budget Office, 2021). This regional analysis suggests that the economic costs of tariffs were felt precisely in those areas that politically supported protectionist policy.

Qualitative analysis of the impact on wages and worker productivity reveals additional dimensions of the problem. The *Tax Foundation* estimates that *Trump-Biden Section 301* and *Section 232* tariffs will reduce long-term GDP by 0.2%, capital stock by 0.1%, and labor hours by the equivalent of 142,000 full-time jobs. The reason tariffs have no impact on pre-tax wages in these estimates is that, in the long run, capital stock decreases proportionally to the decrease in labor hours, so the capital-to-labor ratio, and thus the wage level, remains unchanged (Tax Foundation, 2025). This finding suggests that tariffs do not contribute to improving American workers' living standards, but only redistribute economic activity between sectors with a net negative effect on overall productivity. The fiscal aspect of Trump's trade policy perhaps represents the most dramatic illustration of its unintended consequences. Instead of being a source of government revenue, tariffs have become a mechanism for massive financing of agricultural subsidies. American farmers have indeed absorbed almost all of Trump's revenue from tariffs on China, which now amounts to \$66 billion. In 2018 and 2019, Trump approved payments to American farmers of \$28 billion to compensate for their losses due to Chinese trade retaliation, while the total bailout program reached \$61 billion by the end of the first term (Setser, 2025). Payments to farmers affected by Chinese retaliation consumed over 92% of trade war tax revenue, which dramatically illustrates how tariffs became a means of financing agricultural subsidies rather than a means of increasing government revenue.

The economic efficiency of these bailout programs is questionable when analyzed through the lens of cost per saved job. Research by the Pe-

terson Institute for International Economics estimates that Trump's steel tariffs from 2018 cost taxpayers more than \$900,000 annually for each job they saved or created (United States International Trade Commission, 2023). This cost-benefit ratio far exceeds any reasonable assessment of a job's value, even when considering multiplier effects and positive external effects of the industry. For comparison, the average annual wage of an American manufacturing worker is about \$45,000, which means that government costs for creating one job through tariffs exceed 20 years of average wages. The long-term impact on the federal budget and public debt further complicates the fiscal picture of trade policy. The Penn Wharton Budget Model projects that Trump's tariffs (based on data from April 8, 2025) will increase federal tax revenue by over \$5.2 trillion over 10 years on a conventional basis and \$4.5 trillion on a dynamic basis (Penn Wharton Budget Model, 2025). However, these projections are theoretical because they do not account for the need for continuous bail-out programs and economic costs of reduced economic activity. Over the next 30 years, tariffs are expected to raise revenue of \$16.4 trillion, but these figures fall to \$4.5 trillion and \$11.8 trillion on a dynamic basis.

Analysis of distributional effects reveals that trade policy is not neutral toward different segments of society. Tariffs act as a regressive tax that disproportionately affects lower-income households, as they spend a larger portion of their income on products subject to tariffs. The *Penn Wharton Budget Model* estimates that a middle-income household will face a lifetime loss of \$58,000 as a result of tariffs. These losses are twice as large as those that would result from increasing the corporate tax from 21% to 36%, which is otherwise considered a very distortionary form of taxation. Inter-sectoral labor redistribution created by tariffs also has important implications for the long-term structure of the American economy. While protected sectors experience short-term employment growth, the loss of competitiveness in *downstream* industries can lead to long-term structural weakening of American manufacturing. The automotive industry, as one of the largest users of steel and aluminum, is particularly affected. *Ford CEO Jim Farley* warned investors that «long term, a 25% tariff across the Mexican and Canadian border will put a hole in the American industry like we've never seen» (Wikipedia Contributors,

2025). These warnings indicate that short-term gains in metallurgical industries can be outweighed by long-term losses in more sophisticated manufacturing sectors. The consequences of trade policy for innovation and technological development represent an additional dimension of the problem. Excess input costs due to tariffs can reduce resources available to companies for research and development, while retaliatory tariffs can limit access to international markets needed to amortize high innovation costs. In sectors such as technology, where American companies depend on global markets, trade wars can weaken the innovative capacity of the American economy in the long term.

7. CONCLUSION

The fiscal costs of trade policy must be considered in the context of alternative policies that could achieve similar goals with smaller economic losses. Instead of tariffs, the government could invest the \$61 billion spent on bailout programs in infrastructure, education or research and development, which would likely have more positive long-term effects on American competitiveness. Alternatively, direct subsidies for technological development in key industries could achieve national security goals without imposing costs on the entire economy through higher input prices. Analysis of the economic effects of Trump's tariffs on the American economy reveals a complex picture with predominantly negative consequences. Despite goals of increasing domestic production, reducing the trade deficit and creating jobs, protectionist trade policy has resulted in net economic losses for the American economy.

The main findings of this research can be summarized through several key points: Tariffs acted as a regressive tax on American consumers, increasing living costs for the average household by approximately \$1,200 annually. GDP contraction in the first quarter of 2025 (-0.3%) is directly linked to trade policies, while long-term projections indicate even more significant losses in economic output. While metallurgical industries achieved short-term benefits in terms of increased production and employment, these gains were outweighed by losses in downstream industries that use steel and aluminum as inputs. The cost-benefit ratio

shows that tariffs cost more than \$900,000 annually per created job. Escalation of trade tensions, especially with China, led to retaliatory tariffs that hit American exporters, particularly the agricultural sector. Government bailout programs for farmers consumed more than 92% of tariff revenue, making this policy a net fiscal cost rather than a source of revenue. Tariffs have led to lasting changes in global trade flows, where American exporters lost market share to competitors, especially Brazilian agricultural producers in the Chinese market. These losses will likely persist even after eventual tariff removal. The theoretical approach that justified Trump’s tariffs—the idea that they would force foreign partners to “pay” for trade imbalances—proved empirically incorrect. Tariff costs were entirely passed on to American importers and consumers, while the macroeconomic benefits postulated by the administration have failed to materialize. These findings indicate the need to refocus American trade policy toward multilateral approaches that can better address structural trade problems without imposing significant costs on the domestic economy. Future research should focus on alternatives to protectionist policies that can achieve similar goals of preserving domestic industry and employment with smaller economic costs.

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SPORTS DIPLOMACY AND SECURITY

SPORTS DIPLOMACY AND SECURITY CHALLENGES DURING THE COLD WAR

Tijana Martinović¹

Abstract: This paper explores the complex interconnection between sports diplomacy and security challenges during the Cold War period (1947-1991). During this period of ideological divisions between East and West, sports competitions often served as a substitute for direct confrontation between superpowers. The paper analyzes how sporting events, such as the Olympic Games and other international competitions, were instrumentalized by states to achieve diplomatic goals and project soft power. Special attention is given to significant incidents such as the boycotts of the Olympic Games in Moscow 1980 and Los Angeles 1984, as well as the so-called «ping-pong diplomacy» which paved the way for the normalization of relations between the USA and China. Through analysis of historical documents, diplomatic archives, and secondary sources, the paper demonstrates how sport functioned as an arena for security competition, but paradoxically also as a bridge for dialogue in a period of intense geopolitical tensions. The conclusions indicate that sports diplomacy, despite its instrumentalization, often managed to open diplomatic channels that would otherwise have remained closed, contributing to a certain degree of stability in the Cold War security environment.

Keywords: sports diplomacy, Cold War, security, Olympic Games, ping-pong diplomacy, soft power, ideological competition, international relations, geopolitics

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1. INTRODUCTION

The Cold War period (1947-1991) represents one of the most complex epochs of contemporary history, characterized by ideological, political, and military confrontation between the United States of America and the Soviet Union, as well as their respective allies. Under conditions of nuclear deterrence and the impossibility of direct military conflict, superpowers sought alternative arenas to demonstrate their superiority and achieve foreign policy goals. Sport, as a global phenomenon with enormous popularity and symbolic significance, became one of the most important fields for projecting national prestige and ideological supremacy (Keys, 2003). Sports diplomacy, as a specific form of public diplomacy, involves the use of sport and sporting events to achieve foreign policy goals of states and improve international relations. During the Cold War, this phenomenon experienced its boom, and international sports competitions were transformed into arenas for symbolic measurement of strength between the capitalist and communist blocs (Redihan, 2017). Simultaneously, sport paradoxically served as one of the rare bridges of communication between ideologically opposed sides, enabling forms of cooperation and dialogue that were difficult to achieve in other spheres.

This paper aims to examine the complex dynamics of the relationship between sports diplomacy and security challenges during the Cold War. Through analysis of key sporting events, diplomatic initiatives related to sport, and their security implications, we will try to answer several key questions: How were sports competitions used as instruments of foreign policy strategies of superpowers? To what extent did sport contribute to the escalation or de-escalation of tensions in the Cold War security environment? What were the long-term consequences of the politicization of sport on international relations and the security architecture of the Cold War?

The paper is structured in several logically connected sections. After the introductory part, a conceptual framework follows that defines key concepts and theoretical approaches relevant to the analysis. The third part of the paper is dedicated to the analysis of the Olympic Games as an arena of Cold War competition, with special reference to the boycotts of

the Games in Moscow and Los Angeles. The fourth part explores the phenomenon of “ping-pong diplomacy” and its implications for Sino-American relations. The fifth part analyzes the role of football and other popular sports in the context of Cold War security challenges. The sixth part considers the consequences of Cold War sports diplomacy on contemporary international relations, while the final part summarizes the key findings and conclusions of the research.

2. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK: SPORT, DIPLOMACY, AND SECURITY

2.1. Sports diplomacy as an instrument of foreign policy

Sports diplomacy represents a relatively new concept in the theory of international relations, which involves the use of sport as an instrument for achieving foreign policy goals of states (Murray, 2012). It can manifest through various forms: from organizing international sporting events to raise the international prestige of a country, through using sports exchanges to improve bilateral relations, to instrumentalizing sports successes for projecting national power and influence. Unlike traditional diplomacy, which takes place behind closed doors between professional diplomats, sports diplomacy involves a wider spectrum of actors – athletes, coaches, fans, sports organizations – and takes place before the eyes of the global public. It is precisely this public dimension that makes it a particularly attractive instrument of “soft power,” a concept developed by Joseph Nye (2004) which refers to the ability of a state to achieve its goals through attraction and persuasion, rather than coercion or payment.

During the Cold War, sports diplomacy experienced its full affirmation as an instrument of foreign policy. Both superpowers recognized the potential of sport for projecting their ideological and systemic superiority. For the Soviet Union, international sports competitions represented an opportunity to demonstrate the successes of the socialist system and its ability to create a “new man” – physically and morally superior (Riordan, 1974). For the United States, sports successes served as proof of the su-

periority of the American way of life, individualism, and the free market.

2.2. Sport and the security complex of the Cold War

The security complex of the Cold War, characterized by a bipolar structure of the international system, nuclear deterrence, and ideological antagonism, created a specific context in which sport gained a pronounced political and security dimension. Buzan and Wæver (2003) define a security complex as “a group of states whose primary security interests are so closely linked that their national securities cannot realistically be considered separately from one another.” In the context of the Cold War, every aspect of relations between East and West, including sports competitions, was viewed through the prism of security implications. Sport had a dual role in the security complex of the Cold War. On one hand, it served as an arena for demonstrating power and prestige, contributing to the intensification of rivalry and distrust. On the other hand, it enabled forms of cooperation and communication that could act as mechanisms for reducing tensions and building trust. This ambivalent nature of sports diplomacy makes it a particularly interesting subject of analysis in the context of security studies.

2.3. Theoretical approaches to the analysis of sports diplomacy

Several theoretical approaches are relevant for the analysis of sports diplomacy in the context of the Cold War. The realist perspective, which emphasizes the struggle for power as a key determinant of international relations, allows understanding the instrumentalization of sport for projecting national power and realizing geopolitical interests. The liberalist approach, with a focus on the importance of international institutions and cooperation, provides a framework for analyzing sport as a potential mechanism for improving international understanding and cooperation. The constructivist perspective, which emphasizes the role of identity, norms, and perceptions in international relations, enables understanding of the symbolic dimension of sports competitions and their role in constructing national narratives and identities (Levermore & Budd, 2004). By combining these theoretical approaches, we can get a more compre-

hensive picture of the complex role of sports diplomacy in the security dynamics of the Cold War. In the following chapters, through analysis of specific cases and events, we will try to illustrate this complex dynamics and identify key patterns of interaction between sport, diplomacy, and security in the Cold War context.

3. THE OLYMPIC GAMES AS AN ARENA OF COLD WAR COMPETITION

3.1. Politicization of the Olympic movement

The Olympic Games, conceived as an apolitical competition dedicated to international understanding and peace, became during the Cold War one of the primary arenas for geopolitical and ideological competition between East and West. The entry of the Soviet Union into the Olympic movement in 1952 marked the beginning of a new era in which sports results became a measure of systemic superiority (Rider, 2016).

For the Soviet Union, successes at the Olympic Games represented confirmation of the superiority of the socialist system and its values. This led to the development of a sophisticated system of state-sponsored sport, with massive investments in talents, training, and sports science. The United States, although nominally committed to amateur sport, also had to intensify its efforts to match Soviet successes, which led to increased involvement of the federal government in sport (Rider, 2016).

Medals won at the Olympic Games were not just sporting achievements, but ideological victories, carefully quantified and analyzed in the media on both sides. The informal “medal table,” which is not part of the official Olympic tradition, became a key indicator of national prestige and systemic efficiency. Such politicization of Olympic sport led to a series of controversies and tensions that often undermined the Olympic ideals of peace and understanding.

3.2. Boycott of the Olympic Games in Moscow 1980

The Soviet invasion of Afghanistan in December 1979 provoked a sharp reaction from the West and led to a significant escalation of Cold War tensions. In response to this military intervention, US President Jimmy Carter announced a boycott of the Summer Olympic Games in Moscow in 1980, calling on US allies to do the same. This decision represented the first case in Olympic history where a superpower boycotted the games for explicitly political reasons (Sarantakes, 2011).

The American administration presented the boycott as a necessary measure for punishing Soviet aggression and demonstrating Western unity in opposing the expansionist policy of the USSR. For President Carter, the boycott was part of a broader strategy of pressure on the Soviet Union, which included a grain embargo, suspension of technology transfers, and boycott of the Olympic Games (Sarantakes, 2011).

A total of 65 countries joined the American boycott, including key Western allies such as West Germany, Japan, Canada, and Israel. However, some significant Western allies, such as Great Britain, France, Italy, and Australia, decided to send their athletes, although some of these countries participated in protest gestures such as competing under the Olympic flag instead of the national flag.

The boycott had significant consequences on multiple levels. The number of participating countries was reduced from 121 to 80, which significantly diminished the sporting quality of competition in many disciplines. The economic impact on the Soviet Union was significant, given the enormous investments in infrastructure and organization. On the political level, the boycott further polarized the international community and deepened distrust between East and West (Sarantakes, 2011).

3.3. The Soviet response: Boycott of the Olympic Games in Los Angeles 1984

Four years later, the Soviet Union and its allies retaliated in kind, boycotting the Summer Olympic Games in Los Angeles in 1984. The official justification for the boycott was “alleged security threats to So-

viet athletes” and “anti-Soviet hysteria” in the US. However, it is widely accepted that the real motive was a reciprocal measure for the American boycott of the Moscow games (Hulme, 1990).

The Soviet boycott was joined by 14 Eastern bloc countries, including East Germany, which was a significant sports power and winner of numerous medals. The only exceptions among communist countries were Romania, which decided to send its delegation, and China, which returned to the Olympic movement after a long absence.

Despite the Soviet boycott, the Games in Los Angeles were very successful in organizational and commercial terms, setting new standards for the economic sustainability of the Olympic Games. For the US and the West, the successful organization represented a diplomatic victory and a demonstration of the vitality of the Western economic model (Hulme, 1990).

3.4. Security implications of Olympic boycotts

Olympic boycotts represented a dramatic manifestation of Cold War tensions, and their impact on international security was multifaceted. On one hand, boycotts contributed to further polarization of the international community and deepening of distrust between opposing blocs. The instrumentalization of sport for projecting political messages undermined the idea of sport as a neutral space for international understanding.

On the other hand, boycotts functioned as symbolic valves for releasing political tensions and allowed states to demonstrate their position without resorting to more serious confrontations. In this sense, sports boycotts can be viewed as an example of what Schelling (1966) calls “coercive diplomacy” – the use of limited, often symbolic measures to send political messages without escalation into open conflict.

During and after the boycotts, the international sports community, led by the International Olympic Committee, intensified efforts to depoliticize the Olympic Games and strengthen their autonomy from geopolitical tensions. These efforts, although only partially successful, contributed to the gradual reduction of direct instrumentalization of the Olympic

Games for political purposes in later phases of the Cold War (Cottrell & Nelson, 2010).

4. PING PONG DIPLOMACY AND OPENING TOWARDS CHINA

After the communist revolution in China in 1949 and the establishment of the People's Republic of China, relations between China and the US were extremely hostile. The US refused to recognize the new government in Beijing, instead supporting the nationalist government in Taiwan as the legitimate representative of China. The Sino-Soviet split during the 1960s created a more complex geopolitical situation, which opened the possibility for a change in American policy towards China (Xu, 2008). In the context of the ongoing war in Vietnam and increasingly pronounced tensions with the Soviet Union, the American administration under President Richard Nixon began to consider the possibility of normalizing relations with China as part of a broader strategy of "triangular diplomacy." At the same time, the Chinese leadership, faced with the threat from the Soviet Union on the northern border, was also interested in improving relations with the US (Xu, 2008).

In April 1971, American table tennis players participating in the World Table Tennis Championship in Japan received an unexpected invitation to visit the People's Republic of China. This visit, which became known as "ping-pong diplomacy," marked the first official contact between American and Chinese citizens after more than two decades of complete severance of relations (Itoh, 2011). The background of this invitation was a carefully planned diplomatic initiative. President Mao Zedong personally approved the invitation, recognizing the potential of sport as a neutral and low-risk channel for initial contact. On the American side, the Nixon administration quickly recognized the significance of this gesture and responded positively, allowing the visit despite a long-standing policy of isolating China (Itoh, 2011). The American delegation of table tennis players stayed in China for seven days, playing friendly matches and participating in cultural exchanges. Media coverage of this visit was intense, especially in the US, where it represented the first direct insight into life in communist China after many years.

“Ping-pong diplomacy” had far-reaching consequences for the geopolitical and security dynamics of the Cold War. In July 1971, just three months after the visit of the table tennis players, US Secretary of State Henry Kissinger secretly visited Beijing to prepare the ground for President Nixon’s historic visit to China in February 1972. This visit resulted in the signing of the Shanghai Communiqué, which laid the foundations for the normalization of relations between the two countries (Xu, 2008).

The strategic significance of this diplomatic breakthrough was enormous. For the US, rapprochement with China represented a key element of the “triangular diplomacy” strategy, which aimed to exploit Sino-Soviet tensions to strengthen the American geopolitical position. For China, improving relations with the US reduced the threat of a potential two-front conflict and opened the way to international reintegration after years of isolation. The Soviet Union followed this rapprochement with concern, perceiving it as a potential threat to its security. The formation of an implicit Sino-American axis against the USSR significantly changed the strategic balance of power and contributed to a new phase of détente between the US and the Soviet Union during the 1970s (Kissinger, 1994).

“Ping-pong diplomacy” which followed the evolution of international law (Knežević, S. & Martinović, T., 2024) became a classic example of using sport as an instrument for opening diplomatic channels in situations where traditional diplomatic paths are blocked. The success of this approach demonstrated how seemingly trivial sports contacts can have a transformative impact on international relations when there are coinciding strategic interests of key actors.

5. FOOTBALL AND OTHER POPULAR SPORTS IN THE COLD WAR CONTEXT

5.1. Football as an arena of ideological competition

Football, as the most popular global sport, could not escape politicization during the Cold War. Clubs and national teams were often perceived as representatives not only of their countries but also of their political systems. Matches between teams from countries with different

ideological orientations often gained a dimension that transcended sport (Tomlinson & Young, 2006). In Eastern Europe, football clubs were often directly linked to state institutions – CSKA Moscow with the army, Dynamo with the police. In such a context, the success of these clubs on the international scene was interpreted as proof of the strength of these institutions and, indirectly, of the socialist system. In the West, the model of sports clubs was different, but the successes of Western teams were also used for propaganda purposes as proof of the superiority of the capitalist model (Tomlinson & Young, 2006).

The symbolic charge of matches between teams from East and West Germany was particularly significant. After the division of Germany in 1949, sports encounters between the two German states became rare opportunities for direct comparison of the two systems in the conditions of the German cultural context. West Germany's victory over the favored Hungary in the final of the World Cup in 1954, known as the "Miracle of Bern," had enormous psychological significance for West Germany and was perceived as a symbol of the post-war recovery and regeneration of West German society (Hesselmann & Ide, 2009).

1.2. Basketball and Cold War rivalry

Basketball matches between the US and the USSR during the Cold War were among the most tense sporting events of that period, often reflecting broader geopolitical tensions. The controversial final of the Olympic Games in 1972 in Munich, when the Soviet Union defeated the US for the first time in Olympic history after a disputed repetition of the final seconds of the match, caused huge controversies and was perceived in the US as an injustice with a political background (Wolff, 2002). This victory had enormous symbolic significance for the Soviet Union, as it represented a victory over the US in a sport considered "American" and demonstrated the ability of the Soviet system to develop top athletes even in sports without a long tradition in the USSR. For the US, this defeat was shocking and was experienced as part of a broader narrative about the "loss" of American superiority in the context of the Vietnam War and other challenges to American power during the 1970s (Wolff, 2002).

1.3. Chess as a metaphor for Cold War competition

Chess, as an intellectual game with a long tradition in Russia, had a special place in the sports diplomacy of the Cold War. The dominance of Soviet chess players on the international scene was presented as proof of the intellectual superiority of the Soviet educational system and socialist values. In this context, the matches for the title of world champion between Boris Spassky (USSR) and Bobby Fischer (USA) in 1972 in Reykjavik gained enormous symbolic significance, becoming known as the “match of the century” (Johnson, 2007).

Fischer, the eccentric American chess genius, defeated Spassky and broke the long-standing Soviet dominance, which was celebrated in the US as a significant Cold War victory. This match attracted unprecedented media attention worldwide and transformed the perception of chess in the US, linking it with concepts of intellectual superiority in the context of technological competition with the Soviet Union (Johnson, 2007).

Intense sports rivalries during the Cold War had complex security implications. On one hand, sports competitions served as a valve for releasing geopolitical tensions, enabling symbolic competition instead of direct confrontation. On the other hand, sports encounters often further inflamed nationalistic feelings and antagonisms, especially when they were accompanied by controversies and perceptions of unfair judging. Sports rivalries also created risks of incidents and security crises, especially at major international competitions. The terrorist attack on Israeli athletes during the Olympic Games in Munich in 1972, although not directly related to Cold War tensions, demonstrated the vulnerability of major sporting events and led to a significant intensification of security measures at all future competitions (Wolff, 2002). Also, major sporting competitions are subject to terrorist attacks (Munich massacre) but also to a whole range of other acts aimed, among other things, at attacking the constitutional order of the respective state (Knežević, 2024). However, there is a huge number of successful examples that science and faith can coexist (Knežević, 2024a).

6. LEGACY OF COLD WAR DIPLOMACY IN THE CONTEMPORARY CONTEXT

6.1. Transformation of sports diplomacy after the Cold War

The end of the Cold War and the dissolution of the Soviet Union in 1991 marked a new era in sports diplomacy. The disappearance of the bipolar structure of the international system eliminated the ideological framework that had dominated sports diplomacy in previous decades. However, the politicization of sport did not disappear – it only changed its forms and manifestations (Levermore & Budd, 2004). In the post-Cold War era, sports diplomacy became an instrument used by various actors for different purposes: from traditional states seeking to improve their international image, through international organizations using sport to promote development goals, to multinational corporations using sporting events for global marketing (Levermore & Budd, 2004).

The organization of major sporting events, such as the Olympic Games and the World Cup in football, became an even more important element of national branding strategies and projecting “soft power.” Developing countries and emerging economies such as China, Brazil, South Africa, and Qatar actively sought to organize prestigious sporting events as a way of demonstrating their growing international status and attracting global attention (Grix & Lee, 2013).

6.2. Continuity of sport politicization in the contemporary context

Despite transformations, many patterns of sport politicization established during the Cold War continue to exist in modified forms. The most important sporting events are still arenas for projecting national prestige and demonstrating systemic efficiency. The Olympic Games in Beijing in 2008 were often compared to the Olympic Games in Moscow in 1980 as an example of using sport to legitimize a political system and demonstrate national power (Brownell, 2008).

Boycotts and political pressures remain part of sports diplomacy, although less frequently in the form of complete boycotts as seen during the Cold War. Instead, diplomatic boycotts (where politicians refuse to attend events, but athletes participate), demands for relocating competitions from countries with problematic human rights, and pressures on sponsors to withdraw from controversial events are common (Cottrell & Nelson, 2010).

Sports successes continue to be instrumentalized for purposes of building national pride and cohesion. However, the globalization of sport and increased mobility of athletes complicate this process, creating situations where the successes of emigrants or naturalized athletes become the subject of complex identity negotiations (Bairner, 2001).

7. CONCLUSION

Sports diplomacy during the Cold War represented a complex phenomenon with significant implications for international security. As an arena of symbolic competition between opposing ideological blocs, sport was often instrumentalized for purposes of projecting national power and prestige. The boycotts of the Olympic Games in Moscow and Los Angeles represented dramatic manifestations of the politicization of sport and its connection with broader geopolitical tensions. At the same time, sports diplomacy paradoxically served as a channel for dialogue and de-escalation of tensions in a period when other diplomatic channels were blocked. “Ping-pong diplomacy” between the US and China demonstrated the transformative potential of sports contacts in opening diplomatic possibilities that had far-reaching security implications. The experience of Cold War sports diplomacy left a lasting influence on the dynamics of relations between sport, politics, and security. Many patterns of sport instrumentalization established during this period continue to shape contemporary international relations, adapting to the new global context. Sporting events still represent arenas for demonstrating national prestige and projecting “soft power,” while simultaneously serving as platforms for international cooperation and dialogue. The best legacy of Cold War sports diplomacy perhaps lies precisely in its demonstration of

the ambivalent potential of sport – as an instrument that can both deepen antagonisms and build bridges of understanding. In today’s complex security environment, this lesson remains relevant for understanding and managing the relationship between sport, diplomacy, and international security.

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POLICE MANAGEMENT

MANAGEMENT OF POLICE ORGANIZATION ADMINISTRATIVE APPARATUS THROUGH TOTAL QUALITY MANAGEMENT

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Abstract: This paper explores the possibilities of managing the administrative apparatus of police organizations through the application of total quality management as an imperative for understanding business processes within police organizations. Total quality management represents a new concept of quality management that achieves better business excellence of the organization. In this regard, the essence of this paper relates to researching the possibilities of managing the administrative apparatus of police organizations based on total quality management. The specificities of this influence are not sufficiently known theoretically and practically, especially considering that there is very little literature or papers on this topic, which essentially constitutes what this research problematizes. Proposals for improving the business excellence of police organizations are based on quality management of the police organization's administrative apparatus, whose starting point is in applying the concept of total quality management, which would include clearly defined improvement measures, deadlines, and implementation carriers. The conclusions of theoretical research, as well as proposals for increasing the business excellence of police organizations, are aimed at practical measures, actions, and procedures of managers (leaders) at all organizational levels in introducing, maintaining, controlling, and improving the state of the total quality management system, with full involvement and participation of all employees. In addition to the above, the paper draws attention to the need for restructuring police organizations through restructuring business processes, without changing anything in the organizational structure of the police organization, by applying the concept of total quality

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management, i.e., the need to organize and implement courses and other forms of training for police officers and other employed personnel, especially police managers (leaders) at all management levels in police organizations.

Keywords: management, organization, quality, administration, police, management, excellence.

1. INTRODUCTION

The modern world in the field of service provision is experiencing profound changes that create the foundations of a new business culture and establish new criteria for business success. In today's time, when we observe many organizations in our immediate environment and beyond, we notice their inability to keep pace with the high tempo of changes in their own environment imposed by market globalization, development of information technologies and communication systems, lifestyle changes, etc. The imperative of every organization's business, whether in the private or public sector, or organizations within the state administration system, is success, which can be interpreted differently in different organizations. Police organizations are not an isolated system within the social community that is immune to changes from the business environment and whose purpose is existence for its own sake. On the contrary, police organizations are part of an integrated state administration system that has a primary role in protecting the social community from negative influences and phenomena in the domain of security and protection. Starting from the fact that the administration of the police organization is an integral part of public administration in the state administration system, it can be concluded that the problem is not in the lack of competent people, but in the misunderstanding of changes and insufficient application of adequate management tools that should unite people in the police organization to achieve better business excellence. Current discussions about the quality of services provided to users do not represent a revolution in thinking since service quality has been considered a good argument in light of business excellence for many years. Quality is a planetary and social phenomenon of our time. The new concept of quality represents a new philosophy of business and life aimed at long-term survival and development. At the same time, quality represents a very complex and demand-

ing concept in management theory and practice. The modern world in the field of service provision, technology, organization, and management has been experiencing turbulent and profound changes in recent decades. Modern business brings new rules, new methods, and new people, while changes themselves create the foundations of a new business culture and new criteria for business success. Therefore, it is no coincidence that the 21st century is said to be the century of changes (Karadža, 2014:1-4). The saying (Janićijević, 2004:1) “Everything changes, only changes are constant” best speaks about the character and significance of changes. The key to these changes in police organizations lies in fundamental changes in understanding the concept of quality, the importance of quality, and the police organization’s tendency toward total quality management.

Total quality management is a special managerial concept whose essence lies in changing business processes and improving mutual relationships between business processes to improve the overall quality of the police organization. This concept does not represent a specific, permanent, and stable state, but a way of working that assumes constant improvement and various adjustments. Total quality management is a program of organizational changes through which the organization of the business system is transformed from a bureaucratically arranged structure into a flexible team organization based on business processes.

The current state in police organizations in Bosnia and Herzegovina is such that it cannot be said there is no room for improvement, especially when it comes to providing direct services to citizens. But equally, their social significance cannot be overlooked, considering they perform significant delegated tasks of state administration, which can directly affect the slowing or hindering of processes in other spheres of society. To be effective, police organizations must have built-in feedback mechanisms such as quality controls and checks (inspections), quality prevention, and quality assurance. Through controls and quality checks, deviations from established requirements are measured and corrective measures are initiated. By eliminating identified non-conformities, implementing corrective and preventive measures, and constantly reviewing the state of the quality management system, the consistency of services provided by the police organization’s administration to service users will be ensured.

The effectiveness and efficiency of internal processes of the police organization, especially its administrative part, can be expressed through quantification through measures: length of time processing user service requests, percentage of unresolved cases within the deadline relative to the total number of unresolved cases, number of annulled decisions in second-instance proceedings, state of implementation of planned strategic and operational projects, as well as through efficiency indicators of organizational units of the police organization. A special subsystem of the total quality management system in police organizations would be an adequately established information system. The information system should have quality applications, purposeful databases, and quality mutual information connections. In addition, the information system should improve the quality of the police organization's operations (Rakić & Vejnović, 2006) by enabling management requirements to be more complex, identification of causes and deviations more refined, reporting at time intervals adapted to management needs, as well as harmonizing relations between organizational elements and integrating the forces of individual goals by introducing a total quality management system, and its constant maintenance and improvement.

The state of quality in the service provision process in police organizations of Bosnia and Herzegovina and Western Balkan countries has not been sufficiently researched and assessments supported by facts cannot be given. Therefore, the social significance of research in this paper is reflected in the fact that participants in services provided by the police organization (users and administrative staff in police organizations providing services) are presented with information about the importance of quality in the service provision process and the impact of quality on services.

Police organizations seem insufficiently aware that in the future, without appropriate quality of delivered services, they will not be able to successfully ensure the continuity of their business processes. The current state is such that the attitude toward quality in the service provision process, most often, does not meet the requirements of modern business and is based on a traditional approach to quality in the strictest sense. Service users demand significantly higher standards when it comes to

their satisfaction. Such an approach puts quality in a subordinate position relative to other parameters that determine the police organization as a service provider considered when making final decisions in the service process, such as: delivery deadline, guarantees, payment conditions and methods, etc. Certified police organizations will be more ready to achieve business excellence compared to non-certified ones.

2. INEFFICIENCY OF THE EXISTING ADMINISTRATIVE APPARATUS OF POLICE ORGANIZATIONS

Taking into account the fact that the administrative apparatus is one of the main pillars of every state, including Bosnia and Herzegovina and other countries from its immediate and wider surroundings, it can certainly be concluded that the efficiency and functionality of the administrative apparatus largely determine the state's position itself. Countries in transition face a whole series of problems, and one of them is the transformation of the administrative apparatus at all levels of government, including that which is an integral part of the police organization. The current administrative apparatus in the police organization is such that it largely does not enable adequate and efficient provision of services to citizens. Police administrative apparatuses are complex, oversized, very often do not keep pace with technological development, especially computer technology, and are dominated by the political influence of the ruling party or ruling coalition (Karadža, 2014:21-23).

According to research conducted by the Center for the Promotion of Civil Society of Bosnia and Herzegovina based in Sarajevo, covering the time period from 1996 to 2014, there is a whole series of obstacles that can be singled out as hindering more efficient work of the public administration apparatus, of which the police organization is an integral part, and the most important are: distrust between ruling political parties (especially those political parties that consider themselves the main and only representatives of constituent peoples) which negatively affects the work and functioning of the police, the competence of managing managers is at a very low level due to not possessing certain knowledge, abilities, and skills for managing the administrative apparatus of the police

organization, and the inability to implement necessary reforms imposed in the process of European integration. The leading international organization dealing with human rights protection, Transparency International (TI), almost daily highlights the problem of corruption in the public administration of Bosnia and Herzegovina. Based on research from 2005 conducted by the European Commission for all Western Balkan countries, Bosnia and Herzegovina was positioned in the penultimate place, with only Serbia being worse.

It is completely clear to most today that the existing public administration at entity and state levels is not able to implement necessary changes imposed in the process of European integration. Although the problem of public administration has been known for more than fifteen years, none of the domestic political leaders has launched a significant initiative for public administration reform. The current public administration reform process did not come from within but was unfortunately initiated by the international community. Hoping to achieve the economic standard of the European Union, the Council of Ministers of Bosnia and Herzegovina adopted the Declaration on Accession to the European Union in 1999, creating preconditions for Bosnia and Herzegovina's inclusion in the stabilization and association process with the European Union. However, even after Bosnia and Herzegovina decided on integration into the European Union, the authorities in Bosnia and Herzegovina did not understand the role and importance of public administration in fulfilling obligations on the path of European integration. Believing they could achieve all goals necessary for the country's accession to the European Union without changing the way public administration functions, until the end of 2003, the authorities in Bosnia and Herzegovina neglected the need for radical public administration reform (Local Self-Government, 2005:88).

According to the European Commission document (Bosnia and Herzegovina-Country Strategy Paper 2002-2006), despite the public promise to begin strong reform in the field of public administration, little happened in real life. Except for partial progress made in the field of internal affairs.

3. TRANSITION - THE KEY REASON CAUSING THE NEED FOR NEW ORGANIZATION OF POLICE ORGANIZATION ADMINISTRATION

In Bosnia and Herzegovina, public administration is struggling to “find its way” that it should have in the constitutional-legal system based on the European Charter. After the fall of the communist system and the cessation of existence of two world blocs, there was a process of democratic penetration in a broader sense, as well as the birth of new states arising from that system.

Each of these countries (Slovenia, Croatia, Macedonia, and Czech Republic) embarked on a transition process that implies adaptation to new institutional socio-cultural rules of an open market economy. In addition, the transition period includes a multi-party system, regular elections at state and local levels. Transition in Central Europe and the Balkans began with democratic elections, which represents a basic condition for the decentralization process and establishment of a legal public administration system. After 1989, a dramatic period ensued for some Eastern European countries, where instead of democratization, wars broke out between and within individual states. In those states, the transition process began after the war, which certainly slowed their development of the public administration system as a whole. Ethnic conflicts and internal tensions were mainly obstacles to faster decentralization of regions and faster development of democratic institutions. Due to the very complex situation in individual states, these processes are difficult to implement, and the help of international organizations is very important. In almost every country in the region, the European Charter on Local Self-Government has played a major role in initiating the most important reforms. Administrative reform and reform of police organization administration and police organizations as a whole are closely connected and represent a reform package that includes a large number of administrative changes as well as new legislation and includes all three goals of administrative reform: democracy, efficiency, and fairness. In economic theory, two models of managing the national economy are known. The first is central direction, which includes the use of coercion and the totalitarian role of the state. The sec-

ond is voluntary coordination and cooperation of individuals through the market. Between the methods of central-planned coordination and free coordination of individuals through the market, all socialist economies chose the former (Karadža, 2014:26).

Transition is a process of changes that substantively encompasses all parts of the social and economic system, including the arrangement of the state community, whose basic goals are establishing conditions for the free functioning of the economy, with the existence of democratic institutions necessary for the unhindered development of the market economy. The necessity of economic transition in Bosnia and Herzegovina to market foundations arose from the fact that the Constitution normalized the market system of economic activity and that the existing state and relations in production flows were not compatible with the constitutional determination of the nature of Bosnia and Herzegovina's economic system. Precisely following the general elements of the economic system, key points of economic transition are recognized that result in changes in ownership structure, organization, and direction of economic flows, as well as the innovated economic role of the state. The basic and first step in the transition process is changing the ownership structure of state organizations and their privatization. The following steps are changing fiscal policy, liberalization, and creating a legal framework for free engagement in business activities, both for domestic and foreign companies, as well as deregulation and reducing the state's role in creating restrictions that hindered the development of market mechanisms. The fundamental determinant of the transition process of the economy is privatization. The question arises why this is so. The answer lies in the numerous advantages and qualities that private ownership has compared to other forms. These advantages are expressed in all spheres of society's life and work, with the most numerous being in the economic sphere. Namely, privatization brings numerous economic benefits that can be viewed from macroeconomic and microeconomic aspects.

Based on the above statements, the essential question can be posed: what is happening with police organizations in transition processes? The answer is simple. Police organizations are not an isolated and untouchable part of the social community that could remain immune to changes

in the environment. With the breakup of the former SFRY, the Federal Secretariat for Internal Affairs and Republican Secretariats for Internal Affairs in the republics ceased to exist. Ministries of internal affairs were formed, headed by a minister who belongs to a certain political party or coalition of parties that constitute the ruling structure. The terms “militia” and “militiaman” were replaced with the expressions “police” and “policeman”. However, apart from “cosmetic” changes, not much has changed in principle in the way police organization administrations function, which have remained bureaucratic, sluggish, often inefficient, and partially expensive. Therefore, along with the obvious need to accelerate economic activities that would lead to new production, investments, employment, and exports, there is also an unavoidable need to transform the consciousness of employees in public administration, i.e., police organizations. Government institutions at the state level, including police organizations, strive to provide equal conditions for everyone who wants to be involved in the development of the social community, whether it’s about creating economic prerequisites, protecting the life and health of citizens, or personal and property security of people. Given the above, it can be concluded that the administrative apparatus of police organizations, with its efficiency and effectiveness, should not hinder the improvement of economic activities and democratization of society. On the contrary, the administrative apparatus of police organizations should transform into a citizen service whose basic characteristics would be: 1) speed of serving service users according to requests, 2) efficiency, 3) effectiveness, 4) economy, and 5) unnecessary delays.

4. IMPACT OF THE ENVIRONMENT ON POLICE ORGANIZATIONS

Since police organization administrations are oriented toward the environment, both in terms of acquiring inputs and valorizing outputs, it is primarily important that they base their developmental behavior on understanding and anticipating factors that will determine their business environment. Namely, opportunities and threats for the operations of police organization administrations are created in the environment, and it

is relevant to respond through the process of analysis and prediction (diagnosis and prognosis) to the question of where we are now and where we could be considering the development of the situation on the front of contact points with the environment. From this, it follows that every police organization administration and the entire police organization is in interaction with its environment on which it is very dependent: from it, it receives materials, energy, personnel, finances, and it consumes products and services that the organization provides. Environmental analysis of police organization administrative apparatus provides key information for all phases of strategic decision-making, starting from setting appropriate goals, through formulating, evaluating, and selecting strategic alternatives, implementing the chosen strategy, and evaluating achieved effects. The basic characteristic of the police organization administrative apparatus environment is changeability. If the police organization's administrative apparatus does not have reliable, significant, accurate, timely, and as complete as possible information about the environment, the police organization will not be able to clearly understand that environment and predict its changes. In that case, it is likely that the strategy chosen by the police organization's administrative apparatus will not be in accordance with situational factors, which can be fatal for its survival. Police organizations that want to survive and adapt to the environment, as well as actively determine their future, are inevitably directed toward continuous analysis of the relevant and macro environment. The environment of police organizations always contains uncertainty, but for some police organizations, uncertainty is significantly greater than for others. Environmental uncertainty of police organizations actually means that police organization managers do not have enough information about situational factors significant for the administrative apparatus to make effective decisions. Environmental uncertainty is determined by the degree of complexity and degree of environmental stability. Environmental complexity refers to the number of external elements or forces that are significant for the police organization's administrative apparatus. In a simple environment, the police organization's administrative apparatus interacts with a small number of significant external elements, and in a complex one with a large number of external elements. Environmental stability concerns the

question of whether significant environmental elements are dynamic and constantly changing or are stable, relatively constant. Some part of the environment is considered stable if it remains unchanged over a period of several months or even years. The police organization's environment can be divided into four levels: macro environment, relevant environment, industry, and "task environment". The macro environment (general police organizations) includes areas of social, economic, technological, and political factors that affect the functioning of the police organization and its development. The term "relevant environment" denotes only that part of the general environment of a police organization that contains factors and circumstances directly significant for the life and functioning of the police organization. The relevant environment includes: industry or competitive environment and task environment. Environmental factors at the industry level directly, though in different ways and to different extents, affect all competitive organizations, including police organizations. The task environment is narrower than the competitive environment and refers to service users, suppliers, and competitive organizations that constitute the most immediate environment of the police organization (Karadža, 2014:27-28).

5. ANALYSIS OF THE POLICE ORGANIZATION'S MACRO ENVIRONMENT

For each police organization to be able to use environmental resources individually, it is necessary to be able to successfully analyze its macro environment (Karadža, 2014:28-29):

- The social segment of the macro environment consists of demographic facts (population size, age structure, ethnic composition, etc.), facts about the population's lifestyle (composition and type of households, education, work, consumer needs, etc.) and facts about values (intellectual, political, economic, aesthetic, social, religious),
- The economic environment refers to the nature and changes (structural, developmental, and cyclical) of the economy in which the police organization's administrative apparatus functions. This includes: the general state of the economy, interest rate levels, unemployment rate,

gross domestic product growth rate, national income growth rate, industrial production growth rate, and other indicators,

- The political environment refers to political opportunities in society that positively or negatively affect the functioning of the police organization that leading people in the police organization have or do not have. Legal regulations - at state, entity, and local levels have an exceptionally large impact on the business and development of the police organization,

- The technological environment includes the application of fundamental and applied scientific knowledge with the aim of increasing the efficiency of human practical actions in all spheres of life and work. Analysis of this segment of the organization's environment is focused on the level and direction of technological progress and improvements achieved including: new inventions, products, services, and processes,

- The ecological environment includes all natural factors and influences that can be manifested from the immediate surroundings, primarily the quality of living space,

- The organizational environment on the police organization has an influence arising from its position in relation to other organizations that have related, similar, or identical business activities, as it provides an opportunity to learn from those better than oneself, and

- The managerial environment includes the application of managerial knowledge, techniques, and methods in managing a complex organization such as the police. For the administrative apparatus of police organizations to be successful, it is necessary to identify, monitor, project, and evaluate changes in its macro environment.

Macro environment analysis includes (Karadža, 2014:29):

- Observing the environment to discover changes that are underway and those just emerging,

- Monitoring trends and tendencies in macro environment changes,

- Predicting future directions of macro environment changes, and

- Evaluating changes and drawing conclusions about their possible effects on the organization.

For environmental observation, important questions are (Karadža, 2014:29):

- Which areas of the macro environment are most significant for the organization?
- What are the existing and emerging trends in those areas?
- What are the indicators of those trends?

In observing the macro environment, it is necessary to determine the scope of analysis and select appropriate data sources; select the most significant variables to be studied and appropriate indicators whose values will be monitored, supervised, predicted, and evaluated. Monitoring results should enable: identifying phenomena and trends in the macro environment that should be observed and monitored, and predicting new phenomena and changes in the macro environment. Prediction attempts to project the scope, direction, speed, and magnitude of changes in the macro environment, so accordingly (Karadža, 2014:29-30):

- in the social segment: macro environment predicts: demographic structure in the next two to three decades, changes in the population's lifestyle and changes in societal values;
- in the economic segment: inflation level in the next three years, which industries will grow and which will decline in the next decade, etc., structural changes in the economy; investment movements, import-export ratio and investments in industry,
- in the political segment: which political parties will lose and which will gain power, changes in state policy,
- in the legal segment: changes in legislation and regulations,
- in the technological segment: what could be new applications of existing technologies,
- in the ecological segment: which environmental changes would directly or indirectly affect the functioning of the police organization,
- in the organizational segment: how changes in other similar, related, or identical organizations would affect the police organization, and
- in the managerial segment: what the environment offers in terms of managerial potentials and personnel significant for the functioning of the police organization.

Evaluation here means attempting to assess why and how current and predicted macro environment changes can affect the strategic management of the police organization's administrative apparatus and what their effects will be in the future (Knežević, 2024). In other words, attempts are made to derive implications of previous, current, and anticipated macro environment changes for the functioning of police organizations. It is important to provide a model of organizational management of the police organization's administrative apparatus that is applicable to all police organizations (Karadža, 2014:30).

Information obtained through strategic control enables (Karadža, 2014:31):

- Improving the implementation of the chosen strategy,
- Evaluating strategic alternatives and selecting a strategy for implementation,
- Evaluating the chosen strategy,
- Reformulating set goals,
- Understanding the advantages and disadvantages of the relevant and macro environment of the organization,
- Better understanding of the strengths and weaknesses of the organization itself and its individual parts, and
- Reformulating the organization's mission and philosophy.

For evaluation, important questions are (Karadža, 2014:31):

- How can macro environment changes affect the police organization's administrative apparatus? (What general effects on the economy are expected? Will new services appear? strategies of other administrative apparatuses or services in the state administration system (competitors)? etc.);
- How do macro environment changes affect the existing strategy of the police organization's administrative apparatus (on set organizational goals, administrative apparatus of the police organization (on set organizational goals, on existing services...)?
- How can macro environment changes affect the selection and implementation of future organizational strategies (on possible strategy

selection criteria, on the way of competing with competitors, on possible new services, on potential new service users, on the need for a new organizational structure, on the need for new work processes, etc.)?

Observation, monitoring, prediction, and evaluation in macro environment analysis are not separate phases but interconnected activities. The process of macro environment analysis is deprived of purposefulness if the results obtained by that analysis do not serve as a basis for making strategic decisions and undertaking strategic actions. Expectations from changes in the macro environment (Knežević, 2024) and preparations for them must be integrated; changes must be managed, goals and alternative actions for achieving them must be assessed, possible consequences of alternative actions must be examined, resources must be allocated for implementing the selected alternative.

6. CONCLUSION

For long-term success in the work of the police organization's administrative apparatus, the introduction and implementation of a strategic management model is crucial, to guarantee quality, transparent, and efficient service to service users and all other institutions. This is the basic value of the management system according to TQM methodology aimed at meeting the needs of service users, i.e., citizens. In the administrative apparatus of the police organization, it is not important to look for someone to blame for caused mistakes, but the essence is how to systematically prevent such mistakes from recurring in the future.

However, introducing a management model for the police organization's administrative apparatus according to TQM methodology has no alternative. According to Prof. Majstorović (2000), the basic rule in TQM states: "Nothing in the organization is so good that it couldn't be even better." TQM truly has no end, only the beginning is important, management of the police organization's administrative apparatus and great enthusiasm of individuals guarantee the success of introducing and implementing the management model of the police organization's administrative apparatus, otherwise, if we work as we always have, we will get what we always got, which is almost the same result with small up-down oscillations.

Management of police organizations in countries in transition has faced serious problems. Irrationality and inefficiency of the police organization's administrative apparatus are burning problems they face through negative public perception. Often, police organizations with their administrative apparatuses are cumbersome, sluggish, and expensive, which is reflected in unnecessary time losses created for service users (natural and legal persons), causing dissatisfaction for both.

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